

***Vertical demos over Common large scale field Trials
for Rail, energy and media Industries***

D4.3 Field Trials as showcase events and vertical business validation

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Executive Summary

5G-VICTORI carries out large scale field trials for use case (UC) verification in 5G environments in support for a number of Vertical Industries including **Transportation, Energy, Media and Factories of the Future**, as well as some specific UCs involving cross-Vertical interaction. The ICT-17 5G facilities have been extended for this purpose and deployed in operational environments. The target Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are in this document evaluated in those environments seeking for performance validation of the vertical services, in addition to the validation and enhancement of the 5G capabilities and coverage by the 5G facilities.

All four 5G-VICTORI facilities emerge from a common flexible 5G network architecture defined in earlier deliverables, which is built up following the standard 5G architectural approaches, i.e. ETSI, 3GPP, IEEE and Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN), provided with additional innovative features that are in all cases in accordance to the the common flexible 5G-VICTORI overarching architecture described in the 5G-VICTORI deliverable **D2.4**. These facilities (Patras, Berlin, Bristol, FR/RO) do offer different flavors of 5G implementations in terms of maturity, flexibility and performance, but all of them are integrating the 5G-VICTORI developments that allow the interconnection from one another.

This document takes as reference the KPIs defined in **WP2** and are an extension and continuation of the work reported in the 5G-VICTORI deliverable **D4.2**. In this case, the main focus is on the field trials that have been executed and showcased during the last year of the project. Each of the facilities instantiate different of 5G deployment options.

In this document, all trials are carried out in operational environments and not only reports intra-cluster trials but also two inter-cluster activities, which leverage the common framework that materialises this alignment, i.e. the 5G-VICTORI Operation System (5G-VIOS). This deliverable provides as well optimisation and improvements to the obtained KPIs.

1 Acronyms

1.1 General

Acronym	Description
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
4G	a.k.a. Long Term Evolution (LTE)
4K	Same as UHD, using resolution 3840 x 2160 pixels
5G	Fifth Generation cellular system (3GPP related)
5G NR	5G New Radio
5G-VIOS	5G-VICTORI Operation System
5QI	5G NR Standardized QoS Identifier
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AP	Access Point
API	Application Programming Interface
APN	Access Point Name
AR	Augmented Reality
ARP	Allocation and Retention Priority
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
BBU	Baseband Unit
BE	Best Effort
BSCW	The document server used in the 5G-VICTORI project
CCS	Cambridge Communications Systems
CCTV	Closed Circuit TV
CDN	Content Delivery Network
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf
CPE	Customer Premises Equipment
CPRI	Common Public Radio Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CN	Core Network
DCU	Data Capture Unit
DL	Downlink
DMVPN	Dynamic Multipoint VPN
DN	Data Network
DNN	Data Network Name
DRB	Data Radio Bearer
e2e	End-to-End
EF	Expedited Forwarding, DHCP related
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
eNB	Evolved Node B
EMS	Energy Management System
FRMCS	Future Rail Mobile Communication System
FTP	File Transfer Protocol

GBR	Guaranteed Bit Rate
GIS	Geographic Information System
gNB	gNodeB, new base station that goes with NR
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphics processing unit
GW	Gateway
HPN	High-Performance Networks group
HSS	Home Subscriber Server
i2SM	i2CAT's Slicing Management
ICM	Inter-domain Connectivity Manager
IMPU	SIP Core Identity
IMS	IP Multimedia Subsystem
IMSI	International Mobile Subscriber Identity
IP	Internet Protocol
iPerf	Measurement tool, can be downloaded here .
K8s	Kubernetes
LAA	Licensed-Assisted Access (5G related)
LAN	Local Area Network
LLC	Last Level Cache
LoS	Line-of-Sight
LTE	Long Term Evolution (4G)
LTE-A	LTE Advanced
LTE-M	LTE-Machine Type Communication (MTC)
M-MIMO	Massive MIMO with beamforming
MaaS	Mobility as a Service
MAC	Medium Access Control
MANO	Management and orchestration
MBB	Mobile BroadBand
MC	Mission Critical
MCDData	Mission Critical service Data
MCPTT	Mission Critical service PTT
MCS	Modulation and Coding Scheme
MCVideo	Mission Critical service Video
MCX	Mission Critical Services, X = {MCPTT, MCDData, MCVideo}
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communications
mmWave	Frequency band 24 GHz to 100 GHz
MOCN	Multi-Operator Core Network
MPEG-SAND	Moving Picture Experts Group Server and Network Assisted DASH
MPLS	Multiprotocol Label Switching
MR	Media Router
MRF	Multimedia Resource Function
M Shed	Museum in Bristol
NBMP	Network Based Media Processing

NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NUC	Next Unit Computing
MVB	Merchant Venturers Building
N78	3500 MHz TDD band (3300 – 3800 MHz)
NB-IoT	Narrow Band Internet of Things
NetOS	Zeetta Automate
NR	New Radio (5G related)
NS	Network Service
NSA	Non-Standalone
OAI	OpenAirInterface
OB	Onboard
OCC	Operation Control Center
ONAP	Open Network Automation Platform
OpenMNT	Open Mobile Network Toolchain
O-RAN	Open RAN
OSM	Open Source MANO
P-CSCF	Proxy Call Session Control Function
PCF	Policy Control Function
PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol
PDN	Packet Data Network
PDU	Protocol Data Unit
PHY	Physical layer
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
PoE	Power over Ethernet
PP	Probe Pair
PTMP	Point-to-MultiPoint
PTT	Push-To-Talk
QCI	QoS Class identifier
QFI	QoS Flow Identifier
RAMS	Reliability, Availability, Maintainability & Safety
RAN	Radio Access Network
RaSTA	Rail Safe Transport Application
RAT	Radio Access Technology, like 4G, 5G, Wi-Fi
RLC	Radio Link Control
RMS	Railway Management System
RRH	Remote Radio Head
RRU	Radio Remote Unit
RS	Rail Signaling
RS485	Serial balanced bus
RSRP	Received Strength Reference Power
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
RTT	Round Trip Time
SA	Stand Alone

SD	Slice Differentiator
SDN	Software Defined Network
SDR	Software Defined Radio
SDS	Short Data Service
SGX	Software Guard Extensions (Intel® SGX)
SIM	Subscriber Identification Module
SIP	Session Initiation Protocol
SLAM	Simultaneous localization and mapping
SMF	Session management Function
SNMP	Simple Network Management Protocol
S-NSSAI	Single Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
SRA	Shared Resource Allocation
SSID	Service Set IDentifier (Wi-Fi related)
SST	Service Slice Type
TAP	Test Access Point
TDD	Time Division Duplex
TOBA	Telecom On-Board Architecture
TOC	Table Of Content
UC	Use-Case
UDM	Unified Data Management
UE	User Equipment
UHD	Ultra-High Definition (TV or computer screens)
UL	Uplink
UPF	User Plane Function
uRLCC	ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
USRP	Universal Software Radio Peripheral
VIOS	VICTORI Infrastructure Operating System (see D2.5)
VLAN	Virtual LAN
VM	Virtual Machine, e.g. using VMware
VNF	Virtual Network Functions
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VR	Virtual Reality
VSI	Vertical Service Instance
Wi-Fi	IEEE 802.11
WTC	We The Curious

1.2 5G-VICTORI specific acronyms, partners and related EU projects

Acronym	Description
5G-EVE	Alba Iulia ICT-19 Cluster (e)
5G-UK	The Bristol ICT-19 Cluster (u)
5G-VINNI	The Patras ICT-19 Cluster (v)
5GENESIS	The Berlin ICT-19 Cluster (g)
5G-PPP	5G infrastructure Public Private Partnership

ADMIE	Aka IPTO , Independent Power Transmission Operator (5G-VICTORI Partner)
AIM	Alba Iulia Municipality (5G-VICTORI Partner)
Alstom	Bombardier Transportation Sweden AB has from January 22 2023 changed its name to ALSTOM Rail Sweden AB, but keeps the same registration number and VAT number as before.
COSM	COSMOTE (5G-VICTORI Partner)
DBH	Deutsche Bahn Holding (5G-VICTORI Partner)
DBN	DB Netz (5G-VICTORI Partner)
DCAT	Digital Catapult (5G-VICTORI Partner)
EUR	Eurecom (5G-VICTORI Partner)
FhG	Fraunhofer FOKUS (5G-VICTORI Partner)
ICT-17	The 5G platform developed for the 5G-PICTURE EU project
ICT-19	The 5G platform developed for the 5G-VICTORI
I2CAT	I2CAT Foundation (5G-VICTORI partner)
IASA	Institute of Accelerating Systems and Applications (5G-VICTORI partner)
ICOM	Intracom S.A. Telecom Solutions (5G-VICTORI partner)
IHP	IHP - Leibniz-Institut für innovative Mikroelektronik (5G-VICTORI partner)
IR	Interim Review
IZT	<i>Institut für Zukunftsstudien und Technologiebewertung gemeinnützige GmbH</i> (5G-VICTORI partner)
KCC	Kontron Transportation Austria (5G-VICTORI Partner)
MATI	Mativision Limited (5G-VICTORI partner)
M Shed	Museum in Bristol
MVB	Merchant Venturers Building
Orange	Orange France (5G-VICTORI partner)
ORO	Orange Romania (5G-VICTORI partner)
PXI	PaxLife Innovations (5G-VICTORI partner)
RBB	<i>Rundfunk Berlin-Brandenburg</i> (5G-VICTORI partner)
TRAINOSE	TrainOSE S.A. (5G-VICTORI partner)
UHA	Urban Hawk Limited (5G-VICTORI partner)
UNIVBRIS	University of Bristol (5G-VICTORI partner)
UoP	University of Patras (5G-VICTORI partner)
UTH	University of Thessaly (5G-VICTORI partner)
WP2	Work Package 2: Description – Use cases/ Specifications
WP3	Work Package 3: Vertical Services to be demonstrated
WP4	Work Package 4: Trials of Coexisting Vertical Services, validation and KPI evaluation
ZN OR Zeetta	Zeetta Networks Ltd. (5G-VICTORI partner)

2 Introduction

5G-VICTORI **WP4** “Trials of Coexisting Vertical Services, validation and KPI evaluation” focuses on coordinating and conducting large scale field trials for use case (UC) verification in 5G operational environments for a number of verticals, including **Transportation, Energy, Media** and **Factories of the Future** as well as some specific UCs involving **cross-vertical** interaction. To achieve the above scope, the trials are being executed at vertical facility sites that deployed 5G infrastructures that have been enhanced throughout the duration of the project. All the facilities are developed accordance to the common flexible 5G-VICTORI overarching architecture described in past 5G-VICTORI deliverables.

This deliverable reports on the results that stem from the field trials executed between 2022 and 2023 in all four 5G-VICTORI infrastructures in the context of Work Package 4 (**WP4**). Each individual project facility reports on its final results for all UCs that were initially outlined in the project description. Additionally, this deliverable also presents field trials that are executed between clusters making use of the 5G-VICTORI Operation System (5G-VIOS).

2.1 Objectives

This deliverable reports on the field trials that have taken place at each of the 5G-VICTORI clusters and across clusters making use of 5G-VIOS:

- Description of 5G facilities enhancements and extensions at vertical facility per cluster (Berlin, Patras, Bristol, Alba Iulia).
- 5G configuration and integration with vertical services.
- Field trials at the vertical facilities.
- KPI evaluation per use case per facility.

2.2 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this deliverable is to meet the following **WP4** objectives:

- Deployment of the vertical use cases in the 5G facility sites, taking input from **WP2** and **WP3**.
- Execution of the field trials in the operational environments, with the deployment of the vertical services in enhanced 5G infrastructures that have been instantiated in those environments.
- Validation of the vertical specific KPIs and optimisation.

Table 2-1 Dependencies with other 5G-VICTORI documents

id	Document Title	Relevance
D2.1 [1]	5G-VICTORI Use case and requirements definition and reference architecture for vertical services	This document presents the 5G-VICTORI UCs and their specific requirements (UC requirements, network performance requirements and functional requirements), as they are dictated by the associated vertical industries.
D2.3 [5]	Final individual site facility planning	The deliverable reports on the set of requirements and initial architecture blueprint for each of the sites and presents a high-level overview of the extensions planned for each of the sites. It also defines per site the timeline and progress of the associated upgrades of the required infrastructures.
D2.4 [6]	5G-VICTORI end-to-end reference architecture	5G-VICTORI e2e reference architecture and the way it has been deployed in all sites and facilities is described in this report. Integration activities and deployment

		activities follow the specific deliverable and testing is reported in deliverable D4.2.
D4.1 [1]	Field trials methodology and guidelines	The deliverable described in detail the methodology phases of the 5G-VICTORI experimentation and trials. Specifically, it puts emphasis on the co-design phases of this methodology and the procedures for adhering to the 5G-VICTORI architecture.
D4.2	Intra-Field trials integration and vertical services execution and KPI validation	This deliverable presents the 5G KPIs and the Vertical-specific KPIs validated against specific performance targets.
D3.1 [9], D3.3 [11], D3.5 [13]	D3.1 Preliminary Use case specification for transportation services D3.3 Preliminary Use case specification for Media Services D3.5 Preliminary Use case specification for Energy and Factories of the Future Services	These deliverables describe in detail all test cases that verify 5G-VICTORI applications and services per UC together with the test planning and roadmaps. This procedures are in line with the planning that takes place in deliverable D2.3.
D3.2 [10], D3.4 [12], D3.6 [14]	D3.2 Final Use case specification for transportation services D3.4 Final Use case specification for Media Services D3.6 Final Use case specification for Energy and Factories of the Future services	The deliverables describe in detail all final test cases and lab testing results that verify 5G-VICTORI applications and services per UC. They also entail the testing methodology.

2.1 Document Structure

This deliverable comprises five main sections, which follow a similar cluster-based structure content-wise: overall facility extension and description, initial integration and testing of facilities, 5G configuration and 5G-VICTORI architecture compatibility per cluster, and initial experiment results from the trials:

Section 3 focuses on the final field trials carried out at the Berlin Cluster for its three use cases.

Section 4 summarises the Patras Cluster field trials' results.

Section 5 details the final experiments and field trials carried out in the Bristol Cluster.

Section 6 describes the field trials from the France/Romania Cluster Facility.

Section 7 provides a summary of the inter-cluster trials carried out between Bristol-Patras and Bristol-Berlin.

Section 8 concludes the deliverable.

3 Field trials in Berlin

The 5G-VICTORI Berlin facility was introduced in deliverables [D2.2](#) [4] and [D2.3](#) [5] including the details of the sites and components that are part of the lab tests and the field trials. The owner of the operational environment and host partner for the field trials is the 5G-VICTORI Partner Deutsche Bahn Holding (**DBH**), who made available different sites (stations) for field testing, such as:

- *Berlin Hauptbahnhof* (aka Berlin Central Station), where the field trials for all Berlin UCs took place in September 2022, and
- the testfield S-Bahn Werk Berlin-Schöneeweide [9], where the **UC #3** field trials were carried out in 2022.

Two setups have been used for these lab tests and field tests during 2022. These are described in deliverable [D4.2](#) section 3.1 [2]. The IHP nomadic 5G setup was finally used to perform the trials and, in addition, this setup was used for testing and comparing mmWave and 5G as the track-to-train wireless communication for **UC #3**.

All in all, the field trials of the Berlin cluster took place at the Deutsche Bahn facility *S-Bahn Werk Schöneeweide* on April 26th, 2023. In this section we present the detailed network topology for the trials and the results stemming from these trials for the three Berlin cluster UCs: **UC #1.2**, **UC #1.3** and **UC #3**.

3.1 Detailed Network topology for the trials

The nomadic setup described in deliverable [D4.2](#) will be again used for the field trials, where the UCs tested are **UC #1.2** and **UC #1.3**. To test the deployment of these UCs in a real (operational) scenario, we agreed with **DBH** to use one of its depots in Berlin for the field trials.

The field trials at the *S-Bahn Werk Schöneeweide* made use of the same **IHP** 5G nomadic node used at Berlin Central Station with the following key differences to that setup:

- The core network, RAN, and USIMs were re-provisioned from PLMN ID **999 56** to PLMN ID **001 01** to circumvent issues with some UEs connecting to the 5G SA network.
- The **KCC** onboard gateway (OBG) was deployed on the train to create the on-board environment for the trials. The OBG provided a local network for the CCTV camera as well as a notebook running Keysight Hawkeye Probes. The OBG 5G module was connected over 5G NR to the 5G nomadic network.
- Several devices were deployed at the wayside tent (see Figure 3-1) with direct wired connectivity to the data network (DN). These were the Dispatcher Terminal as well as laptops running Hawkeye endpoints or consuming the on-board CCTV stream.
- The 5G nomadic node server was re-installed to run VMware ESXi. The same Open5GCore 5G Core Network was used, but run on a VM on the server. Kontron MCX data network services were also run in VMs on the nomadic node server (instead of running remotely), as depicted in Figure 3-2.
- Uplink to the Internet was provided by an LTE router using a public provider provided by **DBH**. Most end-to-end UCs did not use this link, however it was helpful as commercial Android phones have fewer issues when they are able to reach certain public Internet services.

Figure 3-1 Sketch of the network deployment at the S-Bahn Werk Schöneweide

Figure 3-2 Network topology based on Figure 3-3 in [2]

3.2 UC #1.2 “Digital Mobility”

3.2.1 Field trial description

Digital mobility’s goal is to validate cloud based large data processing services that real-time interact with end-users. Often the scale of the computing or its memory footprint make it difficult such services to run as pure front-end applications. The cloud-user interaction means massive data exchange that requires large bandwidth and low latency where 5G networks excel. Video streaming is the most traditional example, but this UC goes beyond that and focuses on Simulated Digital Twins (Urban Hawk – **UHA**) as well as in Extended Reality (XR) (Fraunhofer FOKUS – **FhG**). In the railway context they both deliver value for passengers, station management, and maintenance teams. Furthermore, usage of and changes within the digital twin, kept timestamped as historical data, lead to situational awareness, risk assessment and insurance vertical UCs.

3.2.1.1 Simulated Digital Twins

3.2.1.1.1 Building the digital twin

UHA used the latest mobile LiDAR unit (BLK2GO) of Leica Hexagon that they kindly provided pro bono for the trial. Berlin Central station (aka *Berlin Hauptbahnhof*) got 3D scanned in 5 centimeter resolution that resulted in vast point-cloud data (75 Gigabyte). The pointcloud was processed in **UHA**’s Polaron engine, voxelised, then merged with a 1 meter resolution OpenStreetmap map tile of the Berlin Central station and surroundings. The resulting hybrid model then was rendered and streamed from **UHA**’s GPU farm (back-end) to end user smartphones (front-end) via 5G under low latency.

The above hybrid model gives passengers and staff members better overview of the station interior, which is not part of traditional GIS datasets or maps. In addition, it can also reflect changes and

updates as they happen provided additional sensors stream from station to back-end where the local data gets merged into the overall model then rendered and streamed to front-end in real-time.

Figure 3-3 left: 5G smartphone view of the Berlin Central station twin; middle and right: browser view with communication details logged between the endpoints

Figure 3-4 left: voxelised view of Berlin Central station; right: walkable surfaces automatically classified and shown in red

Figure 3-5 Merged LiDAR and OpenStreetMap model; left: route planning before / top, and after / bottom protest, shown as dark spots on the double lane road next to station; right: computed cost-functions from every possible passenger location to the station lounge, summed up in a field

3.2.1.1.2 Data transfer

For both way streaming (front to back = user interaction and point-cloud scans of smaller areas that reflect change; and back to front = render experience) WebRTC was used. Video and data channels were established to facilitate the real-time multi-user experience. The 5G access point was via two 5G-enabled devices provided by FhG and a browser-equipped Notebook (to verify measurement details).

At multiple locations we were able to trigger different simulations depending on the edge and different use cases in order to show how the node connection could create contextually relevant experiences (e.g. See inside the station, share a scan or model, and pathfinding and semantic profiling of terrain - e.g. what is accessible for reduced mobility visitors to Berlin vs able bodied, as well as simulating road and path closures and other disruptive events like a protest building up in front of the station).

3.2.1.1 5G Edge Rendering

The high-level architecture of this UC is depicted in Figure 3-6. The 5G UE runs the client (5G Media App Client) inside a web browser without the need to install any application. Connected via an Ethernet cable to the 5G Nomadic Node described in deliverable D4.2 is an Edge Node (5G Media App Edge Server) realised by a gaming laptop (12th Gen Intel® Core™ i7-12800H @ max 4.8 GHz, 32.0 GB installed RAM, NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3070 Ti Laptop, GPU Memory 8 GB). The Edge Node and other components are depicted in Figure 3-7.

The Edge Node renders any 3D scene developed in Unity or Unreal Engine and streams the video/audio output in real-time to client via WebRTC media channel. Additionally, it sends performance metrics to a metrics server in a Central Cloud (5G Media App Cloud Server). The 5G Media App Edge Server runs three components in total: the 3D application it renders, a signalling server enabling the client to connect to the renderer, and a web server hosting the 5G Media App Client that the client can fetch and use.

Figure 3-6 5G Edge Rendering Architecture

Figure 3-7 Left: Edge Rendering Server (laptop at the edge of the table) connected to the nomadic 5G node, right: UE displaying the remotely rendered 3D application

3.2.2 Experiment and scenario descriptions

The next tables present **UC #1.2** experiment description for the different services.

Table 3-1 Experiment 1 – Digital Mobility 5G Edge Rendering (FhG)

	Description
ExperimentType	Edge Rendering Experiment using mobile (nomadic) 5G system deployed at Deutsche Bahn facility <i>S-Bahn Werk Schöneweide</i> in Berlin
Automated	Automated (after the setup is ready, the remotely rendered application collects and sends metrics data to a metrics server. When clients connect to the application, client-specific data is additionally reported to the server)
TestCases	RDFg01 RDFg02 RDFg03 RDFg04 RDFg05 RDFg06
UEs	iPhone 14 Pro, Nokia X20, Huawei P40 Pro, Google Pixel 6
Network Slice	Network Slicing not required
Network Services	Reliable/stable 5G connectivity with ultra low latency and very low jitter.
Network Scenario	A rendering client running on a 5G UE opens a WebRTC peer-to-peer media channel to a rendering server deployed on the edge of the 5G network. The rendering server is running on a gaming laptop connected to the mobile nomadic node as depicted in Figure 3-7. Once a WebRTC connection between the 5G UE and the Rendering server running on the Edge is established, video and audio packets are transmitted from the rendering server to the remote rendering client. Negligible control data is transmitted from the rendering client to the rendering server.
Exclusive Execution	True
ReservationTime	Multiple test runs were conducted for around 5 min each
Application	Edge Rendering
Performance targets & SLAs	Round-Trip-Time below 20 ms and Jitter below 5 ms
Experiment Parameters	N/A
Edges	The mobile nomadic setup with 5G RAN equipment from Nokia, and complemented with the nomadic 5G Edge Network, designed by FhG , and the Open5GCore as the software 5G Core Network implementation, also developed by FhG is used in this experiment
Remote	This is a real Edge experiment, and all components except for the metrics collection server, which was running in the FhG data center, were deployed on the Edge of the 5G nomadic node. No functional components needed to be deployed in the cloud.
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 3-2 Experiment 2 (UHA)

Description	
ExperimentType	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Connect multiple devices over 5G enabled smartphones and Wi-Fi paired devices 2) Use Leica BLK2GO (Leica Hexagon sensor) scans of Berlin Central station to populate a simulation, passing the data over the local infra to obtain performance data 3) Pass an Obj from a Smartphone Scan of a subsection of Berlin Central station to keep the digital twin up to date 4) Stress test the WebRTC performance of simulation data with multiple end users and concurrent live interactions - creation, destruction, analysis
Automated	true
TestCases	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Connect up to 10 devices and look for failure points 2) Scanning accuracy 3) Ingest up to 20,000,000 points of data per second and present this back into the sim then into WebRTC and end user devices - establish E2E latency 4) Bandwidth & latency 5) Path finding and routing 6) Exporting to traditional 3D model formats that can be imported into Unity and tested in Fraunhofer's XR tool
UEs	See Experiment 1 / FhG
Network Slice	N/A
Network Services	See Experiment 1
Network Scenario	See Experiment 1
Exclusive Execution	true
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	UHA test cases
Performance targets & SLAs	See Experiment 1
Experiment Parameters	See Experiment 1
Edges	See Experiment 1
Remote	See Experiment 1
Remote Descriptor	See Experiment 1
Version	See Experiment 1
Extra	n/a

Table 3-3 Scenario Description

Scenario Description Template – Field	
Radio access technology (RAT)	5G NR
Standalone / Non-Standalone (if applicable)	Standalone
Cell Power	23 dBm
Frequency band:	n78
Maximum bandwidth per component carrier	100 MHz

Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
Cyclic Prefix	normal
Massive MIMO	4x4
Duplex mode	TDD
TDD uplink/downlink pattern	8:1
User location and speed	0 km/h
Background traffic	low throughput
Computational resources available	N/A

3.2.1 Test Cases and KPIs tables

Table 3-4 FOKUS Test report: **FOKUSBer1**

Field	Description
Test Case ID	FOKUSBer1
Facility, Site	Berlin , Berlin Schöneeweide
Description	Streaming the video of a remotely rendered 3D application from a 5G Edge rendering server to a 5G UE connected to the 5G network.
Executed by	Partner: FhG Date: 2023-04-24
Purpose	Analyzing the rendering and network performance in a real-world 5G remote rendering setup
Scenario	A remote rendering server is connected to the 5G core network, ready to stream its video data to connected users. A user connects to the application and starts receiving the remotely rendered video. The user interacts with the application, sending control data to the renderer and receiving back the rendered result.
Slice Configuration	N/A
Components involved	Wayside laptop for 3D remote rendering, Open5GCore, 5G RAN, 5G UE (iPhone 14 Pro, Nokia X20, Huawei P40 Pro, Google Pixel 6)
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Bitrate, round-trip time, video framerate, CPU/GPU Utilization, CPU/GPU Memory
Tools involved	Metrics Server
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	<p>All tested UEs behaved similarly, with negligible deviations in the measured KPIs. The round-trip time varied from as low as 10 ms to as high as 40 ms, however an average of below 20 ms was achieved, with values staying close to 15 ms for most of the time.</p> <p>(left: iPhone 14 Pro, right: Nokia X20)</p>

The video bitrate utilised by all the UEs varied from 20 Mbps to 40 Mbps. The noticeable variance in bitrate is not caused by the network but rather by optimizations on the application's side. Network was not a limiting factor at any point.

(left: iPhone 14 Pro, right: Nokia X20)

Target metric/KPI On average, a round-trip time of below 20 ms was achieved on every UE.

Table 3-3 UHA Test report: **UHABer1**

Field	Description
Test Case ID	UHABer1
Facility, Site	Berlin cluster
Description	Future Mobility - Connect up to 10 devices and look for failure points
Executed by	Partner: UHA Date: 2023-04-26
Purpose	To stress test the WebRTC pipeline that allows multiple users to connect from front to back-end and interact with the map of Hauptbahnhof and its surroundings.
Scenario	Users from 5G smartphones with browser windows open and Laptops simultaneously connected to Urban Hawk's back-end where the simulation was already running.
Slice Configuration	N/A
Components involved	Polaron Engine back-end (Windows, C++, OpenCL, WebRTC). At Urban Hawk's Bristol office on fiber. Polaron Edge (Stun/Turn VM). Polaron Engine front-end (Android, vanilla Javascript, Web browser).
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	WebRTC statistics (internal metrics compiled into every modern browser) were saved every 5 seconds in Mysql. Next to the front-end console logs the Polaron engine's back-end's terminal window logs were observed to verify if communication was live.
Tools involved	Chrome browser on Laptops in developer mode. Polaron engine back-end in streaming mode with console window logging on.
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	Up to 8 users the connections were working and users could interact. Though a bug at the back-end was discovered that led to crashes. When noise/garbage was transmitted by WebRTC from front-end to back to initiate connecting and continue to peer to peer. That then was fixed.

Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail) **PASS. Both lab and field.**

Table 3-4 UHA Test report: UHABer2

Field	Description
Test Case ID	UHABer2
Facility, Site	Berlin cluster
Description	Future Mobility - Scanning accuracy
Executed by	Partner: UHA Date: 2022-09-27
Purpose	To verify if the LiDAR scan is accurate enough for the use case.
Scenario	Since Berlin Central Station is a huge complex, an initial whole facility LiDAR scan can only be taken section by section, which requires point-cloud registration (relying on GPS and panoramic photos at walk through start and stop points, plus section overlap regions to match against) and merging in the end. Registration can lead to errors and distortion, even on significant levels. Further explanation and method descriptions can be provided upon request.
Slice Configuration	N/A
Components involved	Polaron Engine back-end (Windows, C++, OpenCL, WebRTC). At Urban Hawk's Bristol office on fiber. Polaron Edge (Stun/Turn VM). Polaron Engine front-end (Android, vanilla Javascript, Web browser).
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Deviation between the rail track placements and their curvature represented across the datasets.
Tools involved	Leica Hexagon's point-cloud registering tool was used for the exercise. Then Polaron imported, voxelised and projected the station model onto a 1 meter resolution reconstruction based on OpenStreetMap's data.
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	The deviation was below 1 meter, even visibly.

(raw point-cloud)

(projected and merged with OpenStreetMap in 1 meter per voxel resolution that is enough for route planning)

Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)

PASS. Field.

On the 10 centimeter level there was no accurate enough comparison dataset to match against, therefore that comparison was SKIPPED.

Table 3-5 UHA Test report: UHABer3

Field	Description
Test Case ID	UHABer3
Facility, Site	Berlin cluster
Description	Future Mobility – Ingest up to 20,000,000 points of data per second and present this back into the sim then into WebRTC and end user devices - establish E2E latency
Executed by	Partner: UHA Date: 2022-08-25
Purpose	To measure the bandwidth and latency bottleneck from a remote sensor to back-end.
Scenario	A live depth camera was connected first via USB3 then remotely to the back-end from which point-cloud updates were taken and inserted into the hybrid model.

Slice Configuration	N/A
Components involved	Polaron Engine back-end (Windows, C++, OpenCL, WebRTC). At UHA's Bristol office on fiber. Nvidia RTX 3090 and RTX 2080 GPU cards. Stereolabs depth sensing camera with both USB3 and streaming capability for data transfer.
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Number of points that could be put through from sensor to back-end per second. Integration (import, voxelising) time. Both via USB3 and remotely but still in the same network.
Tools involved	Stereo depth sensing camera with a neural model that estimated the depth based on the pair of rgb images at real-time on the GPU. Since the neural model of the time was computationally heavy it was running on a different GPU than Polaron itself. Only the rgb image pairs were streamed, the depth estimation was done on the back-end server, and a shared file on a fast SSD for data exchange between the 2 GPUs.
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	<p><i>(data from a live depth camera sensor, that is meant to keep changing areas of the digital twin up date, is being imported voxelised real-time)</i></p> <p>On average 800k points were taken and integrated at 15Hz via USB3. Remotely (Wi-Fi, same network) about half.</p> <p>The SSD data exchange, the USB3/Wi-Fi connection between camera and server and the server's PCI bus created bottlenecks. Therefore the measurement is biased.</p> <p>If the sensor is close enough to the back-end dataset and GPU (same network or USB connection or beyond 5G bandwidth) then the updating of the main hybrid model with high resolution spatial local data that reflect the change multiple times a second seems realistic. Seeing the current limitations Urban Hawk has not pursued the test further in more detail.</p>
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	FAIL with arguments for more bandwidth (5G beyond) and edge processing. Lab only.

Table 3-6 UHA Test report: UHABer4

Field	Description
Test Case ID	UHABer4
Facility, Site	Berlin cluster
Description	Future Mobility - Bandwidth & latency

Executed by	Partner: UHA	Date: 2023-04-26
	Purpose	
Scenario	To measure	
Slice Configuration	Measured over the network 5G deployment during the field trial.	
Components involved	N/A	
	Polaron Engine back-end (Windows, C++, OpenCL, WebRTC). At Urban Hawk's Bristol office on fiber.	
	Polaron Edge (Stun/Turn VM). Polaron Engine front-end (Android, vanilla Javascript, Web browser).	
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Number of total bytes transferred till timestamp divided by the number of frames then multiplied by 30. Latency of a full round (back to front then to back). Video and data channels.	
Tools involved	WebRTC internal metrics (compiled into the browser) and back-end implemented packet sending in full rounds.	
	Between 500 and 800 kbps while the render stream left the back-end in 414 x 895 pixel resolution. This is per front-end. Latency wise, test packets did a full round in average 60 ms.	
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary		
	The data channels behave the same way as the video channel (or even audio) in WebRTC, there was no deviation in bandwidth or latency.	
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	PASS. Both lab and field.	

Table 3-7 UHA Test report: UHABer5

Field	Description
Test Case ID	UHABer1
Facility, Site	Berlin cluster
Description	Future Mobility - Path finding and routing
Executed by	Partner: UHA Date: 2023-04-26
Purpose	To validate if Polaron can find the optimum path that takes a user from point A to B in the pre-classified spatial map. Polaron solves the problem by constructing Eikonal fields for the whole of the map (similar to Dijkstra's algorithm but more general). The field is built

	iteratively starting from the target and spreading out to the rest of the map. And in a massively parallel way to keep it real-time (in 2D/2.5D that means over 100 Hz). Once the field emerges the optimal routes from any point to the target also emerge. More explanation and description of the method can be provided upon request.
Scenario	In the merged hybrid model/map the Polaron engine had to plan optimal routes between two points, also incorporating live changes and disruption on the map that were manually added by other users.
Slice Configuration	N/A
Components involved	Polaron Engine back-end (Windows, C++, OpenCL, WebRTC). At Urban Hawk's Bristol office on fiber. Polaron Edge (Stun/Turn VM). Polaron Engine front-end (Android, vanilla Javascript, Web browser).
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	The Eikonal field was observed if it builds and avoids the changed/disputed areas and finds alternative ways around them.
Tools involved	Polaron engine.
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	Every time they built.
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	PASS. Both lab and field.

Table 3-8 UHA Test report: UHABer6

Field	Description
Test Case ID	UHABer5
Facility, Site	Berlin cluster
Description	Future Mobility – Exporting to traditional 3D model formats that can be imported into Unity and tested in Fraunhofer's XR tool
Executed by	Partner: UHA Date: 2023-04-26
Purpose	To run XR experiences based on the volumetric hybrid model that is inside Polaron in traditional game engines and open source render tools.
Scenario	The entire geometry in the hybrid model that represents Hauptbahnhof and its surroundings was polygonised (Polaron does not work with polygons or triangles like traditional game engines do; it is pure volumetric data) and exported into the Obj 3d model format. That was then copied over and imported in the Unity open source game engine.
Slice Configuration	N/A
Components involved	Polaron Engine back-end (Windows, C++, OpenCL, WebRTC). At Urban Hawk's Bristol office on fiber. FhG's XR tool based on Unity.
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Generated pure vertex + triangulated 3D model in Obj format.
Tools involved	Polaron engine. FhG's XR tool.
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	The export did not go real-time as the process to polygonise the volumetric data = the voxels took close to a minute. Also Unity did not manage to read the vertex information from the generated Obj file as it was supposed to do.

Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)

(How the hybrid voxel model of Berlin Central station and the surroundings appeared in the Unity engine; the player is inside the station where the triangles are buggy but their locations are correct)

Neither was the most efficient method/solution found and implemented (like marching cubes or tetrahedra for example) at Polaron's back-end, nor was the generated Obj file compressed or optimised in any way. The one minute processing time could have been reduced to a few seconds, which would make the transfer quasi-real-time.

Partial PASS, where the concept is a PASS, the current level of implementation is a FAIL.

3.2.2 Conclusions – Lessons learned

5G provided sufficient bandwidth and latency for the render streaming and user interaction parts, though for such large spatial datasets no bandwidth is good enough, therefore leaving an appetite ahead of future networks beyond 5G. Multiple concurrent users could connect without breaking the service, and that is promising.

From a development perspective the project proved challenging. **UHA** started from TRL 4 and got between TRL 6 and 7 by the end of 5G-VICTORI. The Polaron engine is being developed from scratch where a small business is innovating and competing with much larger well capitalised players.

Early hopes of running Polaron on light devices completely faded. Polaron will always run in the cloud. It will scale further on cloud GPU clusters like Amazon Web Services (AWS). Therefore, exploring real-time low latency data transfer between the end-points will remain a vital part of future development.

The palette of vertical UCs widened. Also, in parallel, photogrammetry and neural models improved a lot (ex. radiance fields, Nerf models) that can replace some of the expensive LiDAR scans and thereby turn the overall data collection more cost effective.

3.2.3 Vertical business KPI validation

Initially **UHA**'s Future Mobility targeted risk and insurance. As the project progressed, and the engine developed, **UHA** realised there was a lot more value to be extracted. Modeling risk through spatial datasets is equal to gaining good situational awareness. The data and the models that describe risk in multi-modal travel and represent value for the insurer do not differ from the requirements of first responders, local authorities, logistics, or even the military. Plus an awesome voxel engine like Polaron can run experiences in the creative sectors as well (e.g. games).

From the original back-end role for Future Mobility Polaron pivoted toward an all-in-one simulation platform. Where **UHA**'s focus shall be on the simulation part, with a lot of what if scenarios evaluated, instead of purely collecting and visualising the spatial data. This approach can give **UHA** an

advantage ahead of larger players, attract more capital, and catch up to (hopefully) become a major player and disruptor in the field.

During 5G-VICTORI UHA's Polaron engine:

- Got accepted into NVIDIA's Deep Learning Super Sampling (DLSS) program as a rare non-gaming application.
- Won the "best-in-class technology" prize in "Adaptation of existing technology for public safety use", NIST 2022 – Commanding Tech Challenge, USA.
- Became actively involved in UK resilience and security programs with partners.
- Got a first (substantial) investment offer.

Further UCs and verticals on <https://polaronworldengine.com>

For Railway Stations & Transport Hubs, Polaron's value proposition is: Railway stations vary in size from massive stations in London to smaller regional hubs. Managing them efficiently, especially with the help of simulation, ensures an optimised transport network and a seamless public transport service.

- **Railway Stations & Transport Hubs:** Rail transport handles a massive volume of passengers. Delays or issues in the railway or external transport network disrupt station operations. Approximately 75% of UK journeys face challenges, which increases to 86% with rail transport. Stations also face safety and security challenges, calls for better efficiency, and increasing responsibilities towards the community and broader customer base.
- **Simulation as a solution and automation tool:** Polaron offers a simulation tool that provides comprehensive data for stations, from footfall mapping to operational challenges. It can produce real-time simulations, detect issues beforehand, enable collaborative planning, and assess the costs and savings of implementing plans. It also helps in optimizing routes, factoring in dynamic changes, and understanding user preferences.
- **Model different types of commuter:** Not everyone is a typical working age commuter. Our partners at RASIC have done an amazing job of profiling the 20+ categories of commuters. What works for a teenager, does not work for a single mum with two kids, or what works for someone with reduced mobility. With an aging transport demographic and increasing changes to patterns of life – the changing demographic is forcing challenges onto the railway that have not been seen before.
- **Data led but with Human Insight and Input:** Modelling allows for the automatic ingestion of data – and its transposition into a 3D model. In an age of increasing conflicts between sensors, privacy and the cost to run larger networks – being able to fuse data from static sources (turnstiles) and privacy respecting sensors (e.g. Smart CCTV that is monitoring for safety issues rather than profiling individuals) having a system that can bring all of this together at an affordable price is paramount.

Key Benefits:

1. **Model demand waves:** Polaron enables large-scale data modeling to predict demand waves and mitigate possible surges. It considers the relationship of a site to its environment.
2. **Cost, demand, and heat map modelling:** Polaron uses a unique method to create and refine cost maps. It can model different events and scenarios, and combine multiple types of data.
3. **Up-to-date 3D models:** Polaron can update and generate map and 3D data, facilitating the use of various inputs. It helps in simulating and comparing trials against different conditions.
4. **Application Programming Interface (API) gateways and Mobile Access:** Polaron integrates with other systems and networks through an API portal. It supports mobile scanning and helps in engaging a broad audience.

5. Key technologies driving infrastructure modelling and automation of monitoring:
- Automatic data updates: Automate the ingestion of various data.
 - Data Caching: Polaron runs on commercial-of-the-shelf (COTS) hardware and offers multiple hosting options.
 - Works where you work: Offers browser-based access for multiple users.
 - Top performance: Features cutting-edge performance with P2P and federated connections.
 - High security: Operates securely within your network.
 - Connect to external services: Easily connects with external data stores and services.
 - Hybrid or OnPrem: Resilience means ensuring that you can still conduct operations in the face of communications issues and disruption. Running a Hybrid model – with a system OnPrem or via Edge based computing connected to a remote cloud service offers the best of both – and can easily be retrofitted to existing networks and systems.

3.3 UC #1.3 “CCTV, Rail Signaling and Rail Critical Services (Telephony)”

The Berlin Rail Critical Services are defined in the 5G-VICTORI project **WP3** document **D3.2** (among other clusters and services). The Rail Critical Services at the 5G-VICTORI Berlin 5G deployment, belonging to **UC #1.3**, are: Rail Signaling (**Alstom**), CCTV streaming (**Alstom**), Cab Telephony (**KCC**) and Sensor Data (**KCC**).

3.3.1 Lab measurements summary

Alstom

Lab measurements were performed during the winter of 2022/2023 at the **FhG** lab in Berlin, using Open5GCore, Huawei 5G RAN and 5G CPE. QoS was developed and introduced by **FhG** for the first time in Open5GCore during 2022-w47. Having the 5G air-interface as the main bottleneck, QoS differentiation using 5QIs 8 and 9 could be demonstrated.

A lab activity was also performed at **IHP** lab, using Open5GCore, Nokia RAN and **KCC** onboard Gateway (OBG). Here the 5G air interface was not the main bottleneck. For example, the **KCC** GW is designed for around 30 Mbps, which is much less than the air-interface performance. Therefore the 5G air-interface related 5QIs 8 and 9 show similar performance when the 5G air interface was loaded with background traffic.

To this end, the same equipment as in the **IHP** lab was used, where an S-Bahn train with onboard equipment ran back and forth on a test track many times. The wayside equipment was installed in nomadic nodes, on a table with laptops and screens, and 5G RUs were positioned 40 meters away from each other.

KCC

Lab measurements of the Rail Telephony and Sensor Data were performed during winter 2022/2023 at **FhG** lab in Berlin, using Open5GCore with Huawei 5G RAN and **KCC**'s Mission-Critical (MC) Services for Railways providing 3GPP Mission Critical service Push-To-Talk (MCPTT) and Mission Critical Data (MCData) on the network side and Rail OBG TRACe with a built-in 5G-SA radio module and 5G CPEs together with MCPTT Rail Telephony and MCData Sensor Applications on 5G mobiles and a Next-Gen Dispatcher on the client side. Usage of the QoS in MCPTT Rail Telephony was limited to default non-MC 5QIs 8 and 9 due to lack of guaranteed-bitrate 5QI 65 support in the RAN network. Isolation of the rail critical traffic from other non-critical user planes using a dedicated 5G DNN was demonstrated as an alternative for non-supported 5G slicing by the network. Sensor data UCs using MCData were demonstrated as well using default 5QIs 8 and 9 and a dedicated 5G DNN.

Next lab measurements were performed at the **IHP** lab, using Open5GCore and Nokia RAN with **KCC**'s MC Services for Railways providing MCPTT/MCData and MCPTT/MCData clients, incl. a

Dispatcher Client. The limitations to non-MC 5QIs persisted while using the Nokia RAN at **IHP** lab, exactly as seen while using the Huawei RAN in the **FhG** lab.

3.3.1 Intro field trials

The above mentioned Rail Critical Services (encompassed in **UC #1.3**) were demonstrated in April 2023 at the Deutsche Bahn facility *S-Bahn Werk Schöneeweide* (see Figure 3-8). The Rail Critical Services showcased were CCTV, Rail Signaling, Telephony, and Sensor data.

Figure 3-8 Rail Critical Services Field Demo at the Berlin S-Bahn Werk Schöneeweide

3.3.2 CCTV and Rail Signaling

Field demonstration of CCTV and Rail Signaling took place in April 2023 at the Deutsche Bahn facility *S-Bahn Werk Schöneeweide*, southeast of Berlin. The field equipment was the very same as used in the **IHP** Lab.

3.3.2.1 Field trials descriptions

3.3.2.1.1 Equipment for CCTV and Rail Signaling

The Field Demo equipment was the same as the one used in the **IHP** Lab. Figure 3-11 describes the hardware and software used at the Berlin Field Trials for CCTV and Rail Signaling services, from wayside at the top down to onboard equipment at bottom.

3.3.2.1.2 Wayside Berlin - IHP Lab and Berlin Hbf Field

Both the **IHP** Lab and the Field Demo were based on the same Wayside **IHP** Nomadic Node (comparing with fixed installation used at **FhG** Lab in Berlin).

Figure 3-9: Ubuntu laptops used for CCTV monitoring and for Hawkeye with Rail Signaling.

Wayside Equipment:

- The Wayside computer for monitoring CCTV camera and controlling Hawkeye was an **Ubuntu Laptop** (see Figure 3-9).
- **FhG's Open5GCore** with an IP address-based QoS solution of the 5G air-interface, using 5QI 8 and 9.
- The **Hawkeye Server** run as a VM on a Wayside laptop. The Hawkeye license was the IHP one with one user and max 10 probes).
- Three **Hawkeye probes** are needed at Wayside, which also run as VMs on the IHP Nomadic node Compute and Storage resource.
 - Two Rail Signaling probes with different QoS settings (5QI 8 and 9).
 - One Background Traffic probe for loading the air-interface. (5QI 9).
- **IHP** Nomadic Node with **5G Nokia RAN** (see Figure 3-10- 5G Radio is the one in the middle).
- **DHCP** supported, some IP addresses configured to stay the same.
- **Grid** based 230 VAC power supply with Battery.

Figure 3-10 Wayside radio equipment, both 5G and mmWave, plus the S-Bahn train.

Version 2023-05-02

5G	5 th Generation 3GPP defined cellular network
CCTV	Closer Circuit Television
CN	Core Network
CPE	Customer Premises Equipment (UE onboard GW)
GBE	GigaBit per second Ethernet
GW	Gateway
HW	Hardware
IHP	Leibniz Institute for High Performance Microelectronics

IP	Internet Protocol
MGMT	Management
OOB	Out Of Band Management
PoE	Power over Ethernet
RAN	Radio Access Network
SW	Software
TDD	Time Division Duplex
UE	User Equipment

Figure 3-11 Berlin IHP Field Demo Equipment – CCTV and Rail Signaling

3.3.2.1.3 Onboard Berlin - IHP Lab and Berlin Field Demo

The Onboard IHP Lab and Field Demo equipment was the same. The CCTV camera was installed on a pole on the train, using zipties.

Figure 3-12: Onboard equipment being installed onboard an S-Bahn train at the S-Bahn Werk SchöneWeide

Onboard Equipment:

- **Onboard 5G Gateway** by **KCC**, with 5G radio modems. The Onboard GW was put on the window with suction cups (after picture was taken).
- **Ethernet Switch** connected to the 5G GW (a first M12 Ethernet port).
- **Power over Ethernet (PoE) Injector** connected to the Ethernet switch.
- **CCTV camera** connected to PoE Injector (the camera is powered using Power over Ethernet).
- **Onboard Ubuntu laptop** by FhG runs the **onboard Hawkeye probes**. The probes were used for Rail Signaling (5QI 8 and 9) and Background traffic (5QI 9).
- Equipment onboard the train use power via **batteries** for 230 VAC power supply (the batteries were charged when the train had power).

The Equipment was installed on the train and at wayside next to a test track. CCTV camera was installed on a pole.

Figure 3-13: Alstom Field Demo of CCTV and Rail Signaling at S-Bahn Werk Schöneweide.

3.3.2.1.4 CCTV Field Demonstration

The field demonstration showed pictures from the camera onboard the train, via the 5G network, to a laptop on Wayside. The bitrate from the camera was around 0.5 Mbps when a picture did not move, and around 5 Mbps when pictures move. The pictures are delayed with around 300 ms using H.264, where the delay of the 5G network is only around 10 ms. This means that the camera and monitoring processing of H.264 frames is the dominant delay. When using MJPEG (only full frames), the delay is shorter, and with H.265 longer.

The test results carried out on 2023-06-19 show:

- 15 seconds backhaul interruption: Testing with 15 seconds interruption (pulling the cable and attaching it again after 15 seconds). The pictures continued after a couple of seconds when the Ethernet cable was put back, then being around 17 seconds. Several tests showed similar results. One test resulted in 32 s lag. The lag is not recovering over time.
- 30 seconds backhaul interruption: Testing with 30 seconds interruption. In some tests the pictures didn't start again (clicking Paus and Play restarts the flow and real time pictures are seen again). Other tests showed gave continued pictures being around 32 seconds delayed. The lag does not recover over time, waiting for half an hour, the pictures were still delayed with 32 seconds.
- 60 seconds backhaul interruption: Trying with 60 seconds interruption a first time, the pictures just hangs and do not start again. The same when trying a second time.

3.3.2.1.4.1 Conclusions on long CCTV pictures delay using H.264 after a backhaul interruption

Conclusions from the demos regarding the long CCTV pictures delay which was experienced using the H.264 camera:

1. The delayed pictures seen in FhG Lab in Berlin 2022 w47, at the Field demo in Berlin 2023 w17, and in the Alstom Lab 2023 w25 must be buffered in the Camera. Note: the camera GUI is fully responsive all the time (e.g. for clicking Paus and Play).
2. The Buffer length seems to be up to around 30 to 60 seconds. The camera continues to generate pictures in a buffer when the backhaul network bitrate is lower than the generated bitrate.
3. The problem with lagging pictures is in line with what people express on Internet forums regarding H.264 cameras, seeing a lag of up to around 30 to 60 seconds.
4. Cameras using H.264 are not useful – it is scary – a viewer thinks the pictures are real time, but it is not. There is no on-screen warning that pictures are old. Can't be used real time monitoring, as backhaul interruptions over a radio network can't be excluded.
5. With these tests, it is clear that buffering is done in the camera. An improvement of the H.264 camera could be:
 - a. Avoid buffer buildups, for example by reducing the bitrate or frame rate into the buffer when pictures are not read with the same pace. Limit buffer length to a configurable value.
 - b. Indicate on screen how old pictures are when leaving the camera. This would make it possible for a user to be aware or be able to do something about it (e.g. restarting the flow).
 - c. IP packets sent from the camera could be fitted with buffering delay information to make it possible for a system to react on the monitoring side.

3.3.2.1.5 Rail Signaling QoS Field Demonstrations

The high-level purpose with the Rail Signaling tests in Berlin labs was to demonstrate that Rail Signaling with QoS can share the same 5G air-interface as other traffic.

- To be able to demonstrate this, at least three Hawkeye probe pairs are needed, three onboard and three wayside probes (three probe pairs).
- The generated Background Traffic is used to emulate other traffic over the air-interface in a controlled way, such that it almost saturates the air-interface 5G performance (for example selecting 60% of a speed-test result).

Rail Signaling has been tested with a lot of different combinations of CCTV and Rail Signaling flows in **FhG Lab**. There 4 Probe pairs was used. See deliverable **D4.2** for these results.

A flow-based QoS solution was implemented, where the 5QI values are signaled to RAN and UE when the PDU session is setup. The **IHP Lab** Field Demo for Rail Signaling was limited to using two Rail Signaling flows plus a Background traffic load (three probe pairs).

The difference between the FhG **Lab** setup using the Huawei CPE and the **IHP Lab** Field Demo setup using the **KCC OBG** is the following:

- 5G air-interface is the main bottleneck when using Huawei CPE.
- The 5G air-interface is not the main bottleneck when using **KCC GW**.

KCC's OBG is designed for around 30 Mbps, which is much less than what the 5G air-interface is capable of (more than 100 Mbps in uplink and several hundreds Mbps in downlink).

When using two Rail Signaling flows with 5QI 8 and 9, plus a Background traffic of around 60% of the speed test bitrate of around 30 Mbps, no QoS difference could be seen between the 5QI 8 and 5QI 9 Rail Signaling flows.

3.3.2.1.5.1 Flow-based QoS – implemented in Open5GCore

In October 2022, the QoS approach changed to a flow-based solution instead. Different pre-configured IP addresses trigger different 5QIs when the PDU sessions are setup.

Open5GCore was configured to communicate QoS Flow information to the UE and RAN during PDU Session Establishment to support the UC. Specifically, this configuration was triggered when a particular subscriber IMSI (that of the SIM card used in the OBG) requested a standard PDU session.

When the PDU session was established, two QoS Flows were defined:

- one that classifies all traffic to or from the IP address of the high priority Hawkeye probe and assigned it 5QI 8
- one default rule for all other traffic to be assigned 5QI 9

It was observed in both the setup using the Huawei CPE and Huawei RAN the later setups as well using the Kontron OBG and Nokia RAN, the signaling of the QoS parameters during PDU Session Establishment and the "tagging" of encapsulated user plane traffic packets was working correctly. This means that the whole 5G system was aware of the desired QoS configuration.

However, how QoS is enforced may vary quite a bit on the devices and components used, plus if there are other major bottlenecks than over the air-interface. The 5QIs only have a meaning for the 5G air-interface.

By "tagging" is meant the inclusion of the QoS Flow Identifier (QFI), a dynamically assigned ID in the GTP-U (the encapsulation protocol) header. The signaling during PDU establishment effectively assigns a QFI to a set of QoS parameters. So, for example, the priority traffic may be given QFI 123, which the UE, RAN, and CN know means the traffic should be treated with 5QI 8, and the non-priority traffic may be given QFI 456, which has been assigned to the other traffic which should be treated with 5QI 9.

3.3.2.1.5.2 QoS over the single 5G air-interface

QoS can only be clearly visible when the 5G air-interface is the single major bottleneck.

When there are many other bottlenecks in the system than over the air-interface, which in a real system is a bad design, then QoS is hardly visible.

The **FhG** Lab showed a clear 5QI difference, while the **IHP** Lab showed no or a minor difference.

3.3.2.1.5.3 Hawkeye Probe Pairs at IHP Lab and Field Demo – 2x RS + 1x BG

Three Hawkeye probe pairs were used at **IHP** Lab and for the Field Demo.

Version 2023-07-12

5G	5 th Generation 3GPP defined cellular network	NR	New Radio
5QI	5G QoS Indicator	NS	Network Slice
BS	Base Station	RAN	Radio Access Network
CN	Core Network	RRU	Remote Radio Unit
CPE	Customer Premises Equipment (UE onboard GW)	TDD	Time Division Duplex
GW	Gateway	UE	User Equipment
		UPF	User Plane Function

Figure 3-14: Hawkeye Probe Pairs at IHP Lab and Field Demo – QoS over 5G air-interface

Figure 3-15 gives a view with signaling in Open5GCore when UE sets up a PDU Session with QoS, used by Rail Signaling and Background traffic over 5G. A sequence diagram can be found in 3GPP TS 23.502, Figure 4.3.2.2.1-1. The numbers at the dashed blue arrows correspond to the 3GPP figure.

QoS in Open5GCore, RAN and UE for Rail Signaling Demo

Version 2023-04-13

5th Generation 3GPP defined cellular network
 5G QoS Indicator
 Access and Mobility Function
 BackGround (traffic)
 Base Station
 Core Network
 Customer Premises Equipment
 Gateway

Policy Control Function
 Protocol Data Unit
 QoS Flow Identifier
 Session Management Function
 Unified Data Management
 User Equipment
 User Plane Function

Figure 3-15 QoS in Open5GCore, RAN and UE for Rail Signaling Demo

Arrow nr 1, UE initiates a PDU Session.

Lot of signaling in between in the 5G System.

Arrow nr 13, The PDU Session is Established.

The **IHP** Lab 5G RAN equipment is from Nokia, handled by Smart Mobile Labs (SML). The Nokia RAN only supports 5QI values 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9. This was the status in March 2023.

Table 3-5 is extracted from 3GPP TS 23.501 for the 5QIs supported in the **IHP** Lab. All Resource types in the table are Non-GBR.

Table 3-5 5QI to QoS characteristics mapping - 5QI values supported at IHP Lab using Nokia RAN

5QI value	Resource Type	Default Priority Level	Packet Delay Budget	Packet Error Rate	Example Services	Comment
5	Non-GBR	10	100 ms	10 ⁻⁶	IMS Signaling	
6		60	300 ms	10 ⁻⁶	Video (Buffered Streaming), TCP-based (e.g. www, e-mail, chat, ftp, p2p file sharing, progressive video, etc.)	
7		70	100 ms	10 ⁻³	Voice, Video (Live Streaming), Interactive Gaming	
8		80	300 ms	10 ⁻⁶	Video (Buffered Streaming)	Used for demo of High Prio Rail Signaling
9		90	300 ms	10 ⁻⁶	TCP-based (e.g. www, e-mail, chat, ftp, p2p file sharing, progressive video, etc.)	

3.3.2.1.6 Comparison between FhG Lab and IHP Lab setup

3.3.2.1.6.1 Bottlenecks between Wayside and Onboard

The **IHP** Lab setup, with Nokia RAN and **KCC** OBG, shows a much lower throughput and weak QoS result over the 5G Air-interface compared the **FhG** Lab using Huawei RAN and CPE (and with powerful wayside computing instead of wayside laptops). The different performance relates to having other bottlenecks than a single one over the 5G air-interface (where the real bottleneck should be in a loaded network – as the air-interface is the scarce resource).

Speedtests performed with Hawkeye in the different systems show a dramatic difference:

- **FhG** Lab (using a fixed installation with Huawei RAN and CPE, plus powerful computing servers): 125 Mbps uplink, 400 Mbps downlink.
- **IHP** Lab (using nomadic nodes with Nokia RAN and Kontron GW, plus laptops for the probe VMs: 35 Mbps uplink, 29 Mbps downlink.

Examples of other bottlenecks than over the 5G air-interface:

- Wayside
 - Hawkeye Probe VM software
 - Virtual environment
 - Linux OS and Computer ports
 - UPF Router and Ethernet switch

- 5G Radio Access Network (RAN) – with scheduler implementing 5QI based QoS (Huawei vs Nokia)
- Onboard
 - 5G Radio modules - with scheduler implementing 5QI based QoS
 - Gateway (Huawei CPE vs Kontron GW)
 - Ethernet switch
 - Ubuntu laptop ports
 - Linux OS with Docker
 - Hawkeye Probe xr_docker

3.3.2.1.7 IHP Lab and Field Demo results in April 2023

These tests were done during one day in week 16 in April 2023 remotely (via WireGuard VPN from Stockholm) to the IHP Lab, just before the Field Demo.

The same results could be seen in the Field Demo during week 17 2023. This is why the result here is taken from the IHP Lab result.

The conclusion is that no QoS differentiation could be seen, with the reason that the 5G air-interface is not the main bottleneck.

Note: if you wonder why the delay varies a lot over time, and why QoS sometimes are not that clear, read section 3.3.2.1.8 for circumstances.

3.3.2.1.7.1 Speed test (downlink and uplink)

- Test ID 27: Demo Speedtest DL PP1 TCP 2 min: 29 Mbps
- Test ID 28: Demo Speedtest UL PP1 TCP 2 min: 35 Mbps

3.3.2.1.7.2 UL QoS tests (parallel flows)

Uplink (UL) tests with RS1, RS2 plus BG traffic often fail: “**No statistics received**”. This is why no graphs can be shown here.

3.3.2.1.7.3 UL Single flow tests

The UL delay is around 17 ms. The loss is 0%.

Figure 3-16 UL RS1 PP2 200 kbps 5QI9 – Delay

Figure 3-17: UL RS1 PP2 200 kbps 5QI9 – Loss

3.3.2.1.7.4 DL QoS tests

Rail Signaling flows (RS1 and RS2) run for 2 minutes in parallel, each with 200 kbps and having different QoS settings with 5QI9 and 5QI8 (where 5QI8 has higher priority in the air-interface schedulers).

- Test ID 22: DEMO DL PP2 RS1 200 kbps 300 bytes packets 5QI9
- Test ID 23: DEMO DL PP3 RS2 200 kbps 300 bytes packets 5QI8
- Test ID 29: DEMO DL PP1 BG 30 Mbps 1300 bytes packets 5QI9

3.3.2.1.7.5 Rail Signaling 1 and 2 with Background traffic during last minute – DELAY

During the last minute where the BG traffic is running, the 5QI8 RS flow gets the same delay, while the 5QI9 flow gets an increased delay.

Figure 3-18: Rail Signaling 1, DL Delay, 5QI9 (PP2).

Figure 3-19: Rail Signaling 2, DL Delay, 5QI8 (PP3).

Conclusion on Delay for 5QI 8 and 9, without and with background traffic:

- During these 2 minutes, the Delay differences between 5QI9 and 5QI8 rail signaling flows can be compared both without background traffic (the first part of the graphs, between 0 and 60 seconds) and with background traffic on (60 to 120 seconds in the graphs).
- The 5QI 8 flow is slightly better off but showing a minor difference. The reason is that the 5G air-interface in the IHP Lab and Field Demo setups is not the main bottleneck, therefore the 5QIs have very little impact.

3.3.2.1.7.6 Rail Signaling 1 and 2 with Background traffic during last minute – LOSS

During the last minute where the BG traffic is running, the 5QI8 RS flow gets a minor lower loss than the 5QI9 flow.

Figure 3-20 Rail Signaling 1 (RS1), DL Loss, 5QI9 (PP2).

Figure 3-21: Rail Signaling 2 (RS2), DL Loss, 5QI8 (PP3).

Conclusion on Loss for 5QI 8 and 9, without and with background traffic:

- During these 2 minutes, the Loss differences between 5QI9 and 5QI8 rail signaling flows can be compared both without background traffic (the first part of the graphs, between 0 and 60 seconds) and with background traffic on (60 to 120 seconds in the graphs).
- The 5QI 8 flow is slightly better off but showing a minor difference. The reason is that the 5G air-interface in the IHP Lab and Field Demo setups is not the main bottleneck, therefore the 5QIs have very little impact.

3.3.2.1.7.7 Background traffic (BG) DL 30 Mbps: 28% Loss and 21 Mbps Throughput
 These two graphs show Background traffic Loss and Throughput.

Figure 3-22 Background traffic (BG) DL 30 Mbps (PP1): 28% Loss.

Figure 3-23: Background traffic (BG) DL 30 Mbps (PP1): 21 Mbps Throughput

Conclusion on Background traffic Loss and Throughput:

- During the time Background Traffic is on, 60 seconds, the software based Hawkeye probes push data at a tick in the operating system of the computer. Pushing too much data can blow buffers.
- The OBG is also a bottleneck in this setup. Data can be lost there as well.
- What we see from these graphs is that the loss doesn't occur over the 5G air-interface.

3.3.2.1.8 Strange Delay and QoS Results

This section adds to why test results are not always as expected. This section applies to both test results from the FhG Lab and from the IHP Lab or Field Demo, plus in general when emulating parallel traffic streams in a system.

3.3.2.1.8.1 Operating System Tick Time

The operating system has an operating system scheduler tick time, which means that tasks run at different time ticks. When Hawkeye sends data from a probe, this is done at a tick. The Hawkeye probes in the Berlin test systems are software based on a Linux operating system, which means that data is sent at time ticks.

When several Hawkeye test flows send data, a flow can be scheduled just before or after another flow. This can result in some strange QoS behavior, for example that a lower priority flow sends its data burst just before the higher prio flow. Hawkeye has no idea of what flows have the lower or higher priority in the 5G System.

3.3.2.1.8.2 5G TDD air-interface

The 5G air-interface in the Berlin labs and field demo is TDD based (Time Division Duplex), using frequency band n78.

The 10 ms radio frame contains 10 subframes. Each Subframe can be allocated for Downlink (**D**), Special (**S**), or Uplink (**U**).

- With a 5 ms repetition scheme: **DDDSU** is the most suitable for 5G, gives a round-trip-time (RTT) of ~7 ms.
- With a 10 ms repetition scheme: **DDDDDDDSUU** is the frame structure for sync coexistence between 4G TDD and 5G TDD. Gives ~8 ms RTT.

For example, data being sent from an onboard probe to the onboard UE for uplink traffic may be served either directly by the UE scheduler or has to wait 7 ms before it can be served, all depending on when the data is sent in time. The TDD scheme leads to a variation in service round-trip-time of up to 7 ms.

3.3.2.1.8.3 Blowing buffers

When a Hawkeye probe is configured to send with a high bitrate. This could lead to blowing buffers with the reason that the amount of data that is needed to be sent every Tick Time is more than the involved interface buffers can handle.

We have seen this in the test activities. For example, the background traffic having 75% loss ratio regardless of bitrate. Another example is 28%.

3.3.2.2 Experiment and scenario descriptions

This section lists two types of table for CCTV and Rail Signaling:

- Experiment Description
- Report from tests

These tests were done during the Field Demo in Berlin 2023-w17.

3.3.2.2.1 Experiment Description and Report for CCTV

Table 3-6 gives a Description overview of the CCTV Experiments.

Table 3-6 Experiment Description for CCTV

Description	
ExperimentType	Equipment based on the IHP Lab setup adapted for the Field Demo.
Automated	Manual installation of the real CCTV camera onboard the train.
TestCases	RCCg02 One train CCTV (5 Mbps in uplink) RCCg03 Twelve trains CCTV (12x5=60 Mbps in uplink) – not performed
UEs	Kontron Onboard GW with radio modems (limited around 30 Mbps)
Network Slice	Network Slicing not supported.
Network Services	5G always connected, best effort.
Network Scenario	CCTV moving pictures from one real camera on the train. Note: the 5G connectivity went up and down many times during test activities.
Exclusive Execution	CCTV pictures were running when there was 5G connectivity over the air-interface. The train moved many times beyond 5G coverage.
ReservationTime	-
Application	CCTV
Performance targets & SLAs	The guesstimate from WP3 documentation outlined a bitrate of 5 Mbps, a latency of less than 150 ms, and a loss ratio of less than 0.5%.
Experiment Parameters	The bitrate from the CCTV cameras was between 0.5 Mbps for still pictures and around 5 Mbps for moving pictures.
Edges	The Open5GCore network with RAN used a 5G base station from Nokia.
Remote	The Field Demo was done on site southeast of Berlin at Deutsche Bahn S-Bahn Werk Schöneweide. No remote operation possible.
Remote Descriptor	na
Version	na
Extra	na

Table 3-7 gives a summary of the CCTV tests done at the Field Demo in Berlin.

Table 3-7 CCTV REPORT from tests done at Field Demo in Berlin

Field	Description
Test Case ID	RCCg02, RCCg03
Facility, Site	Field Demo at Deutsche Bahn S-Bahn Werk Schöneweide, Berlin.
Description	The real CCTV camera onboard the S-Bahn train produced moving pictures over the 5G network (Open5GCore with RAN and UE) to a Wayside laptop.
Executed by	Partner: Alstom, FhG Date: 2023-w17.
Purpose	To see how CCTV behaves over 5G.
Scenario	CCTV over 5G
Slice Configuration	Network Slicing not supported.
Components involved	RCCg02: Wayside laptop for CCTV monitoring, Open5GCore with UPF Router, 5G RAN with Nokia base station. TDD 5G air-interface. Kontron onboard GW with radio modems, Ethernet Switch, PoE injector, CCTV camera. RCCg03: Not performed. See results from FhG Lab in D4.2.
KPIs collected	Bitrates, loss and latency were measured.

(Metrics collected)	
Tools involved	CCTV camera with visual comparison between physical movements and movements presented on the screen.
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	The result is mainly as expected. The loss ratio for the one train video stream got a loss below 1%.
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	In general: the target CCTV over 5G KPIs are met.

3.3.2.2 Experiment Description and Report for Rail Signaling

Table 3-8 provides a description overview of the Rail Signaling Experiments.

Table 3-8 Experiment Description for Rail Signaling

	Description
ExperimentType	Equipment based on the IHP Lab setup adapted for the Field Demo.
Automated	Manual handling and running Hawkeye tests for Rail Signaling, both for one flow and with two flows with different QoS 5QI settings.
TestCases	RCSg02 One train Rail Signaling (200 kbps UL/DL) RCSv03 Twelve trains RS (2.4 Mbps UL/DL) - not performed
UEs	Kontron Onboard GW with radio modems (limited around 30 Mbps)
Network Slice	Network Slicing not supported.
Network Services	5G always connected, using 5QI 8 for the higher priority flow (related to one of the IP address pairs) and 5QI 9 for the lower priority flows.
Network Scenario	Rail Signaling using Hawkeye, emulating one flow alone, or two flows with a background traffic. Note: the 5G connectivity went up and down many times during test activities.
Exclusive Execution	CCTV pictures were running when there was 5G connectivity over the air-interface. The train moved many times beyond 5G coverage. This means that Rail Signaling flows run in parallel with the CCTV flow, plus sometimes in parallel also with Telephony and Sensors data.
ReservationTime	-
Application	Rail Signaling.
Performance targets & SLAs	The estimate from WP3 documentation outlined a bitrate of 200 kbps.
Experiment Parameters	Rail Signaling used either one flow, or two flows with background traffic.
Edges	The Open5GCore network with RAN used a 5G base station from Nokia.
Remote	The Field Demo was done on site southeast of Berlin at Deutsche Bahn S-Bahn Werk Schöneeweide. No remote operation possible.
Remote Descriptor	na
Version	na
Extra	na

Table 3-9 gives a summary of the Rail Signaling tests done at the Field Demo in Berlin.

Table 3-9 Rail Signaling REPORT from tests done at the Field Demo in Berlin

Field	Description
Test Case ID	RCSg02, RCSg03
Facility, Site	Field Demo at Deutsche Bahn S-Bahn Werk Schöneeweide, Berlin.

Description	<p>Rail Signaling is emulated using the Hawkeye software and three probe pairs. Each probe pair has one onboard probe and one wayside probe. Typical usage of the probes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PP1: Background traffic, increased stepwise from 0 to 100% • PP2: Rail Signaling 1, using 5QI 9 • PP3: Rail Signaling 2, using 5QI 8 (higher priority than 5QI 9) <p>Rail Signaling was tested with one flow, or two flows together with background traffic.</p> <p>No QoS differentiation could be seen over air-interface. The reason is that the air-interface in the Field Demo setup was not the main bottleneck. This means that the different 5QI settings with 5QI 8 and 9 has no effect.</p>	
Executed by	Partner: Alstom, FhG	Date: 2023-w17.
Purpose	To see how Rail Signaling behaves over 5G.	
Scenario	Rail Signaling over 5G.	
Slice Configuration	Network Slicing not supported.	
Components involved	<p>RCSg02 (and RCSg03): Wayside Hawkeye Probes, Open5GCore with UPF Router, 5G RAN with Nokia base station, TDD 5G air-interface. Kontron onboard GW with radio modems, Ethernet Switch, Ubuntu Laptop with Hawkeye Probes.</p>	
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Bitrates, loss and latency were measured.	
Tools involved	Hawkeye software with probes.	
Results and KPIs	The result is mainly as expected. The bitrates were conveyed over 5G.	
Primary	Latency and loss were low.	
Complementary		
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	In general: the target Rail Signaling over 5G KPIs are met.	

3.3.2.3 Test Cases and KPIs tables

This section repeats the Test Cases and KPI tables from deliverable [D4.2](#).

However, due to the Field Demo environment with only one hour effective testing, it was not possible (or meaningful) to repeat the tests done the [FhG Lab](#), which took months. Therefore, the tables below often refers to FhG Lab results in deliverable [D4.2](#).

We also must remember that the FhG Lab and IHP Lab setups are different:

- FhG Lab: **the 5G air-interface is a true main bottleneck**, which means that the air-interface related 5QIs 8 and 9 have a clear QoS impact.
- IHP Lab / Field Demo: **the 5G air-interface is not the main bottleneck**, which means that the air-interface related 5QIs 8 and 9 have no meaning.

This section gives an overview of wanted and measured KPI result for:

- CCTV test-cases (RCC).
- Rail Signaling test-cases (RCS).
- Background Traffic test-cases (RCB).

Table 3-10 Test case group RCC (CCTV) – Wanted and Measured result

Test case group RCC (CCTV)			
Test case ID	Title	Target result	Measured result
RCCg02	One train CCTV (5 Mbps in uplink)	Bitrate: 5 Mbps. Latency: <150 ms latency (a guesstimate) Loss ratio: <0.5% (a guesstimate).	Uplink 5 Mbps bitrate no problem. Latency over 5G well below 150 ms, typically lower than 20 ms. Note: moving pictures coding and decoding in the camera and web browser showed a latency of around 300 ms in total. Loss ratio for the higher prio QoS 5QI 8 (compared with 5QI 9 streams) used by 1 stream CCTV was below 0.5%.
RCCg03	Twelve trains CCTV (12x5=60 Mbps in uplink)	Bitrate: 60 Mbps. Latency: <150 ms latency (a guesstimate) Loss ratio: <0.5% (a guesstimate).	<i>Note: this was not possible to test in the Field Demo. The IHP Lab / Field Demo equipment was not capable of 60 Mbps. See D4.2 for FhG Lab results.</i>

Table 3-11 Test case group RCS (Rail Signaling) – Wanted and Measured result

Test case group RCS (Rail Signaling)			
Test case ID	Title	Target result	Measured result
RCSg02	One train Rail Signaling (200 kbps UL/DL)	Bitrate: 200 kbps. Latency: low Loss ratio: low.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 200 kbps is no problem. • Delay for uplink and downlink was lower than 20 ms. • Loss for uplink and downlink was lower than 1%.
RCSv03	Twelve trains RS (2.4 Mbps UL/DL)	<i>Bitrate: 12x200= 2.4 Mbps. Latency: low Loss ratio: low.</i>	<p>Note: this was not possible to test in the Field Demo due to lack of time during the short time the demo equipment was up and running.</p> <p>It is however likely to believe that a Rail Signaling bitrate corresponding to twelve trains, 2.4 Mbps, is very well handled over a 5G cellular network.</p> <p>This can be compared with CCTV which run all the time with a bitrate between 0.5 and 5 Mbps.</p> <p>We also have to remember that the IHP Lab / Field Demo setup had an onboard GW limitation of 30 Mbps.</p> <p>Note: See D4.2 for FhG Lab results.</p>

Table 3-12 Test case group RCB (Background Traffic) – Wanted and Measured result

Test case group RCB (Background Traffic)			
Test case ID	Title	Target result	Measured result
RCBg01	Background Traffic for saturating 5G air-interface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use a bitrate of around 50 to 75% of the speed test result for loading the air-interface. • The reason was to see any QoS differentiation results for the Rail Signaling flows using 5QIs 8 and 9. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The 5G air-interface shows a speed test bitrate of around 30 Mbps (the onboard GW limited the bitrate). • The background traffic for loading the IHP Lab setup was around 20 Mbps. • <i>Note: this can be compared with the Huawei CPE at FhG Lab (which implementation is more hardware based than software) which showed much higher bitrates. See D4.2 for these FhG Lab results.</i>

3.3.2.4 Conclusions – Lessons learned

The field demonstration showed pictures from the camera onboard the train, via the 5G network, to a laptop on Wayside. The bitrate from the camera was around 0.5 Mbps when a picture did not move, and around 5 Mbps when pictures move. The pictures are delayed with around 300 ms using H.264, where the delay of the 5G network is only around 10 ms. This means that the camera and monitoring processing of H.264 frames is the dominant delay. When using MJPEG (only full frames), the delay is shorter, and with H.265 longer.

Rail Signaling flows run in parallel with the CCTV flow, plus sometimes in parallel also with Telephony and Sensors data. 5G is able to support this service

QoS differentiation could be seen over air-interface. The reason is that the air-interface in the Field Demo setup was not the main bottleneck. This means that the different 5QI settings with 5QI 8 and 9 has no effect. Unfortunately the RAN did not support MC 5QI to really appreciate the differentiation when compared with others non-MC 5QI settings.

Based on the results with **FhG** equipment, is likely to believe that a Rail Signaling bitrate corresponding to twelve trains, 2.4 Mbps, is very well handled over a 5G cellular network. Unfortunately there was not enough testing time to assess this as it was done in the lab.

3.3.2.5 Vertical business KPI validation

Test results from the Field Demo in Berlin show that a 5G system is capable of handling CCTV and Rail Signaling. The 5G system with equipment needs to be dimensioned for the traffic it is supposed to carry.

When the 5G air-interface is loaded and when the air-interface is a bottleneck, then QoS with different 5QIs settings, can be recommended.

QoS differentiation could not be shown in the Field Demo in April 2023 in Berlin due to that the air-interface was not the main bottleneck. Note: for clear QoS differentiation results, see the **FhG** Lab results presented in deliverable **D4.2** [2].

5G is the first cellular network generation selected for the first Future Rail Mobile Communication System (FRMCS) deployments, based on FRMCS v2 standard (v1 was for prototyping).

3.3.3 Telephony and Sensor Data

Field demonstration of Railway Telephony and Sensor Data using MCPTT and MCData services via dedicated 5G network took place in April 2023 at the Deutsche Bahn facility *S-Bahn Werk Schöneweide*, southeast of Berlin.

3.3.3.1 Field trial description

The equipment used for the field trial was the very same 5G nomadic node with integrated **KCC**'s MC Services for Railways and rail equipment incl. Rail OBG, Next-Gen Dispatcher and Rail Telephony and Sensor Data apps running on 5G mobiles from the **IHP** Lab.

Figure 3-24 depicts the topology of the setup.

3.3.3.2 Experiment and scenario description

KCC's MCx Services for Railways were installed in the form of several VMs on the nomadic node from **IHP**. The VMs are outlined below:

- **P-CSCF** – The Proxy Call Session Control Function which is the proxy and the first point of contact for the UEs homed in the network.
- **S-CSCF** – The Serving Call Session Control Function which is the central node in the signaling plane. The S-CSCF is responsible for session control and for authenticating subscribers connecting to the P-CSCF. This is done with authentication parameters received in the user profile from the HSS.

- **HSS** – The subscriber database which contains user identities, authentication parameters and profiles.
- **MCx-AS** – The MCx Application Server that hosts and executes Mission Critical Rail Services (MCx). The MCx-AS is the core of all FRMCS Rail Critical Services.
- **MRF** – The Media Resource Function is responsible for connecting voice streams and mixing them for private, conference and group calls. All media flows are connected through the MRF in Rail Critical Network.
- **MR** and **RTPProxy** – The Media Router and related RTP Proxy are used to traverse NAT when MC clients are not directly accessible by the core network routing functions. In addition, the MR serves as a single point which enables the recording and storage of all communications inside of Rail Critical Network.
- **Dispatcher-AS** – The Application Server (AS) related to the Dispatcher Terminals. It serves to coordinate user profiles and to configure the terminals, and adds another layer of features and functionality specifically related to dispatcher functions.
- **UE Config Server (MGMT)** - Serves user profiles and configurations to the UE smartphone clients, coordinates status and reports between the clients and the core server.

The above mentioned deployment provided the following MC services to the mobile clients and fixed dispatcher device in the MCx network:

- MCPTT Voice Calls including Private Calls and Group Calls with normal, imminent peril and emergency priority.
- MCDATA SDS including Private Messages and Group Messages.
- Sensor data delivered via MCDATA SDS to a web application showing orientation of a phone and overall latency in the network.

Version 2022-12-14

5G	5 th Generation 3GPP defined cellular network
CCTV	Closer Circuit Television
CN	Core Network
CPE	Customer Premises Equipment (UE onboard GW)
FhG	Fraunhofer FOKUS in Berlin
GbE	Gigabit per second Ethernet
GW	Gateway
HW	Hardware

IP	Internet Protocol
LAN	Local Area Network
PoE	Power over Ethernet
RAN	Radio Access Network
SW	Software
TDD	Time Division Duplex
UE	User Equipment
UPF	User Plane Function

Figure 3-24 Block diagram for the Rail Critical Services (Telephony and Sensor Data)

Figure 3-25: Nomadic node with deployed Kontron's Mission-Critical Services for Railways and Next-Gen Dispatcher

The 5G SA capable User Equipment (UE), namely Sonim XP10 and Nokia X20 UEs, were equipped with the Rail Telephony App supporting MCPTT and a Sensor App supporting MCDData, connected to PLMN **001 01** and configured for the “mcx” DNN used for critical services.

Additionally, an Rail Onboard Gateway based on railway-certified **KCC** TRACe HW was deployed to provide access to the Rail Critical Services (MCPTT Telephony and MCDData) for onboard devices without 5G capabilities, like onboard Man-Machine Interface (MMI) and **Alstom’s** CCTV camera via onboard Wi-Fi, which was steering the onboard traffic via 5GS using the two CPEs to the MCx core.

Figure 3-26: Rail Onboard Gateway installation with onboard Wi-Fi to 5G connectivity

To allow Kontron’s IMS-based MCx Application Function to request the corresponding 5G Policy and Charging Control Rules incl. delay critical ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (uRLLC), 5G QoS class and guaranteed flow bit rate for mission-critical applications, the 5GC’s Policy Control Function (PCF) exposes the Rx reference-point to the IMS domain to allow the Proxy Call Session Control Function (P-CSCF) to modify:

- the 5G NR Standardized QoS Identifier (5QI),
- Allocation and Retention Priority (ARP),
- Guaranteed Bit Rate (GBR)/non-GBR of the sessions.

The FhG’s PCF’s Rx interface was integrated with KCC’s P-CSCF to support 5G QoS Class identifier (QCI) modification for specific flows. MCx services are defined by 3GPP to use 5QI GBR 65 for MCPTT voice media and 5QI non-GBR 69 for MCPTT signaling. However, these 5QIs are not yet supported by FhG’s PCF. This means that the traffic of the UEs connected via Wi-Fi to the Onboard Gateway were routed by the CPEs via 5GS to the respective MCx Services using the default DNN with only best-effort providing 5QI 9.

5G UEs with the PTT App connected directly to the 5GS were configured with a DNN reserved for mission-critical traffic. Although it is intended to use 5QIs 65 and 69, only the supported 5QIs 9 and 8 were used.

In Table 3-13 the 5QIs outlined in TS23.501 compared with the used 5QI values in the field trial are listed:

Table 3-13 5QI values outlined in TS23.501 vs what were used in the FhG Lab

Outlined wanted 5QI values	Field Trial used 5QI values	Example Services
5QI 65	5QI 9	Mission Critical user plane Push To Talk voice (e.g. MCPTT)
5QI 69	5QI 8	Mission Critical delay sensitive signaling (e.g. MCPTT signaling)

In the Rail Critical Telephony experiment the MCPTT Voice Private and Group Calls connections were established between two or more subscribers, UEs and Dispatcher. Floor control was implemented on top of the group calls and PTT functionality was enabled.

These scenarios (private and group calls) were performed several times at the Schönevide depot and behaved as expected. Voice reliability, quality and latency performed as expected. Latency was roughly 500 ms end-to-end. While not ideal, the implementation of the audio buffers impacts the overall experience of a voice call. Buffering is used to store voice data while waiting for transmission and playback.

Table 3-14 Experiment Rail Critical Telephony - Field

Description	
ExperimentType	Equipment based on the IHP Lab setup adapted for the Field Demo.
Automated	Manual installation, deployment and provisioning
TestCases	RCTg01 On-train voice communication RCTg02 Railway Emergency RCTg06 Performance data application with MCDData
UEs	Sonim XP10, Nokia X20, KCC TRACe
Network Slice	Network Slicing not supported by 5GS

Network Services	5GS best-effort QoS mission-critical 5QI 65 with GBR not supported by RAN
Network Scenario	mobility scenario with moving onboard UE
Exclusive Execution	-
ReservationTime	-
Application	Rail Critical Telephony
Performance targets & SLAs	100/100kbps UL/DL, max. 60ms RTT, max. Packet loss 10 ⁻⁶
Experiment Parameters	PLMN 001/01, mcx DNN, 5QI 8 & 9, no GBR
Edges	The Open5GCore network with RAN used a 5G base station from Nokia.
Remote	The Field Demo was done on site southeast of Berlin at Deutsche Bahn S-Bahn Werk Schöneeweide. No remote operation possible.
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

In the Sensor Data experiment, the data from the onboard accelerometer and gyroscope are reliably transported to a device in the network. The data received can be analyzed and evaluated depending on the requirements of the specific UC.

This scenario was performed several times at the *S-Bahn Werk Schöneeweide* depot and behaved as expected. The UE with the onboard accelerometer and gyroscope was able to select an MCPTT ID as a destination address. SDS messages were reliably delivered synchronously to the destination with a round-trip time of roughly 100 ms. The data received at the destination endpoint was used to recreate the orientation of the mobile in a graphical representation and with a relatively low latency. Ideally, we would transmit the data synchronously and transmit roughly 30 frames per second. This would be required, for example, for remote driver scenarios.

Figure 3-27: Rail Sensor Data application using Rail Onboard Gateway

Table 3-15 Experiment Rail Sensor Data – Field

Description	
ExperimentType	Equipment based on the IHP Lab setup adapted for the Field Demo.
Automated	Manual installation, deployment and provisioning
TestCases	RCDg01 Sensor Data Transmission via MCDData SDS
UEs	Sonim XP10, Nokia X20, Kontron TRACe
Network Slice	Network Slicing not supported by 5GS
Network Services	5GS best-effort QoS mission-critical 5QI 70 with GBR not supported by RAN
Network Scenario	mobility scenario with moving onboard UE
Exclusive Execution	-
ReservationTime	-
Application	Rail Sensor Data
Performance targets & SLAs	100/100kbps UL/DL, max. 200 ms RTT, max. Packet loss 10 ⁻⁶
Experiment Parameters	PLMN 001/01, mcx DNN, 5QI 8 & 9, no GBR
Edges	The Open5GCore network with RAN used a 5G base station from Nokia.
Remote	The Field Demo was done on site southeast of Berlin at Deutsche Bahn S-Bahn Werk Schöneweide. No remote operation possible.
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Additionally, experiments with a so-called Heartbeat Failure (periodic connection monitoring and diagnosis of a MCx client running on using 5G-SA UE) was executed. The Heartbeat Failure scenarios comprise a UE which is registered in the MCx network but moves outside of coverage. Once coverage is re-established, the regular heartbeats are acknowledged end-to-end by the server and a positive confirmation is given to the user that service is again available.

This scenario was performed several times at the *S-Bahn Werk Schöneweide* depot and behaved as expected. The UE was reliable in reconnecting to the network and the heartbeat service performed as expected. In addition, loss of coverage while there is an ongoing call does not automatically result in a drop of that call. The call can be maintained on the UE while inside of a coverage gap, and resumed when coverage is available again. If a call can be maintained is dependent on several factors including the length of time that the UE resides in the coverage gap.

The Rail Onboard Gateway was as well reliable in reconnecting to the network after residing in a coverage gap. The UEs connecting via Wi-Fi to the gateway were then successfully able to communicate with the MC server and the heartbeats were again successfully transmitted.

Table 3-16 Experiment Heartbeat Failure - Field

Description	
ExperimentType	Equipment based on the IHP Lab setup adapted for the Field Demo.
Automated	Manual installation, deployment and provisioning
TestCases	Heartbeat Failure
UEs	Sonim XP10, Nokia X20, KCC TRACe
Network Slice	Network Slicing not supported by 5GS

Network Services	5GS best-effort QoS MC 5QI 65 with GBR not supported by RAN
Network Scenario	mobility scenario with moving onboard UE
Exclusive Execution	-
ReservationTime	-
Application	Rail Critical Telephony
Performance targets & SLAs	100/100kbps UL/DL, max. 60 ms RTT, max. Packet loss 10 ⁻⁶
Experiment Parameters	PLMN 001/01, mcx DNN, 5QI 8 & 9, no GBR
Edges	The Open5GCore network with RAN used a 5G base station from Nokia.
Remote	The Field Demo was done on site southeast of Berlin at Deutsche Bahn S-Bahn Werk Schöneweide. No remote operation possible.
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

For the whole field trial the PLMN 001/01 was used at the Schöneweide depot. In the **FhG** lab, the original implementation of PLMN 999/56 proved to be problematic for the 5G-SA devices (UEs and gateway) attempting to connect to the 5G SA network. The PLMN 001/01 was reserved and used by other setup in the Lab. After re-planning for deployment of PLMN 001/01 reconfiguring the 5GS in the **IHP** nomadic node, the 5G UEs and the TRACe Gateway could reliably attach and maintain their network connections in the field trial.

Table 3-17 Scenario Rail Critical Telephony and Sensor Data - Field

Scenario Description – Field	
Radio access technology (RAT)	5G NR
Standalone / Non-Standalone (if applicable)	Standalone
Cell Power	23 dBm
Frequency band:	n78
Maximum bandwidth per component carrier	100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz
Cyclic Prefix	normal
Massive MIMO	4x4
Duplex mode	TDD
TDD uplink/downlink pattern	DDDSU
User location and speed	0 km/h
Background traffic	Potentially, but sporadic and low throughput
Computational resources available	N/A

3.3.3.3 Test Cases and KPIs tables

Rail critical voice services deployed in the core VMs, were tested using end-user devices running the Rail PTT App. Responsiveness of the PTT App and the quality of the voice communications relies on low-latency network connections. Individual KPIs are available with typical call setup times of ~200 msecs and typical times to request the floor of ~30 ms. Voice communications using 5QIs

65 and 69 were not tested as default 5QIs were configured in the 5GCore for the DNNs used for the tests.

The Dispatcher Application running on the Dispatcher Terminal connected to the Dispatcher Application Server (AS) and downloaded all available application updates and configuration needed to register and run in the MC network. Both the Dispatcher AS and the Dispatcher Terminal were connected directly to the core via virtual NICs and Ethernet respectively. This implies that they were not directly dependent on 5G for a QoS. Download of the application software and configuration for the Dispatcher Terminal was reliable and fast.

The MC subscribers and all calls between the Dispatcher and the MCx subscribers were dependent on the 5G network for a quality of service related to voice communications between the individual endpoints. Calls between MCx subscribers were dependent on the 5G network for quality of service. Communications between Dispatcher and MCx subscribers were reliable, call setup time was reliably fast and voice quality was good.

Additionally, it was noted that there is a slight delay when observing the mouth-to-ear latency between the MCx clients. It is noted however that this latency appears to be normal across all clients and transmission technologies. A more advanced setup will be required to measure this latency and analyze why it appears. Some factors contributing mouth-to-ear latency are listed below.

- Implementation of the client hardware – microphone and speaker.
- Implementation of audio buffers to maintain enough data in the buffer to reliably transmit audio information in the RTP packets in a timely manner - i.e. 1 packet every 20 msec containing around 160 bytes of audio data depending on the sample rate and the compression of the applied audio codec.
- The audio codec applied to the recorded audio data.
- The audio codec applied to the audio data in hardware or software.
- The transmission delay in the 5G network including any congestion and prioritization caused by parallel access of the 5G network by competing clients, and including interference from competing base stations and UEs.
- The processing time required by the Media Router (MR) and the Multimedia Resource Function (MRF), including transcoding if required.

The requirements for mission-critical KPIs including measurement definition is standardized in 3GPP TS 22.179. The following figures and subsequent chapters describe the targeted and achieved KPIs.

The prerequisites for executing the KPIs were:

- on-demand MCPTT session was used.
- no MCPTT XML body encryption was used.
- no MRF transcoding was performed, all rail clients were using G.711 audio codec.
- predefined MCPTT group and emergency group call was used in RCTg02.

The KPIs were evaluated according to 3GPP TS 22.179 requirements. The rail critical service shall be capable of providing the performance specified by the standard for all affiliated rail group members.

Figure 3-28 3GPP TS 22.179 illustrating PTT access times

Figure 3-29 3GPP TS 22.179 illustrating late call entry time

For rail applications and users, one of the most important performance criteria is the MCPTT Access time (KPI 1).

The MCPTT Access time is defined as the time between when a rail user requests to speak (normally by pressing the push-to-talk button on device) and when the user gets a signal to start speaking. This time does not include confirmations from receiving users.

5G cKPI1 MCPTT Access Time measurement results

Figure 3-30 Measurement results of MCPTT Access Time (KPI 1)

According to TS 22.179:

- [R-6.15.3.2-012] For group calls where no acknowledgement is requested from affiliated MCPTT group members, the MCPTT Service shall provide an MCPTT Access time (KPI 1) less than 300 ms for 95% of all MCPTT Request.
- [R-6.15.3.2-012a] For group and private calls where the call is already established, the MCPTT Service shall provide an MCPTT Access time (KPI 1) less than 300 ms for 95% of all MCPTT PTT Requests.
- [R-6.15.3.2-013] For MCPTT Emergency Group Calls and Imminent Peril Calls the MCPTT Service shall provide an MCPTT Access time (KPI 1) less than 300 ms for 99% of all MCPTT Requests.

The KPI 1 measurements were fulfilling the TS 22.179 requirements.

The E2E MCPTT Access time (KPI 2) is defined as the time between when the rail user requests to speak (normally by pressing the push-to-talk button on device) and when this user gets a signal to start speaking. This includes MCPTT call establishment (if applicable) and possibly acknowledgement from first receiving user before voice can be transmitted. Group calls can be set up with or without acknowledgements from receiving users.

5G cKPI2 MCPTT Access Time measurement results

Figure 3-31 measurement results of E2E MCPTT access time (KPI 2)

According to TS 22.179:

- [R-6.15.3.2-014] For group calls where automatic acknowledgement is requested from the UEs of the affiliated MCPTT group members, the MCPTT Service shall provide an E2E MCPTT Access time (KPI 2) less than 1000 ms for users under coverage of the same network.
- [R-6.15.3.2-019] The MCPTT Service shall provide private call E2E MCPTT Access time (KPI 2) equal to or less than 1000 ms for users under coverage of the same network when the MCPTT private call is setup in the Manual Commencement mode.
- [R-6.15.3.2-020] The MCPTT Service shall provide private call E2E MCPTT Access time (KPI 2) equal to or less than 1000 ms for users under coverage of the same network when the MCPTT private call is setup in the Automatic Commencement mode.

The KPI 2 measurement results were fulfilling the TS 22.179 requirements.

A rail user is able to join or leave already ongoing MCPTT Group calls. Late call entry is the activity when an Affiliated MCPTT Group Member joins an MCPTT Group call in which other Affiliated MCPTT Group Members are already active. The Late call entry time (KPI 4) is the time to enter an ongoing MCPTT Group call measured from the time that a rail user decides to monitor such an MCPTT Group Call, to the time when the MCPTT UE's speaker starts to play the audio. The performance requirements for Late call entry time only applies when there is ongoing voice transmitted at the time the MCPTT User joins the call.

5G cKPI4 Late Call Entry Time measurement results

Figure 3-32 measurement results of Late Call Entry Time (KPI 4)

According to TS 22.179:

- [R-6.15.4.2-003] The maximum Late call entry time (KPI 4a) for calls without application layer encryption within one MCPTT system shall be less than 150 ms for 95% of all Late call entry requests.

The KPI 4 measurement results were fulfilling the TS 22.179 requirements but are very close to the allowed limit.

5G MCDData SDS end-to-end Latency Time measurement results

Figure 3-33 measurement results of MCDData SDS E2E Latency Time

Furthermore, call invite/connection/disconnection times provide further indication on performance of the system.

Figure 3-34: Private Call Invite/Connected/Disconnected Times over 5G-SA

3.3.3.4 Conclusions – Lessons learned

Device manufacturers are still early in their implementation and roll-out of 5G SA capable devices. Devices selected earlier in the planning process proved to be unreliable when connecting to the 5G SA network. This unreliability persisted over several RAN network implementations and PLMNs. The selected 5G SA devices (Sonim XP10, Nokia X20 and the Kontron TRACe Gateway) all showed good reliability after moving to PLMN 001/01 for the Berlin Trial.

5GS standalone networks are well suited for deployment of MC Networks and applications from the performance point of view. The service quality, latency and throughput are all adequate for MC UCs over dedicated 5G network. However, the 5GC and 5G-NR in use did not provide any slicing capabilities and no support for the defined mission-critical 5QIs for QoS control. In real field deployments of rail critical services on shared 5G systems, a lack of slicing, MC QoS, congestion protection and isolation of critical traffic all pose insurmountable barriers. This is an area where 5GC and 5G-NR vendors still need to invest efforts into implementation of slicing, congestion control and mission.critical QoS into their enterprise product lines, which were used in these trials.

QoS must be implemented and tested in a 5G SA network to be certain that critical voice connections are prioritized over secondary data / voice applications. That said, given the available bandwidth in a 5G SA network, a calculation can be made on the number of devices deployed vs. the amount of bandwidth required per device. Other bandwidth-limiting functionalities like firewalls can be implemented in the network to limit the amount of bandwidth per device. This is not a replacement for QoS, but can be used as a work-around while QoS is implemented in the 5G network.

Considering a deployment of a Mission Critical Network using a nomadic node and coupled with a standalone RAN, deployment can be achieved within a reasonable amount of time. This preparation time can be optimised with additional product development. This means that a deployment can be foreseen consisting of a single node requiring limited external power connections and an automated, optimized process for power-on / boot procedures. UEs and other clients should be able to connect to the freshly deployed nomadic network within a matter of minutes.

3.3.3.5 Vertical business KPI validation

FhG’s Open5GCore and 5G-NR RAN exceeded most expectations during lab tests and field trials in dedicated mode. Therefore, 5G SA technology is deemed to be very well suited for Mission Critical Applications for live customers including national rail operators. This confirms 5G-SA as the chosen technology for FRMCS deployments and standardization work continues in that direction with the goal to start deployment of nationwide networks in late 2026. First trials are currently ongoing. The importance of 5G-SA for the railway industry and for FRMCS cannot be overstated.

Particularly important going forward is the following:

- additional QoS validation,
- congestion control and traffic isolation in shared 5G networks,

- extended mobility in a home network, and
- roaming between networks - including both mission critical networks and public mobile operators.

Roaming between disparate networks (mission critical and public mobile operators) must enable access to mission critical components deployed in the home network as well as the ability to roam into foreign mission critical networks. Mission critical communications also require a level of connectivity such that ongoing private and group communications can be maintained across transitions between core and access networks, and this with minimal latency and / or gaps in voice and data communications while transitioning. Emergency calls and other emergency services must be delivered reliably to all mission critical devices roaming in the various access networks. This can be achieved using multiple factors of reliability.

- Geo-redundant core networks.
- Resilient (disparate) access networks using deployments schemes where onboard devices can always communicate with 2 or more radio access nodes.
- Access to multiple access networks – 5G-SA and Wi-Fi for example.
- Multipath technologies for reliable delivery of content.
- Physical availability (redundancy) of multiple mission critical devices onboard.
- Fallback paths for communications including both devices and access networks.

Based on the lessons learned from 5G-VICTORI, **KCC** continues with additional EU-related research projects including 5G-RACOM and EERJU R2DATO. This comes in the form of joint and future collaboration / exploitation with railway infrastructure managers like SNCF, DB and other partners. In parallel, **KCC** continues to prepare for deployments with its own customers and with the target of deploying FRMCS based on Mission Critical 5G-SA Networks. Specifications work still continues for FRMCS and we use the knowledge gained from 5G-VICTORI and other trials to enhance those specifications. All-in-all, 5G-VICTORI has been a valuable research program for **KCC** and its partners.

3.4 UC #3 “CDN services in dense, static and mobile environments”

3.4.1 Field trial description

One of the objectives of 5G-VICTORI is to propose a viable solution for provisioning large amounts of data in media Content Delivery Networks (CDNs) by utilising 5G technologies, e.g. for railway environments as defined in **UC #3**. To provide a conclusive proof of concept of the developed solution, a final field trial was performed in a controlled environment at the Deutsche Bahn facility *S-Bahn Werk Schöneweide*, as described in this section.

The experiment undertaken for the final field trial extends on the work in the two preliminary field trials, which are reported in deliverable **D4.2** [2] sections 3.6.1 and 3.6.5, respectively. The first preliminary field trial was conducted at an enclosed railway track at the Deutsche Bahn facility *S-Bahn Werk Schöneweide*, where the data shower from the station server to the train server was successfully performed in a mobility scenario. In order to further verify the system performance in an operational environment, a second field trial of **UC #3** took place at Berlin Central Station. In this field trial, due to challenges with the availability of the tracks and scheduling of trains, the data shower was performed only in a static scenario, with the train being parked at the S-Bahn platform.

3.4.2 Experiment and scenario descriptions

An overview of the final field trial deployment at the Berlin-Schöneweide test site is provided in Figure 3-35. The complete system setup, including hardware components and antenna geometry, is identical to the one that was successfully verified in the preliminary field trials and extensively

described in deliverable D4.2 section 3.6.2. The parameters of the PTMP mmWave link established between the station and train server are presented in Table 3-18.

Figure 3-35 Overview of the system setup for the Berlin-Schöneweide final field trial: a) Wide-angle perspective from the train node T towards the station nodes S1 and S2 during the arrival of the train to the designated position, b) View of the node T mounted in the train

Table 3-18 Scenario description Berlin-Schöneweide final field trial for UC #3

Scenario Description	
Radio access technology (RAT)	mmWave track-to-train
Standalone / Non-Standalone (if applicable)	N/A
Cell Power	14 dBm
Frequency band:	58,32 GHz
Maximum bandwidth per component carrier	2,16 GHz
Sub-carrier spacing	N/A
Number of component carriers	N/A
Cyclic Prefix	normal
Massive MIMO	N/A
Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) schemes (codeword and number of layers)	N/A
Modulation schemes	Downlink: $\pi/2$ -QPSK 13/16 Uplink: $\pi/2$ -QPSK 13/16 (802.11ad MCS7 2502Mbps)
Duplex mode	TDD
TDD uplink/downlink pattern	N/A
Contention based random access procedure/contention free	contention based
User location and speed	0 km/h and 20 km/h
Background traffic	none
Computational resources available	N/A

The field trial emulates a typical S-Bahn operational environment, with an S-Bahn train arriving at a designated mock-up platform and stopping for an interval of 30 seconds, before departing in the same direction. The mmWave **T** node is mounted onboard the train such that during the stop, it is centered at the mid-position with respect to the **S1/S2** platform nodes, operating in a PTMP configuration. The video data from the **RBB** catalog was previously ingressed, filtered for the relevant subset of resolutions and audio codecs that are deemed viable for playout on primarily mobile devices, i.e. 4K and similar resolutions where dropped. After filtering, all manifests¹ are automatically rewritten and the data is “chunked” into segments that are optimised for bulk transfers. This is a necessity as transferring the data as is, i.e. as ~10MB MPEGTS chunks leads to a significant overhead and reduces net transfer rates massively. The prepared data is then transferred via the mmWave link to the railSTACK server onboard the train during the 30 second interval. The parameters of the experiment are summarised in Table 3-19.

Table 3-19 Experiment description Berlin-Schöneweide final field trial for UC #3

Experiment Description	
ExperimentType	Standard
Automated	Manual
TestCases	MCBg03
UEs	N/A
Network Slice	N/A
Network Services	definition of the network services Catalogues
Network Scenario	refers to Table 3-A
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	0.5 min
Application	Not yet onboarded
Performance targets & SLAs	1.7 Gbps
Experiment Parameters	S1/S2 antenna height 1,8 m S1/S2 antenna distance to track 4 m S1/S2 inter-antenna distance 12 m
Edges	N/A
Remote	N/A (no additional platform considered)
Remote Descriptor	N/A (no additional platform considered)
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

3.4.3 Test Cases and KPIs tables

3.4.3.1 Test using mmWave only

The performance of the mmWave wireless link, as well as the data transfer statistics, were monitored real-time during the experiment using a custom-made graphical user interface. One instance of the test runs performed for the final field trial is presented in Figure 3-36, where a test set of **7.5GB** of video data was successfully cached to the railSTACK server. Due to the prolonged association time of the mmWave nodes, for this instance the stop interval needed to be extended to 40 seconds, in order to complete the targeted cache load. The mmWave link parameter readings show that the link margin was sufficient to achieve the highest PHY rate of the 60 GHz radios of approx. **2.5 Gbps**, for both links **T-S1** and **T-S2**. By observing the link status, it can be concluded that the train node **T** did

¹ A video manifest describes the video stream for the player, defining the available streams, and the locations of all the files required to play the video.

connect to both station nodes **S1** and **S2** simultaneously, which occurred during the parking of the train at the mock-up platform. As shown, the data transfer initially was performed through the link **T-S2** (435 MB) during arrival, after which the link switched to **T-S1** for the remainder of the data set (7033 MB) in the final parking position.

Track-to-Train mmWave Link Monitor

Figure 3-36 Performance monitoring of the mmWave link onboard the train during the Berlin-Schöneeweide final field trial (media CDN)

3.4.3.1 Test using mmWave and 5G

As an extension to the final field trial for **UC #3**, an additional experiment was performed to compare the performance of two different wireless technologies for the data transfer from the landside to the train server. Specifically, the performance of the 60 GHz mmWave link based on 802.11ad COTS nodes (utilised for all previous field trials of **UC #3**) was benchmarked against the performance of a 5G link based on a Huawei CPE and Nokia RRH/5G Nomadic node, operating at a carrier frequency of 3.7 GHz and channel bandwidth of 100 MHz. It should be noted that the experiment was performed in a lab environment at **IHP**, due to the bulk setup of the 5G nomadic node. A high-level overview of the test setup is provided in Figure 3-37.

Figure 3-37 Overview of the setup for the extended UC #3 trial performed in a lab at IHP, showing the two different link configurations (mmWave and 5G) between the train and station server

The experiment was conducted in two instances: one using a PTP 60 GHz mmWave link (nodes **T** and **S1**) between the landside and train server and another by replacing it with the 3.7 GHz 5G link. The link performance was benchmarked by running TCP/IP iperf3 and ping instances in a 60 s interval for both cases, with the results presented in Figure 3-38. As expected, the mmWave link is able to provide a significantly higher iperf3 throughput (mean: 1.65 Gbps, std.dev: 62.3 Mbps) compared to the 3.7 GHz 5G link (mean: 287.23 Mbps, std. dev.: 31.55 Mbps), due to the inherently larger modulation bandwidth. With respect to the ping-measured latency, the mmWave link exhibited a significantly lower RTT (mean: 0.69 ms, std.dev: 0.29 ms) compared to the 3.7GHz 5G link (mean: 15.93 ms, std. dev.: 5.85 ms).

The same holds true for the “actual” transfer of media assets. While the mmWave was perfectly capable for transmitting the ~8GB payload within the envisioned time frame of 30 sec, this could not be replicated using a 5G connection. This is likely explained, at least partially, by the fact that from the mmWave setup direct fibre connections could be used to connect the cache and the railSTACK server to the nomadic nodes. For the 5G approach significantly more equipment is required, which all have impact on the end-to-end performance.

Figure 3-38 Performance benchmark of the iperf3 TCP/IP throughput and ping RTT for the mmWave and 5G connection between the landside and train server

The test report that stems from the final field trial in Berlin **UC #3** is presented in Table 3-20

Table 3-20 Test Report for the final field trial in Berlin UC #3

Field	Description
Test Case ID	MCBg03
Facility, Site	Berlin, S-Bahn Werk Schöneeweide (Berlin)
Description	Media data in the station cache (that were not contained in the train’s media cache already), also known as “media content delta”, shall be uploaded to the train’s media cache via the mmWave data link whilst the train is stopped at the station. To transmit the media content delta during the train’s standing time, an average PHY data rate of at least

	2.5 Gbps is required. The test case succeeds if the entire media content delta is transmitted to the train cache.
Executed by	Partner: IHP , PXI
Purpose	On board network deployment and track-to train connectivity demonstration in a mobility scenario
Scenario	refers to Table 3-18
Slice Configuration	No slice configuration was performed
Components involved	1. 5G data link (mmWave in this case) 2. Media cache in station (5G platform) 3. Media cache on train (5G train)
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Node association time, throughput
Tools involved	iperf3, ping, GUI developed by IHP , media segmentation and caching by PXI
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	Mobility demonstration: <i>mmWave track-to-train connectivity: Throughput≈~1.7 Gbps cached data: 7.5 GB within 40 second stop</i>
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	<i>Throughput KPI passed for the mmWave nodes, data transfer completed in typical train stop interval</i>

3.4.4 Conclusions – Lessons learned

Performing the trials in a realistic railway environment required dealing with significant challenges, including but not limited to: device mounting regulations, accessibility/availability of test trains and platforms. However, these also provided valuable insights for adaptation of the system design, in terms of antenna geometry, wireless link parameters, video data segmentation, etc., that have been described in the experiment reports.

As wireless connectivity is one of the main aspects in the **UC #3** mobility scenario, several design considerations can be made from the trials. Specifically for the mmWave links, ensuring unobstructed line-of-sight path between the train and station nodes during the arrival, stop and departure of the train is critical. Furthermore, distributing multiple mmWave nodes at the edges and midpoints of the platform would not only provide better coverage in the PTMP setup, but would also allow for node association to occur during the arrival of the train and use the stop interval more efficiently for the data transfer.

While, conceptually, the mmWave link simply serves as a high-bandwidth network connection, the particularities of the setup needed to be reflected. This involves careful selection of the subset of data that is to be transferred in the first place (dropping of highest quality for example) and also the packaging of the data. To make optimal use of a high-bandwidth but only shortly available connection, the data had to chunk such that the transfer algorithms overhead was minimised. After a large number of trials ~250MB were identified to be optimal. Similarly, the data synchronisation/transfer methods of railSTACK had to be adapted to reliably establish a connection to the ground system with minimal delay to maximise the available time for data transfer.

In summary, the proposed system concept for **UC #3** has been successfully verified throughout numerous field trials, both in a static and mobility scenaria in typical railway environments. The goal of caching large amounts of video data to the train server in the order of 7GB within relatively short 30s intervals has been shown viable when using high-bandwidth mmWave wireless links. The

customised ingress and transfer preparation was integrated with an existing commercial product, **PXI railSTACK**, to achieve a viable, fully automatic, end-to-end integration proving the viability of the approach.

3.4.5 Vertical business KPI validation

Despite varying results in terms of throughput and transfer duration, the overall viability of the UC could be demonstrated. We achieved a working end-to-end integration. From data ingress and transformation, to the “data shower” of the train while at stop up to a playout on mobile devices is technically feasible and performed reliably.

3.5 Conclusions – Berlin

The partners **FhG** and **IHP** designed, integrated and deployed a fully operational nomadic 5G network for hosting the Berlin 5G-VICTORI services. It has served the functional requirements for three UCs: **UC #1.2**, **UC #1.3** and **UC #3** involving heterogeneous service providers ranging from media to transportation.

A summary of the main conclusions from the trial activities is as follows:

- All UCs have been demonstrated in 2023 in the field, which was an operational environment provided by Deutsche Bahn. The trials and (some) provided services were initially supposed to be offered to the general public, however several restrictions at Berlin Central Station led to decide for a test environment for the trials.
- **UC #1.2** has proved in an operational environment that 5G is a suitable technology for streaming remote rendered 3D applications if reliability and other QoS parameters especially latency can be guaranteed. – For the digital twin, 5G provided sufficient bandwidth and latency for the render streaming and user interaction parts, which will be improved in future networks beyond 5G. Multiple concurrent users could connect without breaking the service, and that is promising.
- **UC #1.3** services were fully tested in an operational environment with success, despite the limitations in discriminating MC services due to RAN constraints. QoS has been implemented to differentiate between connections that need to be prioritized over secondary ones.
- **UC #3** was delivered using mmWave as the wireless transport technology providing track-to-train connectivity. A data rate of up to 1.6 Gbps has been obtained in two field trials in operational environments. The goal of caching large amounts of video data to the train server in the order of 7GB within relatively short 30s intervals has been shown viable when utilizing high-bandwidth mmWave wireless links. In addition, 5G has been assessed in parallel to the initial trial in a lab environment using the nomadic 5G node. The results stemming from the use of 5G reveal that still mmWaves underperform 5G in both data rate and latency, given the high modulation bandwidth of the former.

4 Field Trials in Patras

Field trials in Patras took place at **TRA** (Railway vertical) and **ADMIE** (Energy/ Factories of the future vertical) operational environments during May and June 2023. The final demonstration of **UC #1.1** and **UC #3** took place during the night of the 26th of June at the operational environment of **TRA** (TRAI NOSE depot). The final demonstration of **UC #2** took place during the 27th of June.

4.1 Detailed Network topology for the trials

4.1.1 Transport network deployment

To execute the UCs in the area of Patras (and integrate these sites with the Patras5G facility), 5G-VICTORI transport network deployment in Patras was extended to reach out to the two major vertical sites and interconnected 4 gNodeBs for the various UCs. Patras 5G-VINNI main facility on University of Patras (**UoP**) campus is interconnected with **ADMIE** main facility in Rion (point **ADMIE** for execution of trials and tests related to **UC #2**) and with **TRAI NOSE** Depot in Patras City Center (point **TRAI NOSE_1** for execution of trials and tests related to **UC #1.1** and **UC #3**), via **ICOM**'s high-throughput, low-latency E-band backhaul network.

The final transport network that interconnects the main cloud facility at **UoP** with each of the trials' sites (**ADMIE**) and **TRAI NOSE_1** is depicted in Figure 4-1 b).

a) Patras transport network diagram diagram deployed for the field trials

b) Transport network and technologies deployed at each Patras facility

Figure 4-1 Patras transport network

Figure 4-2 Network topology UC #1.1

Figure 4-3 Deployed 5G RAN network at ADMIE facility – Patras

4.1.2 Network topology for UC #1.1

The 5G-VICTORI 4-stanchion transport network deployment interconnecting the on-board network with the 5G Core at the **TRA** depot, is illustrated in Figure 4-2. The network layout and the technologies utilised have been analysed in deliverable **D2.3** [5]. As shown in Figure 4-2, mmWave and Sub-6 technologies are used interchangeably along the train route for **UC #1.1**.

4.1.3 Network topology for UC #2

The transport network deployment interconnects the private indoor network deployed at the **ADMIE** premises with the Patras 5G-VINNI main facility at **UoP**. 5G RAN solutions and appropriate edge computing resources have been deployed at **ADMIE** facilities (see Figure 4-3) as analysed in deliverable **D2.3** [5].

4.1.4 Network topology for UC #3

The transport network depicted in Figure 4-1 interconnects the gNodeB deployed for **UC #3** and **COSM** facility as described in the section for **UC #3** (section 4.4).

4.2 UC #1.1 Provisioning of Railway Services

The scope of **UC #1.1** is to:

- Demonstrate a disaggregated multi-technology 5G cellular network addressing the railway environment specific requirements and challenges.
- Explore multi-technology transport network connectivity through a variety of technologies, including both mmWave and Sub-6 GHz technologies.
- Provide high-speed, low latency network connectivity on-board (**KCC** Critical operation services, CCTV on board).

For that purpose the Greek cluster has deployed an innovative network, comprising two parts:

- a 4-stanchion wireless network along the railtrack that was used for the trials interconnected to the main edge hub, where a server with all application elements, 5G core and mobility management were deployed, and
- an on board network with 5G access point, server, switch and wireless network deployments for the interconnection to the 4-stanchion network.

4.2.1 Field trial description

The objective of this UC is to demonstrate eMBB functionality through heterogeneous access technologies for on-board network connectivity in a railway setup leveraging the 5G-VINNI facility in Patras. There are several innovations that concern the field trials of the specific UC other than the fact that a 1 km train to railtrack network has been deployed in an operational environment in addition to on-board network deployment was showcased. For the field trials of **UC #1.1**, we used 5G technology on board based on OpenAirInterface (OAI), an open source technology and in line with the overall 5G-VICTORI architecture adopting a fully disaggregated 5G deployment option that is tailored for rail environments. Specifically, the trials exhibited eMBB functionality through heterogeneous technology access for on-board network connectivity in a railway setup. Furthermore integration with novel mobility management platform that was developed for 5G-VICTORI was performed. To execute the trial, interconnection of on-board devices with the trackside and the trackside with the core network was showcased.

Specifically, for the purposes of the trial, we built a network that ran along 1 km of railtrack and deployed 4 stanchions along this railtrack. The temporarily deployed stanchions were equipped with wireless antennas, nodes, switches – in some cases also power generators (see deliverables **D2.3** [5] and **D4.2** [2]) and were interconnected with the main hub at the Operations Room through a wired network (fibre and PoE). All stanchions and the fibre network were set up temporarily and only for the purpose of tests at night, when the rail tracks were not used by operational trains carrying passengers and they were decommissioned early every morning before the normal operation of trains was starting again. The central hub (Central switch and server) was deployed at an Operation Centre (temporarily at the Depot). The Operations Centre for the field trials was hosted at a newly deployed server with the Mobility management and Applications that were required, and was connected to the **UoP** cloud.

For the interconnection of each stanchion antenna to the Operations Room, a combined PoE and fibre transport network was deployed. For the interconnection of the each of the stanchion antennas to the onboard network, corresponding technologies were deployed on board. The on-board network deployment for Patras trials had multiple (non-permanently deployed) antennas. With respect to the 5G technology deployed on board, Table 4-1 summarises its elements.

Table 4-1 Scenario Description (Configuration of setup at Patras facility in June 2023’s demo)

Deployment Options	Option_5GVINNI_1 - OAIFor UC #1.1
Comments	This is an indoor (onboard) option for UC1
Open- Source	Yes
SA/NSA	SA
Cloud options	Yes (OpenStack, Kubernetes, Openshift)
MANO	OSM
Core	OpenAirInterface (OAI) Core Network
RAN	USRP B210, USRP N310, USRP X310
UE	Google Pixel 6, Quectel RMQ500GL

4.2.2 Experiment and scenario descriptions

4.2.2.1 On-board network deployment

The on-board train deployment consists of several devices used as either parts of the communication links or parts for the offered applications on top. These include the following (see figure below):

- 2 mmWave nodes (one on the front of the train and one on the back) that ensure communication with the trackside mmWave stanchions (**D0** and **D2** points). The nodes are mounted outside of the train, and 1 Gbps Ethernet cables connect them to the mobility management server on the train.
- 1 sub-6GHz node, custom made by **UTH**, which is located inside the train and connected with the mobility management server. Wiring is installed from the node to the external part of the train, where 3 antennas are mounted. The Sub-6 GHz node is used for communicating with the Sub-6 GHz stanchions (**D1** and **D3**).
- The mobility management server, located on board and bridges 4 different connections: 1) 2 coming from the train mmWave nodes, 2) 1 coming from the Sub-6 GHz node, and 3) 1 coming from the application server that is used as a traffic generator. The server is using a P4 based programmable software switch, which decides which path shall be activated at any time. The decisions are based on querying the Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP) interfaces of the devices participating in the train-to-track links, and based on their metrics, as well as the location of the train, decides which link is used.
- An application server, used to run the traffic generator for our experiments. It also acts as a router for the rest of the applications running on the train, in order to push the traffic to the mobility management framework, and subsequently the train-to-track network.
- A server running the OAI RAN in a disaggregated CU/DU split configuration. The server interfaces with a Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) that is used to create the actual 5G network within the train. The OAI RAN is connected to the OAI 5G Core Network located at the Operations room, through the mobility management and track-to-train network.
- A laptop device, equipped with a 5G modem (Quectel RM-500Q-GL), used to measure the 5G connection of the cell, as it is backhauled backhaul over the fluctuating track-to-train network.
- A Wi-Fi access point, used for connecting to a local train network, which communicates with the trackside and subsequently the operations room through the mobility management framework.

- A Real Time Streaming Protocol (RTSP) IP camera, mounted outside of the train, able to stream real-time footage to the operations room over the track-to-train network.
- The different components and cabling deployed inside a server rack on the train.

Figure 4-4 All elements of the fully deployed on board train network deployment as used for the Patras trials

4-stanchion deployment

Figure 4-5 The 4-stanchion deployment (UTH and IHP)

The trackside network consists of four different points (**D0**, **D1**, **D2**, **D3**) that communicate with either a fiber or 10 Gbps Ethernet links with the Operations room. The technologies available at each stanchion are either mmWave (**D0** and **D2**) or Sub-6 GHz (**D1** and **D3**). The first two stanchions (**D0** and **D1**) are connected with an Ethernet link, terminated at two different ports on the mobility management server within the Operations room. **D2** and **D3** links are using a single fiber link to connect to a switch located within the Operations room, with VLAN tags differentiating the traffic coming from each one of them. Traffic coming from them is subsequently delivered to the two different VLANs and terminated to two different network interfaces on the mobility management server in the Operations Room. The fibre connection is running for approximately 300 m from the depot, and is switched to Ethernet links to provide network connectivity to the **D2** and **D3** points. PoE injectors are also used for the case of the mmWave links (**D0** and **D2**) so as to provide power to the nodes installed on the stanchions. For the case of **D1** and **D3**, power generators were used in order to power the Sub-6 GHz nodes.

For the case of the Sub-6 GHz nodes, custom nodes were provided by **UTH**. These consist of high-end PCs, equipped with IEEE 802.11 ac and ax cards. The two different cards were used with either a 3x3 or 4x4 MIMO configuration for the static setups. The team concluded that the most stable setup (and given the mobility of the train) was achieved with the 3x3 MIMO setup for the 802.11ac cards, allowing effective throughput when using a static setup of up to 550 Mbps. Throughput of up to 900 Mbps was observed in the 4x4 MIMO setup, but in a highly unstable manner, and hence the 3x3 setup was used. Similarly, the 802.11ax cards were not able to achieve high throughput speeds in a consistent and reproducible manner. Towards being able to achieve higher Modulation and Coding Schemes (MCS) in higher distances, directional panel antennas were used and mounted on the stanchions. The antennas were configurable for their sector size to 60, 90 or 120 degrees (and respective gains of 21, 20 and 19 dBi). Through extensive testing, the 90-degree configuration yielded the highest throughput in higher distances and was selected for the final demonstration.

The mmWave nodes are COTS 60-GHz 802.11ad-compliant devices (Mikrotik wAP 60Gx3). They utilize Qualcomm QCA6335 chip for digital signal processing, supporting up to MCS8 according to the IEEE802.11ad standard. The radio-frequency (RF) front-end is based on Qualcomm’s QCA631 chip with three 6x6 phased-array antennas supporting beam steering in 2D. With three sectors, the modules are capable of 180° coverage in azimuth. However, a net data rate of 1 Gbps is possible because of 1 GbE connection.

4.2.2.2 Demonstrations and results – May-June 2023

Before the 5G-VICTORI final demonstration event showcased in the 2nd half of June 2023 in Patras, an additional preliminary field trial, similar to the one reported in deliverable **D4.2**, was carried out in May 2023 for **UC #1.1** including mobility handover testing.

This field trial took place at the premises of the TRAINOSE depot in Patras, Greece. The test track, shown in Figure 4-6, is located within the depot limits. Compared to the first field trial results reported in the deliverable **D4.2** (cf. section 4.2.4.2 in **D4.2**), the location of the stanchion node D0 was moved outside the depot, approximately 20 m from the previous location as depicted in the figure. This was done because of the conclusions presented in D4.2 (cf. section 4.2.9 in **D4.2**). This setup has been used for the final demo as well.

Figure 4-6 Overview of the test track and AP positions along the track

↓
New D0 position
(out of the depot boundary)

Two mmWave station nodes were mounted on tripods at a height of approx. 3 m and positioned alongside the track at the locations **D0** and **D2**. Figure 4-7 and Figure 4-8 show the mmWave trackside nodes at their respective locations. Both mmWave station nodes are powered using intermediate PoE-capable switches over the Ethernet connection due to the long cable connection (> 100 m). The **D0** node is connected directly to the landside server located in the control room due to its relative proximity to the server room. On the other hand, the **D2** connection was not directly routed to the server room, but it was connected to the switch located at the **D3** location and then via

fiber cable to the server placed in the control room. Hence, both **D2** and **D3** nodes share the same fiber connection to the server but have different VLANs.

A dedicated sub-urban train, shown in Figure 4-9, is used for mobility testing. Two mmWave nodes were mounted on the train at the front and rear side, labeled as **T1** and **T2**, respectively. As shown in the figure, the nodes were mounted outside the windows of the front and back side of the train using suction cups. The distance between them was approx. 35 m. Both train nodes were PoE-powered and connected to the on-board mobility server via switch using separate 1 Gbps Ethernet connections. Furthermore, a GPS receiver was used to track the location of the train for a coherent link analysis with the GPS antenna being mounted next to node T2.

Figure 4-7 Overview of the mmWave station node at position D0: a) mmWave node D0, b) View towards D1, c) View towards the end of the track.

Figure 4-8 Overview of the mmWave station node at position D2: a) mmWave node D1, b) View towards D1, c) View towards D3

Figure 4-9 Overview of the mmWave train nodes mounted at the front (T2) and back (T1) of the train

Measurement results - Static

First, a static mmWave link testing was performed in the parked position close to **D0**. The result is shown in Figure 4-10. The throughput of the mmWave link was measured by running an iperf3 TCP/IP test between a notebook connected to the switch to which both mmWave train nodes were connected and the landside server. The test lasted for 60 seconds and showed net data rates of 941 ± 21 Mbps for **T1-D0** and 892 ± 19 Mbps for **T2-D0**. The latency of the unloaded mmWave link was also measured, by performing ping test of a 60 seconds duration in the same setup. The results, shown in the same figure, returned a round-trip time latency of 1.4 ± 0.4 ms for **T1-D0** and 1.4 ± 0.1 ms for **T2-D0**.

Figure 4-10 Throughput and latency measurements in static conditions, May 2023

Measurement results - Mobility

The results of the mobility test are presented in Figure 4-11, with several panels being shown. The train started from a point between **D0** and **D1** and was moving towards **D2** and further. The first (top) panel shows the overall throughput in Mbps between the on-board laptop generating iperf3 TCP/IP traffic and the landside server. The second and the third panel show the distance and angle between the train node **T2**, where GPS antenna is located, to the track nodes **D0 (S1)** and **D2 (S2)**. The panels 4 and 5 show the connectivity status of **T1** and **T2** to both station nodes, respectively. The panels 6 and 7 depict the signal quality of **T1** and **T2**, respectively, when connected to either **D0** or **D2**. The last two panels plot the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) for the train nodes **T1** and **T2**. From the graphs one can see that at first both **T1** and **T2** are connected to **D0** since the train is close to it and a stable high throughput is measured. As the train moves away from **D0** towards **D2** (the distance to **D0** increases and to **D2** decreases), first the connection **T1-D0** (i.e. **S1**) is lost, and after some time also **T2-D0**. However, the link is still maintained with a high throughput. Also, it can be noted that during the duration of the **T2-D0** connection, the connection between **T1** and **D2** (i.e. **S2**) is established. Later, after losing connection with **D0**, **T2** gets connected to **D2**. One can observe that during that time the mmWave link is still active, but the transmission speed is varying. This can also be concluded on the basis of signal quality.

Figure 4-11 Performance of the mmWave link only testing under mobility in the TRAINOSE field trial May 2023

4.2.2.3 Mobility Management

The mobility management framework is in charge of maintaining the established connections between the applications and services running on the train, to the operations room (e.g. camera stream, 5G cell backhaul connection, connection to the MCPTT servers) as the train moves and the associations change from the train to the trackside (see Figure 4-12). The change in the associations can take place within a single technology (e.g. switching from the front mmWave node (T1) to the back (T2) seamlessly), or across the different technologies (mmWave to Sub-6 GHz). To this aim, the mobility management acts at two different points: 1) on the train, for selecting which link is used, 2) all traffic arriving to the operations room from the trackside points, for selecting which stanchion will be used for sending traffic back to the train. The two points need to run independently, with information that they collect from their side of the network (train or trackside) and without any communication channel being established among them.

To achieve this, two programmable software switches were used, one on the train, and one in the operations room. The train switch bridged four different interfaces, two coming from the mmWave nodes, one from the Sub-6 GHz node, and one from the application server that is running on the train and is the entrypoint for all the traffic pushed over the network. The trackside switch was bridging five interfaces, four coming from the stanchions, and one from the traffic server located in the operations room. This is the exit point for all the traffic reaching the operation room from the train. Both switches are programmable through the P4 language, and can be configured during their operation by using the switch’s API to establish a specific flow. The selection of which flow shall be active, and hence which link will be used to communicate with the trackside/train is running independently on each switch, based on their perception of the network from their side.

The mobility management server located on the train is using SNMP in order to retrieve statistics from the communication devices on the train. The statistics regard their reported received signal strength indicators (RSSI), the link quality metrics, and current association. These metrics were selected as they exist on both technologies (mmWave and Sub-6 GHz). For the Sub-6 GHz, the respective SNMP agent was developed using the snmpd framework, in order to serve statistics using the same API to the switch. Based on this information, as well as information from a GPS device on the train, a controller on the switch is able to conclude on which link is more beneficial to use for communicating with the trackside. This functionality is used for egress traffic on the train. For ingress traffic, all packets are forwarded to the application server on the train.

Figure 4-12 Mobility Management Network architecture

A similar process takes place on the mobility management server and switch in the operations room. SNMP is used to query the stanchions about their associations, RSSI and link qualities. If there is a change in the association (e.g. the Sub-6 GHz node is connected as it is within the stanchion coverage area), the link leading to the stanchion becomes a candidate for selecting to forward egress traffic. The selection is based on the last link that traffic was received from, as this is the one that is currently selected from the train side. For ingress traffic, all packets are forwarded to the server located in the operations room.

Monitoring Dashboard

A monitoring dashboard was developed in order to retrieve the status of the track-to-train network, as well as depict the stream from the CCTV camera on-board (see Figure 4-13). The following information was depicted in real time during the different tests:

- The camera stream, using an RTSP to webRTC server installed on the application server of the train.
- The position of the train on an interactive map configuration. The location of the train was obtained using a GPS device mounted on board.
- The relative position of the train with respect to each of the stanchions. The actual distance in meters was depicted.
- The current selection of technology for communicating with the trackside (Sub-6 GHz or mmWave).
- The reported RSSI values from all the different technologies, as received from the mobility management controller on-board (see Figure 4-14).
- The current throughput obtained over the setup, measured with iperf3 (see Figure 4-14).
- The current throughput over the 5G cell (OAI) backhauled over the network, as reported from the UE device on the train (laptop with Quectel RM-500Q modem).

Figure 4-13 Monitoring dashboard (camera stream, train position and connected technology)

Figure 4-14 Monitoring dashboard (RSSI values, connectivity and UR throughput)

Figure 4-15 Area of interest and collected measurements within it

Figure 4-16 Indicative measurements from different points of interest: On the left side, D0 is only seen through the front mmWave unit (T1), and achieves throughput of 928Mbps. On the right, train is serviced only through Sub-6 GHz by D3, achieving throughput of 336Mbps

The next tables present **UC #1.1** experiment description for the different services.

Table 4-2 Experiment 1 (UTH mobility management)

Description	
ExperimentType	Track-to-train session preservation as the train devices associate with across different stanchions
Automated	Yes, mobility management was configured as services running in the background of the switches and acts upon reception of traffic

TestCases	REDv2 REDv3
UEs	Three On-board UEs associating with the stanchions (mmWave T1 and T2, and Sub-6 GHz on-board node)
Network Slice	N/A
Network Services	Mobility management service: session preservation across different handovers
Network Scenario	Saturated link for either the Uplink (train to operations room) or the Downlink (operations room to train) Intratechnology handover: change in the onboard used mmWave device (T1 front, T2 back) Inter-technology handover: change in the technology of the associated stanchion (mmWave to Sub-6 GHz and vice versa)
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	Iperf3 was used to saturate the links, in either TCP or UDP configuration
Performance targets & SLAs	Latency, Uplink and Downlink capacity between train and operations room. U-CA-1101 -Total capacity offered to a single train / wagon is about 1 Gbps. U-PE-1103 -KPI: latency min. between UE and service end-points 20 ms. F-CA-1104 : Antenna operation at high frequency bands delivering the required capacity U-PE-1102 Mobility. F-CA-1104 Transport Network Capacity >1Gbps
Experiment Parameters	1. Train car starts moving, gets into coverage of a subsequent track-side unit. 2. P4 controllers are notified of the change and establish the respective flows in the programmable switches. 3.Handovers shall not impact applications running on-board
Edges	Edge server deployed in the operations room, acting as a traffic sink
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 4-3 Experiment 2 (camera streaming)

Description	
ExperimentType	Track real-time monitoring with on board camera streaming over the track-to-train backhaul
Automated	Yes, as soon as the camera is powered on, it is able to stream data. Data received from the camera (RTSP) is converted to a Web-RTC stream in the on-board server, so as it can be transmitted to the monitoring dashboard
TestCases	RENv01
UEs	N/A
Network Slice	N/A
Network Services	Camera streaming is preserved across the different handovers managed through the mobility management function

Network Scenario	Stream is requested from the monitoring dashboard, displayed in the operations room
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	Monitoring dashboard displaying the camera stream in the Operations Room
Performance targets & SLAs	Latency between camera and Control center 100ms High Video Quality of CCTV session U-PE-1103: E2ELatency: for this service type -Not critical F-CA-1104: Air Interface –Access/Transport Network Capacity (>150Mbps) F-PE-1105: Air Interface Characteristics
Experiment Parameters	Track-to-train Connectivity as in the mobility management experiment
Edges	Operation Room monitoring dashboard, displaying the camera stream
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 4-4 Experiment 3 (eMBB for passengers))

Description	
ExperimentType	The test validates the onboard 5G network deployment in an operational environment and evaluates its performance for video, live-streaming content, under various mobility conditions
Automated	The OAI RAN needs to be started at a point where the connection to the Operations Room is active (within the area of interest). This is to associate with the 5G Core Network that is located within the Operation Room premises.
TestCases	REPV01, REPV02
UEs	Laptop with Quectel RM-500Q-GL modem, Google Pixel 6 Smartphone
Network Slice	N/A
Network Services	5G Network service offered on-board
Network Scenario	The test procedure is repeated in several positions within the short range of the access nodes, corresponding to the train wagon dimensions. Other/ furthermeasurements shall not be taken into consideration. The test procedure is repeated for various traffic conditions of the nodes. Imposed traffic (from iperf server) may vary from no traffic (0 Kbps) to fully loaded conditions (depending on access node max.configuration). Measurements are collected for several iterations.
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	Traffic generator on the phone/laptop exchanging traffic with the Core Network located at the Operations Room, Video stream depiction on the phone
Performance targets & SLAs	U-PE-1102: Mobility

	<p>U-PE-1103: E2ELatency: for this service type -Not critical: <150ms</p> <p>F-CA-1104: Air Interface -Access/Transport Network Capacity</p> <p>F-PE-1105: Air Interface Characteristics</p> <p>F-FU-1111: Multi-Tenancy</p> <p>F-FU-1112: Slicing (on the 5G network)</p> <p>S-FU-1114: Mobility –Handovers (HO) (i.e. HO between subsequent trackside nodes (access or transport network ones))</p> <p>Additional Performance KPIs: Jitter: <40 ms, Packet Loss: <1%, Guaranteed Data Rate: 5-10 Mbps</p>
Experiment Parameters	Track-to-train Connectivity as in the mobility management experiment, 5G network configuration using OAI and running a disaggregated RAN (CU/DU) on the train, and the Core Network at the Operations Room
Edges	Operations Room monitoring dashboard, 5G Core Network located at the operations room, Traffic sink application on the Core Network
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 4-5 Scenario Description (on board UTH)

Scenario Description Template – Field	
Radio access technology (RAT)	5G-NR
Standalone / Non-Standalone (if applicable)	Standalone
Cell Power	14dBm
Frequency band:	N78
Maximum bandwidth per component carrier	50MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30KHz
Cyclic Prefix	Normal
Massive MIMO	2x2 MIMO
Duplex mode	TDD
TDD uplink/downlink pattern	nrofDownlinkSlots = 7; nrofUplinkSlots = 2;
User location and speed	0 km/h and 30km/h
Background traffic	None/ variable
Computational resources available	5G

4.2.1 Test Cases and KPIs tables (UTH)

For the first set of experiments, the integrated multi-technology backhaul (mmWave and Sub-6 GHz) for the train connections under mobility was tested. In this context, the mobility management framework was tested in terms of session preservation and any potential overhead that it places to the communication between the train and the operations room.

The system was tested under mobility mainly, while static tests revealed the maximum throughput available per technology/stanchion.

Figure 4-17 mmWave stanchions and onboard network under mobility (no Sub-6 GHz access). Max. throughput reported is 942 Mbps. Access to the mmWave stanchion seamlessly changes between the two onboard units T1 and T2

Single technology sub-6GHz testing under mobility

Figure 4-18 Sub-6 GHz stanchions and onboard network under mobility (no mmWave access). Reported RSSI values from all the technologies (mmWave is not active, hence RSSI is reported as -120 dBm)

Figure 4-19 Throughput calculation under mobility for 2 stanchions (D1 and D3). Maximum throughput for the Sub-6 GHz network under mobility is reported as 405Mbps

Another objective of the experiment execution is to evaluate the effectiveness of the mobility management framework. The mobility management framework needs to cope with handovers either in the same technology (change in the association of the onboard mmWave unit **T1/T2**), as well as changes across different technologies (handover between different stanchions). The mobility management framework is programming dynamically the flows in the P4 software switches either on the train, or the operation room, so as traffic entering/exiting the track-to-train network is always depicted in the same manner at the two endpoints. To this aim, the flows are set to mangle packet headers (MAC and IP layer) as they go through the switch, and the output port for the ingress/egress traffic is determined by each flow.

Figure 4-20 Mobility management for the two different types of handovers. RSSI values are also depicted (one of the parameters affecting the decision for handover). During the association with D0, three handovers occur for accessing D0 between the front (T1) or the back (T2) onboard mmWave units. Two cross technology handovers (D0 to D1 and D1 to D2) are depicted. Iperf sessions are preserved across the different handovers

Throughput test under mobility

Figure 4-21 Experiment and throughput for all the stanchions. Handovers take place in different areas based on the current location (obtained through GPS) and reported RSSI per technology. The iperf session is preserved across all the different handovers

Table 4-6 Experiment eMBB to passengers static and under mobility

Field	Description
Test Case ID	REDv02, REDv03
Facility, Site	5G-VINNI, TRA site
Description	This test case demonstrated the provisioning of eMBB to train passengers through the provisioning of an on-board OAI-based disaggregated cell, connected over the backhaul to the operations room where the OAI-Core Network was instantiated.
Executed by	Partner: UTH, IHP, UoP, TRA
Purpose	On board Network deployment and track-to train connectivity testing, static and under mobility
Scenario	REDv02, REDv03
Slice Configuration	No slice configuration was performed
Components involved	Onboard Ethernet Switch. Onboard wired network. On board server. Onboard mmWave and Sub-6 GHz nodes D0-D3 stanchions (mmWave and Sub-6 GHz nodes)
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Throughput and latency (RTT) measurements, packet losses under mobility
Tools involved	iperf3, ping
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	<p>static testing: mmWave track-to-train connectivity: Throughput~940 Mbps, RTT~1,3 ms Sub-6 GHz track-to train connectivity: Throughput= ~450 Mbps, RTT~2.1 ms</p> <p>Mobility Testing: mmWave track-to-train connectivity: Throughput around 900-950 Mbps during LoS with notable during handover (lasting for less than 500ms) Sub-6 GHz track-to train connectivity: Throughput maximum 150-380 Mbps depending on the distance Cross-technology handover: Instantaneous losses (lasting less than 500 ms) for packets currently in transit to the network</p>

Target metric/KPI verification (pass/fail) and	Throughput KPI passed for the mmWave nodes, Sub-6 GHz nodes provided significantly enhanced throughput (x7 times higher compared to previous tests), sufficient for the hosted applications to be served on top. RTT passed but without the backhaul connection to the UoP cloud Mobility Management working seamlessly across different technologies, connections on top are preserved.
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For the second set of experiments, the real-time streaming was tested under mobility. The camera mounted on the train was able to only serve an RTSP stream, which cannot be depicted directly to the browser depicting the monitoring framework. To this aim, the server on the train was used to transcode the video to a browser compatible WebRTC stream. The monitoring framework is subsequently querying the train server to get and depict the stream. As the mobility management framework was handling the underlying network handovers, the stream was able to be preserved across the changes in association.

Table 4-7 Experiment camera streaming under mobility

Field	Description
Test Case ID	RENv01
Facility, Site	5G-VINNI, TRA site
Description	This test case demonstrated the provisioning of real-time video streaming to the operations room through the integrated multi-technology backhaul
Executed by	Partner: UTH, IHP, UoP, TRA
Purpose	Video streaming from the train to the operations room without interruptions
Scenario	RENv01
Slice Configuration	No slice configuration was performed
Components involved	Onboard Ethernet Switch. Onboard wired network. On board server for transcoding video to a compatible format that can be depicted in the operations room server (RTSP to WebRTC). Onboard mmWave and Sub-6 GHz nodes D0-D3 stanchions (mmWave and Sub-6 GHz nodes) Application server in the control room for depicting the video stream from the train. On-board camera streaming a 2K video stream (2048 x 1080).
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Application throughput
Tools involved	RTSP to WebRTC transcoder, WebRTC video depiction plugin
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	2K Video was depicted in real-time with low latency (<20ms from the camera to the application server in the Operations Room), seamlessly across handovers.
Target metric/KPI verification (pass/fail) and	Seamless provisioning with no interruption time achieved, latency expected results achieved, total capacity of per access cell achieved.

For the third case of experiments, a 5G cell was operating on the train, based on the OAI platform, with the core network being deployed in the Operations Room. All the cellular traffic exchanged within the train went over the backhaul to reach the gateway. Iperf was used to measure the throughput delivered to a UE on board. As the mobility management is handling all the changes in the underlying network, the overlay 5G network was unaware of the changes in association between the different stanchions, and reported a maximum throughput performance of 109 Mbps.

5G-UE throughput performance under mobility

Figure 4-22 5G-UE throughput, with the 5G network being backhauled over the track-to-train network, under mobility

Table 4-8 Experiment on board network connectivity under mobility

Field	Description
Test Case ID	REPV02, REPV03
Facility, Site	5G-VINNI, TRA site
Description	This test case demonstrated the connectivity within the onboard network and the connectivity between the onboard (standalone) network to the 5G-VINNI facility (control room) while the multi-technology (Sub-6 GHz and mmWave) backhaul network is operational.
Executed by	Partner: UTH, IHP, UoP, COSM, TRA
Purpose	On board eMBB network provisioning without interruptions across handovers to different stanchions.
Scenario	REPV02, REPV03
Slice Configuration	No slice configuration was performed
Components involved	Onboard Ethernet Switch. Onboard 5G-NR disaggregated cell on a server, equipped with SDR (USRP B210). Onboard wired network. On board server. Onboard mmWave and Sub-6 GHz nodes D0-D3 stanchions (mmWave and Sub-6 GHz nodes) 5G Core Network VM in the control room. 5G UEs (Laptop with Quectel RM500Q-GL modem and Google Pixel 6 phone) for connecting to the network.
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Throughput and latency (RTT) measurements for the 5G-NR network
Tools involved	iperf3, ping
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	static testing: 5G-NR throughput test: peaking at 109Mbps for SISO configuration, for 2x2 MIMO up to 230Mbps were observed, RTT=~ 14ms Mobility Testing: 5G-NR throughput test: variations between 50-109Mbps, RTT depending on the technology backhaul (mmWave backhaul RTT=~ 14ms, Sub-6 GHz RTT=~ 14 – 25 ms)
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	Seamless provisioning with no interruption time achieved, latency expected results achieved, total capacity of per access cell achieved.

4.2.2 Conclusions – Lessons learned

All the tests in this UC were successfully conducted and meaningful results were collected. The operation of the mobility management service was validated successfully, as it was able to preserve the connections across the same/cross-technology networks. The mobility management design

allows it to run independently on the train or the operations room, without any signaling between the two entities; by exploiting the information and view of the network that both entities have, they conclude on the flow establishment and forward traffic to the respective interfaces independently. This feature enables the easy scaling of the function to several switches (instead of two that were used) at the different endpoints of the network (e.g. different operation rooms for the rail operators in different areas). Moreover, the mobility management function is agnostic to the underlying technologies; this feature renders it a feasible solution for cross-border communication setup (e.g. in a 5G corridor case), where multiple operators and stakeholders with different interests are involved.

In terms of the achieved throughput performance for the case of mmWave units, they have been able to transmit close to 1 Gbps of traffic, even under mobility. Their physical rate in most cases was higher (> 2 Gbps), however they were restricted by their Ethernet interface which can only send/receive 1 Gbps of traffic. For the case of Sub-6 GHz access, static experiments were able to achieve higher throughput. Even with the directional antennas that the final tests were conducted, the throughput was not able to surpass the 0.5 Gbps, due to the wireless module configuration. With newer technology wireless cards, effective throughput can surpass 1 Gbps, nevertheless they proved to be very unstable during the tests. Nevertheless, the Sub-6 GHz units demonstrated very high coverage (close to 1 km outside the target area of coverage) without LoS. This feature would render them a fit solution for the cases where the terrain only provides nLoS links.

4.2.3 Vertical business KPI validation (Kontron)

The **KCC** MC Solution based on MCx / FRMCS was deployed at the **TRA** Depot of the Patras facility as a second deployment, in an additional 5G-VICTORI cluster after the trial in Berlin with **FhG** was successfully completed. As such, the text here follows a similar structure to what is found in sections [Rail Telephony and Sensor Data \(Kontron\)](#) and [Vertical business KPI validation](#). Nonetheless, there are specific details and complexities of this deployment that are quite interesting and specific to the selected radio access technologies, and thus warrant additional analysis as to their viability for deployment to local and national railway operators.

The Service Layer of FRMCS, as the future of railway communications, can be and in effect is agnostic to the underlying wireless transport technologies used to have wireless communication to the user equipment. QoS can therefore be implemented using 5G SA, or using other complementary radio access technologies like the solutions presented here and based on mmWave and Sub-6 GHz. Connectivity to the onboard MC devices was achieved using both Wi-Fi and an onboard 5G-SA deployment.

The mmWave and Sub-6 GHz solutions provided by **UoP** exceeded most bandwidth expectations during field tests and trials. It is implied that 5G SA is the chosen technology for FRMCS deployments and work continues in that direction with the goal to start deployment of nationwide networks in late 2026. Trials are currently ongoing. The importance of 5G SA for the railway industry and for FRMCS cannot be overstated. That said, technologies such as mmWave and Sub-6 GHz can also be considered to be suitable for deployment of MC Applications for live customers including local and national rail operators where 5G is not considered to be a viable option due to cost, ease and efficiency of deployment, and other factors.

Particularly important for these alternative radio access technologies is the following:

- additional QoS validation given the constructs available for the specific technologies,
- congestion control and traffic isolation in shared networks,
- extended mobility in the home network, and
- seamless roaming between networks – including all access technologies deployed.

Roaming between disparate access technologies must enable access to MC components deployed in the home network as well as the ability to roam into foreign MC networks. MC communications also require a level of connectivity such that ongoing private and group communications can be maintained across transitions between core and access networks, and this with minimal latency and / or gaps in voice and data communications while transitioning. Emergency calls and other emergency services must be delivered reliably to all MC devices roaming in the various access networks. This is achieved using multiple factors of reliability.

- Geo-redundant core networks.
- Resilient (disparate) access networks using deployment schemes where onboard devices can always communicate with 2 or more radio access nodes.
- Access to multiple access networks – 5G SA and Wi-Fi for example.
- Multipath technologies for reliable delivery of content.
- Physical availability (redundancy) of multiple MC devices onboard.
- Fallback paths for communications including both devices and access networks.

Based on the lessons learned from 5G-VICTORI, **KCC** continues with additional EU-related research projects including 5G-RACOM and EERJU R2DATO. This comes in the form of joint and future collaboration / exploitation with railway infrastructure managers like SNCF, DB and other partners. In parallel, **KCC** continues to prepare for deployments with its own customers and with the target of deploying FRMCS based on MC 5G SA Networks. Specifications work still continues for FRMCS and we use the knowledge gained from 5G-VICTORI and other trials to influence those specifications. All-in-all, 5G-VICTORI has been a valuable research program for **KCC** and its partners.

4.3 UC #2 Factories of the future

UC #2 concerns the deployments of a variety of vertical specific services over the same private 5G network. The services are mainly smart factory related but due to the peculiarities of the **ADMIE** facilities (high voltage areas with sensitive data that require security) combined with the variety of terrains in the specific facilities make these verticals very demanding with respect to network deployment.

The facility interconnects two **ADMIE** sites. Data from various legacy sources are combined through the 5G network for Preventive maintenance and Monitoring of critical infrastructures:

- Real-time monitoring of HV power cable. Measurements of active power (MW), reactive power (MVar) and current (A) from the primary and secondary windings of the transformer at each site are collected and compared in real time. The monitoring of the two buses enhances the estimation of the status of the system connected via the power cable in the steady state – and the quasi-steady state when the latency difference of the measurements is maintained below a specific threshold.
- Sensor data collection. This service uses a large number of measurements originating from different types of sensors for the monitoring of the health of the actual HV power cable. The submarine cable is impregnated with a low-viscosity insulation fluid (oil) in order to increase its operating dielectric stress, working temperature and current carrying capacity. Oil pressure, oil temperature and other relevant measurements are continuously collected and processed in order to estimate the health of the cable. A rich dashboard is created with the use of UiTOP (**ICOM**) which is also capable of storing and analysing vast amounts of data. For privacy reasons, measurements never leave **ADMIE** premises and the service is accessible only inside the site (geo-fencing).

- Facility CCTV/robot monitoring. Surveillance with 5G enabled robot that can reach out to high voltage areas in the facility. 5G enabled robot and CCTV camera can transmit high quality video stream outside the **ADMIE** site, where intrusion detection algorithms run.

4.3.1 Field trial description

The novelties that are related to the final field trials in Patras, concern both the private 5G network deployment and the services that were executed simultaneously over distinct end-to-end slices for **ADMIE**. Specifically, the deployment of private 5G network for services isolation was successfully performed, at **ADMIE** with a 5G deployment that combined multi UPF and MEC solutions in order to satisfy the low latency requirements of the **ADMIE** services (synchronisation, etc.), as well as data isolation for out of premises (geo-fencing) service isolation. To that respect 5G Core functions reside on the operators' side so that authorisation, etc., is performed there, while the UPF resides on site (facility) and only authorised personnel may participate on location-based slices. Furthermore, we deployed novel applications and services with CCTV image recognition and robotic mobile monitoring for the first time in a real HV environment to the best of our knowledge.

Figure 4-23 a) 5G network deployed at ADMIE facility for Patras trials, b) robotic camera for the high voltage environment with live streaming over 5G, c) various interconnected sensors at the high voltage facility

To evaluate the various services that are required for the specific UC and achieve the expected KPIs, **UC #2** trial was performed in three groups of test cases, which were envisaged depending on the vertical service requirements. It is noted that all experiments that were executed during the Patras field trials have been tested and reported in deliverables **D3.6** [14] and **D4.2** [2].

As mentioned already, the transport network deployed for the specific UC was specifically built to interconnect the two facilities (**ICOM**). The anticipated performance metrics of the mmWave link were put under test, and the resulted throughput measurements are depicted in Figure 4-24.

Figure 4-24 Full duplex throughput of ICOM's mmWave link

To showcase the advantages of the proposed 5G-VICTORI architecture, two identical gNodeBs were deployed at Patras5G cloud facility (UoP- emulating the Central Offices of ADMIE) and at the ADMIE Rion facility (facility environment). The former is fed with CPE connected emulated sensors and is being used for showcasing and measurement purposes while the latter is being fed with data from the sensors in the facility (see D3.6 and D4.2).

To demonstrate the simultaneous use of the private network features we have used the part of the physical facility sensors (see D4.2) and virtual devices though dockerized Modbus TCP simulators instantiated in 5G enabled Raspberry devices (Rpi4). Figure 4-23 a) presents the actual setup inside the control room, at ADMIE facilities. In the legacy setup, physical sensors are hardwired to an electrical panel and provide their analogue and digital measurements on the front panel's dashboard. Physical sensors provide a great range of binary and scalar signals which can be divided into time-critical and maintenance related information. For the purposes of the trial, the panel has been equipped with Modbus TCP gateways which provide IP connectivity to the sensors. Finally, the Modbus TCP gateways use a 5G CPE to connect to the 5G Non-Private Network (NPN) network. The second ADMIE site is interconnected through fibre with Rio facility. The data are collected through emulated sensors and are synchronised at the MEC deployed at Rio site.

Furthermore, a robotic camera is interconnected via 5G NR at the ADMIE premises. Specifically, a mobile surveillance robot is deployed in order to provide a remote monitoring service for ADMIE. The robot is controlled remotely and is able to move around the facility, collect HD video feed and send it via 5G at the UoP data center in real-time, where the service is running. The video feed is accesible via web browser. In addition to the robot video feed, a CCTV UHD camera is installed and connected to the private network and is used for indoor intruder detection scenarios. The UHD video feed is also sent to the UoP data center for analysis and the processed video can be viewed via web browser, as in the robot scenario.

4.3.2 Experiment and scenario descriptions

Figure 4-25 illustrates the instantiation of three concurrent services, as envisaged in **UC #2** by the Greek cluster. All 5G core functions and **ADMIE** services have been deployed at the edge (a special 5G private network and standalone server deployed at the **ADMIE** facility). In this experiment slicing has been tested with two concurrent services, unveiling the benefits of the isolated services. The deployment of the 5G-VICTORI architecture at the **ADMIE** facility for the scope of **UC #2** is tested.

The 5G deployment options are used here (see deliverable **D4.2** [2]) for both gNodeBs. To benefit from the flexibility of the proposed architecture, the 5G core technology utilised here is based on the Open 5GS option deployed flexibly on containers.

Figure 4-25 High-level architecture of UC #2

For the execution of this specific experiment, we are showcasing the sensor data collection service over 5G, enhanced with the private networks (isolation) features and slicing enabled by the service-based architecture. Here all sensors are connected through the UPF2 (residing at the **ADMIE** facility/field). As depicted in Figure 4-25, the CCTV application is hosted on the **UoP** cloud (emulating **ADMIE** control room) to provide assets surveillance at a remotely located control room, possibly via internet. Real-time monitoring and Sensor data collection for latency and security reasons should not leave **ADMIE** premises, hence the data network that interconnects the sensors and the application terminates on site. All services use slices for the same 5G NPN.

Open5GS core functionality is deployed at the **UoP** cloud (Kubernetes cluster). However, as it is shown in Figure 4-26, two sets of UPF, SMF have been also instantiated at two Kubernetes clusters (MEC at **ADMIE** facility and cloud at the central office). The 2 gNodeBs provide geographically separated network connection and access to the two separate data networks (intidicated by TAC).

Sensors' monitoring service is then accessible only via the data network of UPF2, meaning that the service will be accessible only if the UE is inside the **ADMIE** premises and cannot be reached when connected through UPF1.

Figure 4-26 gNB based UPF selection flow

Surveillance services

CCTV monitoring of facilities over 5G provides live video feed when technical personnel is present or an event occurs, while not compromising other Industry 4.0 applications running in the background. For the demonstration of this service, two UHD CCTV cameras are installed inside the HV cable control room and a third robotic camera is used inside the Smart Factory facility. The purpose of the Facility CCTV Monitoring service on high-level is the following:

- Provide network slice customized for CCTV monitoring.
- Demonstrate that CCTV Streaming is conveyed over 5G with the required characteristics, regardless of other services and background traffic.

Table 4-9 Experiment 1 (UoP / ADMIE)

Description	
ExperimentType	Location-based service provisioning for privacy and low latency purposes (combined)
Automated	
TestCases	REComb01, REComb04
UEs	1 CPE serving as gateway for the industrial sensors.

	1 RPi4 + 5G HAT for sensors simulation 1 UE for accessing the services (only at ADMIE premises)
Network Slice	
Network Services	Geofencing (location-based service provisioning)
Network Scenario	Sensors' readings are transmitted through access (gNB2) and data network (UPF2) located at ADMIE premises and collected by applications hosted also at the edge. User with UE registered at gNB1 at UoP campus cannot access services. User with same UE registered but registered at gNB2 is able to access real-time and preventive maintenance applications
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	1.Real-time monitoring of submarine HV cable 2.Preventive maintenance
Performance targets & SLAs	S-FU-4302 - Mobile Edge Computing Capabilities S-FU-4303 - Multi-Tenancy S-FU-4304 - Slicing S-FU-4306 - On Demand deployment of network services FU-5301 (Air Interface – Access Network) S-FU-5308 (Management & Orchestration of Distributed Pools of Resources)
Experiment Parameters	1. 5G core 2. 3. 4.
Edges	MEC server (Autonomous Edge + gNB)
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 4-10 Experiment 2 (ADMIE / UoP)

	Description
ExperimentType	Real-time monitoring of ADMIE facilities and intruder detection with video streaming from both a 5G-enabled mobile surveillance robot and an indoor CCTV UHD camera connected in the private network
Automated	Semi-automated (the mobile surveillance robot needs some initial configuration in order to start streaming its video feed towards the service running at the UoP data center)
TestCases	EDCv01
UEs	One CCTV UHD camera, one mobile surveillance robot with 5G connectivity
Network Slice	CCTV slice
Network Services	Stable 5G connectivity with high bandwidth for high-quality video streaming
Network Scenario	High-quality video feeds from the robot and CCTV camera are sent to the smart monitoring service running at UoP cloud (e.g. ADMIE monitoring)

	offices) upon request from the user e.g. ADMIE personnel, sent via web server
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	Smart CCTV surveillance of ADMIE facilities over 5G
Performance targets & SLAs	<p>Successful implementation of smart CCTV services</p> <p>U-CA-5202 (High Traffic Density) - total capacity offered by a number of access network nodes</p> <p>S-FU-5303 (Multi-Tenancy) - Delivery of services with the requested QoS to multiple tenants over a single network deployment</p> <p>S-FU-5307 (On Demand deployment of network services) - Show on demand eMBB service deployment</p> <p>Additional Performance KPIs: CCTV datarate over network around 15 Mbps/camera, CCTV streaming latency 150 ms, CCTV maximum packet loss ratio 0.5%</p>
Experiment Parameters	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CCTV camera and mobile surveillance robot set up and running. 2. Smart CCTV surveillance service set up and running. 3. Streaming starts and video feeds are sent to the MEC server (autonomous edge + gNB) and from there toward the monitoring service running at UoP cloud, all done on top of the private 5G network in parallel with other services.
Edges	MEC server (Autonomous Edge + gNB)
Remote	Open5GS core at UoP cloud
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

4.3.3 Test Cases and KPIs tables

For real-time monitoring and preventive maintenance applications, latency and bandwidth related KPIs have been tested in the lab and in the field and have been reported in deliverable [D3.6](#). In these experiments, Patras5G monolithic deployment option#1 (SA 5G architecture based on Amarisoft solutions) was used, since the mmWave link between the two sites was not functional at that time.

For the first set of experiments, the focus is to demonstrate that by leveraging the proposed architecture of Figure 4-25 and the MEC capabilities of the solution, applications with different requirements can be supported simultaneously across a multi site deployment. Figure 4-27 illustrates a view from Argo, which is the Kubernetes continuous delivery tool used for the cloud and on-site deployment of services (**S-FU-4306** - On Demand deployment of network services). It is shown that SMF1, SMF2 and UPF1 run on the cloud, while UPF2 and application services run on a different cluster at the edge, thus fulfilling Slicing (**S-FU-4304**), MEC Capabilities (**S-FU-4302**), and Management & Orchestration of Distributed Pools of Resources (**S-FU-5308**) of the UC.

Location-based service provisioning is realized via the selection of different data network according to gNB that the UE is registered - **FU-5301** (Air Interface – Access Network). Figure 4-28 depicts UiTOP dashboard accessed from a UE connected to gNB2 at **ADMIE** premises. Since UE is connected to gNB2 it uses UPF2 and has access to UiTOP service running on Autonomous Edge. On the contrary, when the UE is registered to the NPN through gNB1 at the University campus, it uses UPF1 as its data network and it cannot access the specific service.

Figure 4-29 depicts measurements' collection latency from sensors located at both sites (Rio, Antirio) and latency difference for pairs of measurements as defined in deliverable D3.6 (EDHv03). It is shown that network latency and latency difference is similar with the lab trials (deployment option #1) as:

1. The dominant part of the latency is the delay added by the access network (same gNB is used).
2. There is no added delay from the mmWave connection as data network (UPF#2) resides at ADMIE premises.
3. There is no added delay from background traffic. CCTV monitoring services uses UPF#1 as its data network.

Figure 4-27 View of Open5GS Kubernetes deployment on the cloud where pods of SMF1, UPF1 (red) and SMF2 (green) are visible.

Figure 4-28 left) UiTOP dashboard accessed from a UE at ADMIE premises, right) Real-time monitoring app dashboard.

Figure 4-29 Live latency and latency different monitoring of measurements collection from Rio and Antirio sites.

Figure 4-30 ESC Field Testing – Single video stream from CCTV camera – Uplink bitrate usage of the channel

For the second case of experiments, the MEC server (autonomous edge + gNB) located in **ADMIE** facility in Rio was used in order to deploy a CCTV network slice over 5G while the other two Smart Factory services were running in the background. The CCTV video traffic originated from a static CCTV UHD camera and a HD camera installed inside a mobile surveillance robot. All the traffic exchanged within the HV power cable control room went over the mmWave backhaul to reach the cloud in UoP facilities. Firstly Wireshark and later a Grafana-based environment were used to measure and visualise the uplink datarate of both the CCTV camera and the 5G-enabled camera inside the mobile surveillance robot. The results prove the seamless CCTV service provisioning over 5G with full isolation from other running services and without introducing performance errors. In addition, it shows smart facility monitoring services, i.e., intruder detection, inside power utility facilities, which are a special case of industrial environment due to their harsh conditions e.g. high-voltage, electromagnetic interference, etc. Some of the results as well as images from the final demo can be found below:

Figure 4-31 ESC Field Testing – Single video stream from mobile surveillance robot – Uplink bitrate usage of the channel

Figure 4-32 ESC Field Testing – Capture from the CCTV camera and analyzed by the intruder detection service, accessed by UoP.

Figure 4-33 ESC Field Testing – 5G-enabled mobile surveillance robot in action.

Demo results are summarised in Table 4-11:

Table 4-11 CCTV services report from tests done at the Field Demo in Patras

Field	Description
Test Case ID	EDCv01
Facility, Site	5G-VINNI, ADMIE site
Description	This test case demonstrated the provisioning of a CCTV network slice for critical assets monitoring over a private 5G network, where the CCTV equipment are connected over the mmWave backhaul to the UoP cloud (e.g. ADMIE offices) where the Open5GS Core Network and facility CCTV monitoring service were instantiated.
Executed by	Partner: ADMIE, ICOM, UoP
Purpose	Smart CCTV surveillance services for industrial environments over 5G
Scenario	EDCv01
Slice Configuration	CCTV slice
Components involved	MEC server (Autonomous Edge + gNB) CCTV camera Mobile surveillance robot with 5G connectivity Network switch mmWave 10Gbit Link UoP DC
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	CCTV camera datarate, mobile surveillance robot camera datarate, CCTV streaming latency, CCTV maximum packet loss ratio
Tools involved	wireshark
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	Video streaming latency: Min = 0.9 s / avg = 2.32 s / max latency = 5.01 s (including application processing overhead) CCTV camera datarate: Min = 6.5 Mbps / avg = 9.33 Mbps / max bitrate usage = 12.78 Mbps 5G-enabled mobile surveillance robot camera datarate: Min = 0.4 Mbps / avg = 1.5 Mbps / max bitrate usage = 2.5 Mbps Aggregated datarate: Min = 7.3 Mbps / avg = 11.03 Mbps / max bitrate usage = 15 Mbps
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	Seamless provisioning with no interruption time achieved, throughput expected results achieved

All services were demonstrated simultaneously during the lab trial in Patras. Figure 4-34 depicts 4 UEs simultaneously connected to the network:

- UE_1 – connected to gNB_1 not able to access UiTOP (later connected to gNB_2 and able to access UiTOP).
- UE_2 – Rpi4 connected to gNB_2 and used a Modbus TCP simulator.
- UE_3 – Rpi4 on surveillance robot connected to gNB_2 and transmitting high quality video stream.
- UE_4 – Huawei 5G CPE connected to gNB_2 and used as gateway for the physical sensors.

Figure 4-34 Grafana dashboard showing 4 UEs connected to Open5GS during field trials in Patras

4.3.4 Conclusions – Lessons learned

During lab and field testing of **UC #2**, meaningful results were collected. Different deployment options were used and validated, each one presenting different features. With Deployment option #4 (Option_5GVINNI_4 Callbox for UC #2 – see deliverable **D4.2** [2]) where Amarisoft core was used, QoS for guaranteed minimum throughput was demonstrated in the lab. This means that services with higher priority can achieve stable uplink / downlink regardless of the background traffic.

Deployment option #3 (Option_5GVINNI_3 AW2S for **UC #2**) was validated in the lab and field and showcased the use of geographically separated UPF instances through the use of two kybernetes clusters. This deployment utilises Open5Gs as its core and leverages its containerized solution. Through this deployment, geo-fencing and end-to-end service slicing were demonstrated.

While all deployments were successfully tested in the lab and then replicated at **ADMIE** site, it must be noted that instantiating these services at the field was a demanding task. Equipment comprising sensors, gateways, gNBs, servers, switches and power delivery units should be adequately protected from excess humidity, heat, and workers of other **ADMIE** departments in the area. Moreover, backhauling was succeeded via a mmWave link with the **UoP** campus. The mmWave antennas were installed at the HV power pole (since there was no other spot with line of sight with the University). This decision introduced many difficulties to our endeavor. Installation and configuration of the antennas was performed through the collaboration of different teams (from **ADMIE**, **UoP** and **ICOM**) and of course after a scheduled power cut. These limitations reveal that 5G might present a much more flexible solution than the legacy hardwired ones, but still demands installation effort in such terrains.

4.3.5 Vertical business KPI validation

The main objective of **UC #2** was to validate that Smart Factory related services with different KPIs can be supported simultaneously by a private 5G deployment.

The first and most demanding service was the real-time monitoring of the HV submarine cable and more specifically the differential monitoring of the two power buses that it connects. The service demands low latency measurements collection and processing and low latency difference between the measurements collection by each site. The service presents 38.5 ms (mean) end to end latency. Latency difference between the two sites has a mean value of 0.75 ms and a max of 2.08 ms. This

means that the service can estimate adequately the steady state and dynamic state of the network (dynamic phenomena of 10^{-2} s).

As a critical infrastructure, the operator is responsible for ensuring privacy and control the level of access for each type of information. Location-based service provisioning, as described in the previous chapter ensures that i) critical information never leaves **ADMIE** premises ii) access to this information is prohibited to anyone outside the facilities. This feature can be also used to give location-based information to workers by filtering information according to the facilities they are visiting at that moment. In our case, except from the privacy, the local data network was used for i) local processing of measurements for latency reasons ii) local processing of no latency constrained measurements of each site and communication of only needed aggregated values to the cloud for data communication and storage savings purposes.

In the previous chapter, it was noted that there were many difficulties during the installation of a 5G NPN with edge processing capabilities at **ADMIE** facilities. Nevertheless, the ease of deployment cannot be compared with the legacy hardwired solution. Moreover, after the initial installation it is much easier to deploy a new service or change the network configuration according to new needs. So, the new 5G enabled deployment outperforms the previous one in terms of ease of deployment, flexibility, and maintenance.

Finally, the ability to stream high quality video stream from a moving surveillance robot to a remote location, improves the safety for first responders in the case of event, and the security of the overall facility.

4.4 UC #3 Content Delivery Network services

As the Media services are becoming increasingly available in transportation environments, a variety of media-related services can be offered and used to facilitate passengers' needs in various directions, especially infotainment and safety/security. The 5G-VICTORI Media UC in Patras (**UC #3**) targets both of these directions and proposes the use of 5G technologies in railway environments as the enabler to deliver uninterrupted high-quality CDN-aided infotainment services to railway passengers as well as surveillance and safety services at the railway premises, sufficiently supporting their high data rates and low latency requirements.

Infotainment services require high data rates to achieve fast multimedia caching on-board for sufficient content volume availability that will be able to cover the duration of the train trip until the next stop. To this end, a hierarchical multi-level vCDN streaming solution for railway is developed in the context of the Patras Cluster Media UC. The solution utilizes several levels of caches deployed centrally, at train stations and on board trains, which get synchronized using the high data rates of 5G-NR connectivity and therefore proactively storing large volumes of multimedia content onboard a train during its stop at the station.

On the other hand, surveillance and safety services require high data rates for high quality video streaming and low latency for smooth interchange of field-of-views. The Patras Cluster Media use case develops a remote surveillance application for high quality footage streaming during Field-of-View (FoV) stability and fast, lower quality footage streaming during FoV rotations, in order to achieve smooth transition and motion sickness avoidance.

4.4.1 Field trial description

The final deployment and evaluation stage of the different services of the Patras cluster Media UC took place at the **TRA** Depot of the Patras facility (on-site), using a **TRA** Train and based on the same network infrastructure deployment used by the Transportation UC. The main focus was given on the successful delivery of the Media services in the field and the verification of their operation, as well as on measuring selected KPIs from the previous lab testing phases. Specifically, for the CDN scenario emphasis was placed on the data shower test case and its relevant metrics, i.e. data shower

data rate, volume of content downloaded onboard during the train's stop at the station and trip duration covered by the downloaded content, as well as on the the general streaming experience of the passengers. For the surveillance scenario, both the 360° camera high quality streaming test case and the field-of-view rotation test case were the main focus of the field trials, evaluating the security footage receiver's overall experience and measuring relevant metrics, i.e. data rate required for high quality / low quality footage streaming.

For the deployment of components for both scenarios all the required field facilities were utilized, including **COSM** premises in Athens, **UoP**'s Cloud facility and the **TRAINOSE** Depot in Patras. Each of the involved field facilities hosted the respective hardware and software components required for providing the Media services.

4.4.2 Experiment and scenario descriptions

The CDN-aided infotainment services were demonstrated during the train's stop at the TRAINOSE Depot station in Patras city center, which was 5G-and MEC-enabled, communicating at the same time with the central CDN facilities at UoP cloud premises. In brief:

- The UoP's 5G-VINNI facility was utilized to host the necessary CDN VNFs (in its cloud domain), and it was extended with the UoP's 5G Autonomous Edge (i.e. a private, lightweight 5G SA) deployed at **TRA** premises.
- The CDN platform provided by **ICOM** was comprising 3 CDN stages implemented by 3 CDN application components: (1) the Central CDN Server serving as a point of connection to various sources/ TV/ VoD providers etc., (2) the Main CDN Server serving as the main caching point that receives content from the Central CDN server, and (3) the Edge CDN Server providing the last mile caching server that receives content from the Main CDN server. In this linear graph of the 3 CDN components, the most delay and data-rate critical interface -which determines the overall CDN service performance - is that between the edge CDN server and the Main CDN server. Connectivity to this interface is provided over over the UoP 5G Autonomous Edge.
- The 5G-VINNI facility was also interconnected with **COSM** premises in Athens (Maroussi Central OTE building), to obtain the media content (the two linear COSMOTE TV channels) from a niche content origin extending the commercial COSMOTE TV platform (at central COSM premises) especially for the purposes of the project. The COSMOTE niche content origin was based on HPE COTS HW and SW for Back-end/ Front-end, which hosted the necessary Harmonic Electra XOS OTT Encoders SW - Harmonic XOS-APPLIANCE ELECTRA XOS ATO APPLIANCE including the licenses for deploying XOS app on XOS server, XOS platform enabling RTMP, Push/Pull packaging, encoding for one HD + TV channels, and Device Management. Logically this part of the facility implemented the following necessary elements:
 - an Origin, which receives content from Encoder and forwards it to Central CDN Server
 - an OTT Encoder, which encodes the streams
 - the Headend equipment with interfaces tailored to **ICOM** CDN requirements, which constitutes the borderline of the niche deployment.

The Source-CDN interface specifications that were implemented are the following:

- Container type: Fragmented mp4 (fmp4) streaming media format.
- Pull-based communication between COSMOTE TV source and **ICOM** central CDN server.
- HLS manifest with 3 image qualities (3 renditions in ABR ladder) and one sound quality per channel.
- Chunks created based on **ICOM** CDN requirements.

- Unencrypted channels were used.
- Segmentation was performed at niche COSMOTE TV side. In this way, the requirement to co-locate **ICOM** central CDN server with COSMOTE TV origin is overcome, to better define slices at Patras facilities while having a realistic deployment of this UC.
- Specific delay was inserted to the linear content at CDN side to apply the data shower concept properly.

The Train Station Cache was deployed as a VNF at the MEC level on a server at the Train Station, and the Train Cache was deployed on a laptop on-board the train. The Train Station Cache and the Train Cache were able to communicate with each other through the gNodeB placed at the train station and a 5G-CPE on-board the train. Finally, an end-user (passenger) was watching the content through his personal laptop. The described setup of the field trials for the CDN scenario along with the different facilities of the deployment is illustrated in Figure 4-35.

Figure 4-35 The field trials setup for the CDN scenario

The installations at each field facility are showcased in Figure 4-36.

a) Patras 5G-VINNI Central facilities

b) COSMOTE -TV Niche Content Origin

a) Train station

b) 5G Core @ TRA

c) 5G RAN @ Train Station

d) On-board Train deployment & vCDN edge Cache

e) COSMOTE TV channel – Passenger view

Figure 4-36 All elements deployed for the UC#3 final demonstrations

The remote surveillance services were also demonstrated at the **TRA** Depot station in Patras, and specifically the field experiments took place at the railway security and control room, which received surveillance footage from equipment placed at the depot station. In particular, the 360° camera was set to monitor the train station and was connected through Ethernet to the camera server for streams processing and transmission, also deployed at the depot. The camera client was deployed in the security staff room, configuring a G connection between the camera server and the camera client a 5G-CPE and the gNodeB at the train station, using uplink network configuration. The described setup of the field trials for the CDN scenario along with the different facilities of the deployment is illustrated in Figure 4-37.

Figure 4-37 The field trials setup for the surveillance scenario

The installations at the field facility are showcased in Figure 4-38.

a) Surveillance camera deployment

b) 5G-CPE connected to Camera server

c) gNB @ TRAINOSE station

d) Camera server

e) Camera client

Figure 4-38 Deployed elements for Experiment 2 of UC #3

Table 4-12 Table 4 7 Experiment 1 – vCDN Services

Description	
ExperimentType	The experimentation for this testing cycle was performed on the field (field trials). The CDN-aided infotainment services were demonstrated during the train’s stop at the TRAINOSE Depot station in Patras city center, which was 5G-and MEC-enabled, interconnected with the central CDN facilities at UoP cloud premises.
Automated	Yes, the multi stage CDN application was configured to be deployed automatically through the orchestration layer and the data shower functionality also took place automatically when 5G connectivity was detected.
TestCases	MCDv04 and MCDv05 were executed, focusing on the data shower functionality and the content distribution to passengers onboard.
UEs	In this experiment a 5G CPE is used on board the train to connect to the gNB at the train station. The CPE model is Huawei CPE Pro 2.
Network Slice	An eMBB network slice was configured, providing high data rates to the application. Slice: Template sst 1/ sd 10, of eMBB type.
Network Services	N/A
Network Scenario	As defined in Table 4-14.
Exclusive Execution	No other application was executed simultaneously.
ReservationTime	The duration of the experiment was approximately 2 hours.
Application	CDN-aided data shower application. As the train moves towards the train stations and gets into coverage of the Station gNodeB. The CPE establishes a 5G connectivity to the gNB and the train cache (onboard, edge cache) connects to the train station (central) cache and start the data shower.
Performance targets & SLAs	High data rates and large volume of transferred data in a specific amount of time set as target KPIs in MCDv04 and MCDv05.
Experiment Parameters	As defined in Table 4-14.
Edges	Edge server deployed in the operations room.
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	3 - This is the third (field) testing cycle, after two lab testing phases.
Extra	N/A

Table 4-13 Experiment 2 – Surveillance Services

Description	
ExperimentType	The experimentation for this testing cycle was performed on the field (field trials). The remote surveillance services were demonstrated at the TRAINOSE Depot station in Patras with the use of a 360° 4K camera.
Automated	N/A
TestCases	MCSv02 and MCSv03 were executed, focusing on the evaluation of FoV stability phase and FoV change phase.
UEs	In this experiment a 5G CPE is connected to the 360° camera to transmit the uplink footage. The 5G CPE connects to the station gNB. The CPE model is Huawei CPE Pro 2.

Network Slice	An eMBB network slice with uplink network configuration was configured, providing high data rates to the security footage upstreaming. Slice: Template sst 1/ sd 10, of eMBB type.
Network Services	N/A
Network Scenario	As defined in Table 4-14.
Exclusive Execution	No other application was executed simultaneously.
ReservationTime	The duration of the experiment was approximately 2 hours.
Application	360° camera remote surveillance application. High quality footage streamed by the 360° camera during periods with stable FoV is provided to a remote operator. Lower quality footage with very low latency during FoV changes is provided to a remote operator.
Performance targets & SLAs	High data rates in the uplink direction set as target KPIs in MCSv02 and MCSv03.
Experiment Parameters	As defined in Table 4-14.
Edges	N/A
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	3 - This is the third (field) testing cycle, after two lab testing phases.
Extra	N/A

Table 4-14: Scenario Description (for both Experiments of this UC)

Scenario Description Template – Field trial	
Radio access technology (RAT)	5G NR
Standalone / Non-Standalone (if applicable)	SA
Cell Power	2X5Watt
Frequency band:	Band 78
Maximum bandwidth per component carrier	50MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	15Khz
Cyclic Prefix	normal
Massive MIMO	4x4
Duplex mode	TDD
TDD uplink/downlink pattern	DL:UL – 7:2
User location and speed	Location: 50m to cell edge, speed: ~20-50 Km given that the train run inside city area.
Background traffic	No
Computational resources available	Edge server available

4.4.3 Test Cases and KPIs tables

The tables below describe in detail each test case that was executed during the field trials for the two experiments, the results obtained from the measurements procedure and the evaluation of each test case outcome.

Table 4-15 Test Case MCDv04

Field	Description
Test Case ID	MCDv04
Facility, Site	5G-VINNI, TRA site
Description	The data shower functionality was examined and evaluated in order to verify that large amounts of live COSMOTE TV content are transferred to the onboard server in a very short time through 5G connectivity.
Executed by	Partner: COSM , ICOM , UoP , TRA
Purpose	Evaluation of the data shower data rate and the volume of content transferred onboard.
Scenario	MCDv04
Slice Configuration	eMBB slice configured as in Table 4-7.
Components involved	Central CDN server VM at UoP Cloud Train Station cache VNF at UoP MEC Server at the station Train Cache on local laptop Local 5G-CPE and gNodeB COSM TV content
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Data rate between MEC (Train Station) Cache & Train Cache Amount of content transferred onboard
Tools involved	Logging system of Train Cache.
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	Data rate between MEC (Train Station) Cache & Train Cache: ~100 Mbps average (depending on the position of the train in relation to the gNB) Amount of content transferred onboard: 900 MB in about 30sec
Target metric/KPI verification (pass/fail) and	Passed, as the data shower exploits the total of the available 5G data rates provided by the network and the content transferred onboard is the maximum possible with the provided data rates.

Figure 4-39 and Figure 4-40 show instances of the train arriving at the station and updating its CDN cache by downloading the required media content (i.e. data shower). The data showers correspond to the peaks of the graphs presented in the figures. The graphs show also the correlation between the real-time monitored downlink speed of the 5G radio system and the measured accumulative data that was downloaded. The difference in the duration, speed and total downloaded data on each occasion is because the second data shower had less content to update.

Figure 4-39 DL Data Rate during Data Shower

Figure 4-40 Cumulative downloaded content in MB during Data Shower

Table 4-16 Test Case MCDv05

Field	Description
Test Case ID	MCDv05
Facility, Site	5G-VINNI, TRA site
Description	This test case examined the smooth distribution of the COSMOTE TV content to train passengers through ICOM's CDN application running on laptops/smartphones and the uninterrupted streaming experience.
Executed by	Partner: COSM, ICOM, UoP, TRA
Purpose	Evaluation of the maximum possible streaming time for passengers according to the volume of content loaded onboard.
Scenario	MCDv05

Slice Configuration	eMBB slice configured as mentioned in Table 4-7.
Components involved	Train Cache on local laptop COSM TV content at Train Cache (onboard) Passenger UE (local laptop) ICOM CDN application on passenger UE
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Increase of viewing time bar on passenger UE according to the duration of the stop and the max datarate.
Tools involved	Verification through viewing of COSMOTE TV content duration increasement on passenger UE.
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	Viewing time bar on passenger UE was increased in accordance with the duration of the stop and decreased in accordance to the coverage gaps between data showers. In the demo deployment increase/decrease of viewing time of about 5 minutes was observed.
Target metric/KPI verification (pass/fail) and	Passed, as enough content was added to the passenger's viewing screen after the data shower in order to continue the uninterrupted streaming until the next stop.

Table 4-17 Test Cases MCSv02 & MCSv03

Field	Description
Test Case ID	MCSv02 & MCSv03
Facility, Site	5G-VINNI, TRA site
Description	The functionality of the surveillance application and its components is evaluated during FoV stability and FoV changes (rotation/zooming).
Executed by	Partner: COSM, ICOM, UoP, TRA
Purpose	Evaluation of the high quality streaming operation during FoV stability and lower quality low latency streaming operation during FoV changes.
Scenario	MCSv02 & MCSv03
Slice Configuration	eMBB slice configured with uplink network configuration as mentioned in Table 4-13, in order to facilitate the uplink nature of the data streams in this experiment.
Components involved	360° surveillance camera at train station Camera server PC with streams processing and optimization SW Camera client at security staff room with streams coordination and rendering SW Local 5G-CPE and gNodeB
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	High and lower quality streaming data rate FPS for high and lower quality streaming
Tools involved	Logging system of the surveillance application, ping.
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	High quality streaming data rate during FoV stability (with motion capturing): ≈12 Mbps. Lower quality streaming data rate during FoV changes (with motion capturing): ≈36 Mbps. 154 FPS on average during FoV stability. 444 FPS on average during FoV changes.
Target metric/KPI verification (pass/fail) and	Passed, as the network covered the data rate requirements both for high and for lower quality streaming.

Figure 4-41 and Figure 4-42 show two instances of the 360° camera being deployed for use. The timestamps show that for each case we had increased uplink speed while at the same time the aggregated traffic was steadily increased. The second experiment was longer in duration so more traffic was detected.

Figure 4-41 UL Data Rate during surveillance service operation

Figure 4-42 Cumulative UL Data during surveillance service operation

4.4.4 Conclusions – Lessons learned

In the third phase of testing performed in the field, the lab results of the previous two phases were validated, for both the vCDN and the Surveillance services. Considering the vCDN services, test cases **MCDv01** and **MCDv02** focusing on the deployment and connectivity verification were regarded as redundant in this testing phase, as the compute environment and network interfaces' setup has been the same as in the lab setup. **MCDv03** focusing on validating the synchronisation capability of vCDN application components was also regarded as redundant in this phase, as it was associated mainly to the application development and integration activities.

In this phase, emphasis was put in validating and evaluating performance over the field network deployment. To this end, the data shower mechanism from the train station cache to the train cache in the context of test case **MCDv04** was tested. In the field setup, the data rate with which the COSMOTE TV content was downloaded in the train cache was measured to 100 Mbps, depending on the relative distance between the train and the gNB. During the time that the train resided within the gNB coverage (3 minutes window, ~30 seconds downloading based on single channel content readiness), an average data volume of 900MB of content was downloaded at the train cache. As demonstrated (in the context of test case **MCDv05**), the content was smoothly distributed to the passenger UEs on board the train, over the required ~10Mbps connections. In overall, for the CDN

scenario, the integration of **ICOM**'s CDN with COSMOTE TV content was successfully tested in the railway vertical environment.

However, achieving the necessary performance in the field has not been a straight-forward task. In practice, the distance of gNBs from the railway tracks, the spatial characteristics of the operational environment, the terrain and the materials of the soundings, as well as the materials of the train can significantly impact radio coverage, thus service performance. Among the lessons' learned is that checking network quality and radio network parameters optimisation is necessary so that network coverage is optimised at the location where the train stops. At the same time, the placement of the CPE (providing 5G connectivity to the edge cache) need to be carefully planned (e.g. placing the CPE near a window in the middle of the train could have better performance than placing it at the front wagon). Last but not least, scalability studies in terms of number of channels, stopping times, duration of train trip between stops etc. will be needed once 5G networks become more crowded, in order to ensure that proper eMBB slices are configured per deployment case.

For the surveillance scenario two test cases were run and evaluated. Currently- latency-based configuration of slices is not possible at the available 5G Core networks. Thus, an UL-bandwidth optimised eMBB slice was configured in the field trials, in order to facilitate the uplink nature of the data streams in this scenario. The obtained results in the field validated the lab experimentation ones. In particular, for the test cases **MCSv02** and **MCSv03**, the camera was set to transmit the field-of-view to the camera client. It was observed that the high-quality stream of the camera requires an average bandwidth of ~12 Mbps to be transmitted. Differentiation in quality of streaming is possible during motion detection and FoV changes phases (e.g., lower quality streaming data rate is possible).

In overall, for the surveillance scenario, the high quality stream was successfully watched by the remote client and it was observed that even multiple cameras may be supported, network-wise. The data rates offered by the network cover this data rate requirement and it can be computed that even 8 simultaneous cameras can be supported.

4.4.5 Vertical business validation

From a business perspective 5G ecosystems is considered the prevailing market formulation to support 5G use cases. In this context, various stakeholders have started to envision a specific position in 5G ecosystems, targeting the realisation of specific use cases. However, the business roles of various stakeholders in 5G ecosystems need to be distributed and validated based on numerous factors as mentioned in [18]. To this end, 5G-PPP Phase III projects aimed at the business validation of use cases -in terms of identification of complexities, need for expertise, identification of interest of stakeholders, etc., through the short scale field deployments.

In this context, considering the CDN UC, from a vertical business validation perspective, CDN services are constantly attracting the interest of various stakeholders, primarily being content distribution companies, network operators, and lately road operators and public transportation operators. The 5G-VICTORI project-level planning brought together **ICOM** as "service provider", **COSM** as "content provider, CDN and also mobile network operator", **TRA** as "railway operator" as well as UoP as facility owner. This formulation of partner profiles and expertise was proven in practice through their smooth collaboration in the context of the vCDN use case. Partners brought in their expertise in their fields and cooperated effectively to perform the demonstration activities. The integration and demo activities validated the business role of each of the appropriately skilled partners and revealed (and validated) the necessity for separation of concerns, responsibilities and capabilities between service providers (CDN and content providers), network operators, vertical industries (in this case railways), aggregators (in this case the role was undertaken by up) in line with the layered 5G ecosystems vision. Practically, no conflicting interests or hugely overlapping capabilities or gaps in expertise -to be covered by additional stakeholders- were spotted. These are reflected also in the business modelling activities of the project, reported in deliverable **D5.4** [17].

Last but not least, the attractiveness of CDN services in public transportation vertical environment has been also evaluated through the social-dimension assessment in the context of Task 3.4 (Deliverable D3.7 [16]) as means to validate the business opportunities opened up via this UC.

Considering the surveillance services use case, from a vertical business validation perspective, surveillance services are increasingly required by stakeholders, vertical industries even mobile operators, operating highly distributed facilities. Stakeholders with interest or/and activities in this market have been service providers (surveillance service providers), verticals operating own infrastructure, and recently telecom operators mainly providing real time monitoring solutions. The 5G-VICTORI project-level planning brought together ICOM as “service provider”, COSM as “mobile network operator”, TRA as “vertical operating distributed facility” as well as UoP as facility owner. This formulation of partner profiles and expertise was also proven in practice through their smooth collaboration in the context of the surveillance use case. Although this use case can be provided in various environments by stakeholders having conflicting interests and overlapping capabilities (e.g. service providers or verticals operating own NPN, or network operators as identified in the demo activities) no gaps in expertise -to be covered by additional stakeholders- were spotted.

4.5 UC #4 Smart Energy Metering

This UC focuses on the development of a technology solution that can be used to monitor the whole railway system and identify optimal strategies ensuring cost-effective operation for the railway network.

Monitoring and operations optimization of the railway network is quite a challenging problem in railway environments due to the large number of parameters, variables, and constraints involved in the decision-making process. In many cases, decisions taken by the infrastructure manager to perform specific activities (i.e., maintenance) have a direct impact on train operators as they may lead to service disruptions. This is a common situation, especially in railway networks comprising double-track lines without redundancy, such as the Greek railway network shown in Figure 4-43, where maintenance has an impact not only on service availability and reliability but also on safety. In addition to this, decisions taken by railway operations to optimize the operation of their system (identify energy-aware driving profiles) may affect scheduling policies for the railway network.

Figure 4-43 The Hellenic Train Railway network

Towards this direction, the present UC relies on a platform that has been developed assisting infrastructure managers and operators to identify cost-effective maintenance plans that can not only increase operating speed and capacity but also improve the reliability of the railway system. The platform developed in the context of the EU project 5G-VICTORI provides a set of tools that can be used to monitor in real time:

- a) a variety of operational parameters of the rolling stock (i.e, train kinematic parameters, position, energy consumption, etc.), and
- b) the status of the railway track using cost-effective sensors.

Based on the collected measurements a set of optimal operational plans that can jointly optimize the payoff for the Infrastructure Managers and the Rail service providers are prescribed. To achieve this, the platform operates adopting a cloud-based microservices architecture allowing users to be actively involved in all stages of data analysis performed during track maintenance. This includes:

- data on-boarding offering the option to upload either offline data or connect measuring equipment acquiring data from the field,
- visualization of the collected measurements through simple re-configurable dashboards,
- analysis of past measurements using diagnostic analytics. The outcome of this analysis provides pointers to the exact locations where defects may exist,
- prediction of the status of the track over time, and
- recommendation of optimal maintenance plans, solving a set of Multi-Objective Optimization (MOO) problems using as input data from the previous stages.

The necessary intelligence is provided to the Intelligent Asset Management Systems IAMS platform through a set of Machine Learning (ML) models that have been purposely designed to: a) detect track anomalies, b) estimate the deterioration of the track over time and, c) recommend a set of candidate time periods where maintenance activities can be scheduled. To develop the relevant ML models, we rely on data collected from track monitoring equipment (i.e., accelerators, vibration sensors and industrial cameras) installed on a train operated by Hellenic Train. The data acquisition system that has been installed collects fully synchronised measurements from heterogeneous sensors with sampling frequencies exceeding 10 kHz/channel/sec. It is well known that track irregularities generate a certain level of vibration in moving trains influencing stability and safety of travellers. Most of these irregularities are determined through human inspection, while maintenance processes are carried out during regular/fixed reviews of the system. Currently, the measurements that can be used are classified in two main categories including:

- direct measurements aiming at identifying the exact track irregularity including its size and location, using laser scanning and video capture, and
- indirect measurements using accelerations at the axial box or the carriage body to reflect the status of the irregularity in the track.

The developed platform relies on the second approach as it provides a very cost efficient and effective approach in detecting track anomalies. Collection of qualitative data with high sampling rates offer significant benefits in the maintenance process as it enables not only accurate characterisation of irregularities that may appear in the tracks but also estimation of the way these irregularities evolve over time. However, a main challenge is related to the high capacity required to transmit the collected measurements from the train to trackside for further analysis. In 5G-VICTORI, this problem has been addressed through the 5G network providing the necessary mechanisms (capacity, traffic isolation, automation in service establishment) to support the required services.

4.5.1 Field trial description

To collect the measurements needed to perform the analysis, an experimental campaign has been conducted. To do so, a data management platform has been developed and deployed in an operational environment collecting fully synchronised measurements from a variety of sensors installed on-board.

The measuring system has been mounted in a Siemens Desiro (OSE class 46024 see Figure 4-44) that has been allocated by Hellenic Train in support of the experimentation activities. The main objective of the system is to capture the vibration generated by the wheel-rail interaction]. Combining vibration/acceleration measurements together with images from industrial cameras the system is able to detect the presence of track defects. In the following subsection, a brief overview of the data management system along with its implementation details is provided.

Figure 4-44. Siemens DESIRO 460 electric train (25KV) operated by Hellenic Train used to support the field trials

To support the experimentation activities of the use case project, a cloud-based Industrial Internet of Things (IIOT) system has been deployed enabling: data collection from a variety of sensing devices, visualisation of the collected measurements, and transmission of the measurements to the operations and control centre. The overall system comprises an onboard segment responsible to collect measurements from the installed sensors and a communication segment that creates secure connections between the on-board segment and the cloud-based IOT platform. The latter is responsible to store and visualise the collected measurements. For resilience purposes, the system also supports the option to redirect traffic to a local (on-board) database

Figure 4-45 provides the schematic diagram of the onboard data acquisition module. This module comprises the following segments:

Figure 4-45. Interfaces between the acquisition devices and the gateway

- The data acquisition segment that collects measurements from multiple devices. For this segment, the sampling rate, the type of measurements that are collected (i.e., current or voltage), the number of input channels and the synchronisation unit.
- The aggregation and packet assembly segment. This is responsible for combining measurements from different input devices, adding the corresponding timestamp, and assembling the JSON file in the appropriate format.
- Communication protocol segment (5G connectivity) that is responsible to establish secure connectivity with the data management system collecting the measurements
- The QoS assurance mechanism (segment 3) that guarantee of delivery of the transmitted messages.

In the first round of the experimentation activities the following devices have been installed:

- A general-purpose vibration Sensor
- 3-axis accelerometer
- Frame Grabber Camera
- Current sensors
- GPS device
- Custom x86 device hosting the on-board solution
- Power supply: UPS and power generation
- GPS system providing also the reference clock for the synchronisation of the individual subsystems.

The mounting position of the sensors is shown in Figure 4-46.

Figure 4-46 Hellenic Train Measurement Campaign: a) Siemens Desiro used in the experimentation b) Installation of vibration sensor (Monitran 1185C), c) Basler Line scan camera monitoring railway tracks with custom enclosure designed by Hellenic Train, d) 3-Axis accelerometer mounting position(PCB 356A02), e) current sensors mounting position.

4.5.2 Experiment and scenario descriptions

The next tables present **UC #4** experiment description for the different services.

Table 4-18 Experiment 1 (IIoT services for railway infrastructure managers and operators)

Description	
ExperimentType	The use case tests the performance of a complete system used to monitor the operation of the rolling stock, the condition of the railway infrastructure and the power consumption of system
Automated	Deployment of end-to-end slices providing connectivity for the sensing devices (energy metering, acceleration and vibration sensors, industrial cameras-frame grabbers)
TestCases	
UEs	RM-500Q-GL router, Teltonika 5G router RUTX50
Network Slice	uRLLC slice for IoT sensors, eMBB for industrial camera
Network Services	1 – Real time monitoring of the railway track using 3-axis accelerometers and vibration sensors 2- Real time monitoring of the railway track using high speed cameras monitoring the track condition 3 – Power consumption monitoring and correlation with kinematic parameters

Network Scenario	Transmission of real time data from the train to the ground in support of a) real time railway track anomaly detection , b) use of measurements to optimize the operation of the system through the identification of optimal operational plans (i.e., energy aware driving profiles and optimal maintenance plans)
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	Development of a cloud based Intelligent Asset management system supporting the operation of the railway system
Performance targets & SLAs	<p>U-PE-1103: E2ELatency: <150ms</p> <p>F-FU-1111: Multi-Tenancy</p> <p>F-FU-1112: Slicing (on the 5G network)</p> <p>S-FU-1114: Mobility –Handovers (HO) (i.e. HO between subsequent trackside nodes (access or transport network ones))</p> <p>Additional Performance KPIs: Jitter: <40 ms, Packet Loss: <1%, Guaranteed Data Rate: 5-10 Mbps</p>
Experiment Parameters	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collection of measurements from the sensors to the 5G-CPE 2. Correlation of measurements and timestamping 3. Transmission of measurements from the on-board 5G-CPE to the ground 4. Trackside processing at the edge server
Edges	Edge server used to process in real time measurements collected from the rolling stock
Remote	Central cloud facilities used to store measurements and train the AI/ML models
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 4-19 Scenario Description

Scenario Description Template – Lab / field	
Radio access technology (RAT)	5G-NR based on OAI
Standalone / Non-Standalone (if applicable)	5G-SA
Cell Power	N/A
Frequency band:	N78
Maximum bandwidth per component carrier	100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	N/A
Cyclic Prefix	N/A
Massive MIMO	2x2 MIMO
Duplex mode	N/A
TDD uplink/downlink pattern	N/A
User location and speed	See Figure 4-6
Background traffic	N/A
Computational resources available	X86 servers

4.5.3 Test Cases and KPIs tables

The main objective of the use case is to test the operation of the railway system management platform that can be used to estimate and then predict the status of the railway track and prescribe optimal intervention plans.

Figure 4-47 – Interactions and communication between the different modules supporting the operation of the platform. Connectivity between the onboard components and the edge cloud facilities is provided over 5G

To achieve this, the platform comprises a set of microservices adopting the architecture shown in Figure 4-47 performing the following actions:

- Data Acquisition responsible for the collection of data from various sensors. It should be mentioned that Hellenic Train allocated a specific train for experimentation purposes. This train has been equipped with sensors monitoring a variety of parameters (such as acceleration, vibration, position, etc.) attached to the rolling stock frame, continuously monitoring the status of the tracks.
- Message Broker facilitating inter-module connectivity. The interaction between the developed modules utilize an asynchronous Application Programming Interfaces (API) based on MQTT.
- Storage (data, ML metadata repository) implemented through InfluxDB for the time series datasets and PostgreSQL for object storage. InfluxDB through MQTT exporter stores all real time measurements acquired from the field. PostgreSQL is used to store ML metadata.
- Train module responsible for the selection and optimization of the hyperparameters of the ML models. The ML schemes are able to detect track defects and estimate the deterioration rate of track quality over time.
- Prescribe module responsible for the MOO and recommendation of the optimal maintenance plans. The MOO problems that have been formulated in order to estimate the candidate time periods during which maintenance activities can be scheduled under various constraints and cost functions.

The connectivity between the different modules is provided through Application Programming Interfaces (API) adopting the Publish (PUB)-Subscribe (SUB) approach. The two basic PUB and SUB commands have been implemented using a message broker. Each application can publish or subscribe to a specific topic and send or receive the necessary information. The basic components that have been used to implement the various modules include:

- MQTT (MQ Telemetry Transport) is a lightweight, publish-subscribe, machine to machine network protocol. It is designed for connections with remote locations that have devices with resource constraints or limited network bandwidth. It runs over a transport protocol that provides ordered, lossless, bidirectional connections—typically, TCP/IP. It is an open OASIS standard and an ISO recommendation (ISO/IEC 20922).
- Graphical user interfaces developed using the open source anvil.works platform written in Python,

Figure 4-48 (left) Time series data visualization dashboards showing acceleration, vibration and speed, (middle) Wavelet analysis performed in a specific track segment for anomaly detection, (right) Normal vs abnormal speed vibration profiles

Figure 4-49 (left): ML model validation against test data. 1: indicates defect in a specific track point, 0: normal track point, (middle): geolocation of track defects, (right): verification of track anomalies using field surveys

Figure 4-50 Track degradation model

Figure 4-48 - Figure 4-50 provide some snapshots of the graphical interfaces developed to support the application of the Hellenic Train use case. Users have the option to view plots of the collected time-series per track segment. Typical plots that can be generated include acceleration and

vibration, speed, simple statistics per track segment etc. Comparisons between different track segments can also be provided. A typical example is shown in Figure 4-48 (left) where platform users can customize their dashboard and view down-sampled versions of the collected metrics. In addition to simple time-series plots, the dashboard provides forms to visualize basic statistics and view graphs of advanced signal processing models. The relevant dashboard is shown in Figure 4-48 (right) where users can select the track segment and time window where the analysis can be performed. Users can select on AI model through a drop-down list of AI models that can be trained to identify track defects. So far, the platform supports the following ML models: Support Vector Machine (SVM), Neural Networks (NN) models based on Recurrent Neural Networks, Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM), Principal component analysis (PCA), Self-Organizing Maps (SOM) and Logistic Regression. The results of the training process (optimal ML model and relevant performance metrics) are stored in the ML repository. The trained ML models are available to the users through the ML repository. The ML repository contains the list of all pretrained ML models together with their corresponding accuracy metrics (i.e., training error). Users can select through the "tick box" the optimal pretrained model that they want to deploy in the system. Once selected, the ML models can be tested using either history measurements Figure 4-49 a) or real time data collected by the monitoring platform. To further verify the accuracy of the results obtained field surveys have been performed (Figure 4-49 b-c). Finally, based on the collected measurements the degradation of the track over time can be estimated which in turn is used to optimize the operation of the train (see Figure 4-50).

From a technical perspective, the performance of developed services over the 5G platform has been reported in D3.6. The relevant results for different number of connections and sampling frequencies are shown in the following tables.

Metric	Description																									
Average e2e delay for a network slice	<p>This KPI describes the average e2e UL packet delay between the PSA UPF and the UE for a network slice.</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Data extracted from the graph: Total Delay per message (s) vs Number of Connections</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Number of Connections</th> <th>10KB (s)</th> <th>50KB (s)</th> <th>100KB (s)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>100</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.01</td> <td>0.02</td> </tr> <tr> <td>200</td> <td>0.01</td> <td>0.05</td> <td>0.10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>300</td> <td>0.02</td> <td>0.25</td> <td>0.35</td> </tr> <tr> <td>400</td> <td>0.15</td> <td>0.50</td> <td>0.78</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Number of Connections	10KB (s)	50KB (s)	100KB (s)	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	100	0.00	0.01	0.02	200	0.01	0.05	0.10	300	0.02	0.25	0.35	400	0.15	0.50	0.78
Number of Connections	10KB (s)	50KB (s)	100KB (s)																							
0	0.00	0.00	0.00																							
100	0.00	0.01	0.02																							
200	0.01	0.05	0.10																							
300	0.02	0.25	0.35																							
400	0.15	0.50	0.78																							

throughput for Single Network Slice Instance	<p>This KPI describes the downstream throughput of one single network slice instance by computing the packet size for each successfully transmitted DL IP packet through the network slice instance during each observing granularity period and is used to evaluate integrity performance of the end-to-end network slice instance. It is obtained by downstream throughput provided by N3 interface from all UPFs to NG-RAN which are related to the single network slice.</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Data for Throughput vs Number of connections</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Number of connections</th> <th>10KB (Messages/sec)</th> <th>50KB (Messages/sec)</th> <th>100KB (Messages/sec)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>1.0</td> <td>1.0</td> <td>1.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>100</td> <td>1.0</td> <td>1.0</td> <td>1.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>200</td> <td>1.0</td> <td>1.0</td> <td>0.95</td> </tr> <tr> <td>300</td> <td>0.98</td> <td>0.75</td> <td>0.65</td> </tr> <tr> <td>400</td> <td>0.95</td> <td>0.6</td> <td>0.25</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Number of connections	10KB (Messages/sec)	50KB (Messages/sec)	100KB (Messages/sec)	0	1.0	1.0	1.0	100	1.0	1.0	1.0	200	1.0	1.0	0.95	300	0.98	0.75	0.65	400	0.95	0.6	0.25
Number of connections	10KB (Messages/sec)	50KB (Messages/sec)	100KB (Messages/sec)																							
0	1.0	1.0	1.0																							
100	1.0	1.0	1.0																							
200	1.0	1.0	0.95																							
300	0.98	0.75	0.65																							
400	0.95	0.6	0.25																							

4.5.4 Conclusions – Lessons learned

As already discussed monitoring and operations optimisation of the railway network although of great importance for the rail industry can be quite a challenging problem in railway environments due to the large number of parameters, variables, and constraints involved in the decision-making process. Through this activity it was proven that from a technical view point the 5G-VICTORI solution can effectively and efficiently support optimised monitoring and operation of railways systems. However, as all trials were performed in operational environments detailed planning was needed to allow granting of permission for access, installation of equipment, device mounting regulations etc. This had significant impact also in the overall project time plan. Equipment installation and deployment in harsh environments such as operational trains and rail tracks requires additional attention in planning, time allocation and risk assessment and management. Optimising rail monitoring services directly impacts the requirements of the 5G infrastructure, therefore it is bringing the need for additional degrees of intelligence in the 5G infrastructure.

4.5.5 Vertical business KPI validation

To validate the results obtained through the developed platform a Sensitivity Analysis has been performed. It is well known that the main factors affecting the performance of data acquisition system is the precision of the sensors, the frame grabbing rate of the industrial camera used to monitor the track and the network bandwidth interconnecting the building blocks of the systems. A detailed analysis is out of the scope of the present deliverable, however, for the shake of completeness these factors are summarized below.

- Sensors:** The sensors used for HT use case are a mix of IEPE accelerometer's and standard 4-20mA output vibration transmitters. The former operates in a frequency range between 0-20 kHz introducing very low noise while the latter in lower frequency ranges. In practice, using the 4-20 mA sensors we are able to monitor the rise in vibration at a specific point of the track but unable to understand the cause of this rise which is necessary for predictive maintenance. This problem can be solved using IEPE sensors which combined with high sampling frequency measurements we can proactively detect faults. A disadvantage of IEPE sensors is their high price as compared to standard 4-20mA sensors are x5 - x10 more expensive, require 3 communications channels per sensor increasing the required bandwidth.
- Sampling frequencies:** The selection of the sampling frequencies at the data acquisition subsystem depends on the type of faults and the type of sensors used to monitor the track condition. Based on the Shannon sampling theory the system should be sampled at a rate of at least 2x the operational frequency of the IEPE accelerometers. Lower sampling rates may results to loss of spectral information increasing uncertainty. For cost efficiency reasons, the

sampling rate has been selected to preserve 99\% of the spectral information of IEPE sensors.

- **Synchronisation:** Channel measurement synchronisation is a critical parameter affecting quality of data. Synchronisation error across the distributed measurements channels may affect the performance of the IAMS platform as the corresponding correlation analysis performed by the data analytics modules may end-up to wrong conclusions regarding the cause and position of faults. For the HT use case we have used an extension of the network time protocol (NTP)~ms accuracy, called precision time protocol (PTP)~ ns accuracy, used in industrial acquisition systems.
- An additional parameter that affects also the quality of the collected measurements is the **speed of the frame grabber** used to take snapshots from the track. Besides the selection of sensors, the configuration of the data acquisition system in one of the main building blocks that impacts the IAMS efficiency. Parameters such as sampling rates, precise synchronization of measurements collected across distributed channels and data acquisition platforms and, correlation of measurements coming from heterogeneous sources should be carefully considered in the design of an IAMS platform. Finally, the system should have sufficient network capacity to transfer the collected measurements from the platform installed on-board to the cloud based data management system.

4.6 Conclusions – Patras

The partners **UoP**, **ICOM**, **UTH**, **IASA**, **COSM**, **TRA**, **IHP**, **KCC**, **ADMIE** have co-designed, integrated and deployed 5 fully operational 5G network deployments and a full end to end transport deployment for executing the Patras 5G-VICTORI UCs. Four UCs, i.e. **UC #1.1**, **UC #2**, **UC #3** and **UC #4**, have been deployed at the vertical facilities in large scale heterogeneous environments and have deployed several services (counting 10 services over 4 vertical and cross vertical industries).

A summary of the main conclusions from the trial activities is as follows:

- All UCs have been demonstrated as large scale field trials in 2023, all integrated in operational vertical facilities with very interesting results.
- **UC #1.1** provided 5G connectivity on board while the operational train was moving along an operational railtrack. The mobility management framework that was developed for 5G-VICTORI supported connectivity over a 4 node transport network of various technologies that was deployed for the purposes of **UC #1.1** large scale trials, which proved to be very tedious with respect to the design and deployment of the network technologies.
- The **KCC** Mission Critical Solution based on MCx / FRMCS deployed both at the **TRA** trials and Berlin trials provided important insights for the specific service deployment.
- **UC #2** services were fully tested in an **ADMIE** operational environment, despite the limitations in hardware deployment in those HV facilities. End to end network slicing was achieved and private network solutions with two 5G indoor configurations was exhibited.
- **UC #3.1** was deployed at the **TRA** facility with performed in the field, the lab results of the previous two phases were validated, for both the vCDN and the Surveillance services.
- **UC #4** was deployed at **TRA** facility where innovative service deployment unveiled benefits of 5G for the specific vertical industry.

5 Field Trials in Bristol

5.1 Detailed Network topology for the trials

The demonstration of the Bristol cluster took place at the Bristol 5G-VICTORI facility in 4th of October, 2022, encompassing four locations within the city centre of Bristol. These locations were as follows: (for a more detailed explanation of the network setup and performance along the entire route, please refer to deliverable **D2.3** [5] and **D4.2** [2]):

- Outside the M Shed Museum.
- A boat trip along the Bristol Harbourside, indicated by the blue dotted colour on the map. The boat trip starts at the M Shed and concludes at Millennium Square (MSq), passing through the SS Great Britain Steam Ship.
- We The Curious (WTC) / MSq.
- Smart Internet Lab, High Performance Networks group (HPN), Merchant Venturers Building (MVB).

For a visual representation of the 5G-VICTORI Digital Mobility UC #1.2 Demonstration setup locations in the Bristol facility, please refer to Figure 5-1. The blue dotted path indicates the boat journey, while the yellow dotted path shows the walking journey.

Figure 5-1 5G-VICTORI Bristol - Digital Mobility UC Demonstration setup

During the Bristol Field Trail that took place from October 3rd to October 4th, 2022 (setup and the main demo), the Bristol 5G-VICTORI facility showcased the 5G-VICTORI Digital Mobility UC (UC #1.2) with three applications: **App1**, **App2**, and **App3**. A summary of these applications is provided below, and for more detailed information, please refer to **D2.1** to **D2.3** [3][4][5]:

- **App1**: This application, developed by Mativision (**MATI**), offers immersive media and AR/VR services to travelers.
- **App2**: **MATI** also developed **App2**, which focuses on 360° VR multi-camera live streaming. It emphasizes large user connectivity and caters to a greater number of users.

- **App3:** Urban Hawk (**UHA**) Future Mobility application, developed by an entity called Urban Hawk, provides 5G-enabled multi-user and multi-agent planning.

The Bristol demonstration incorporated various solutions and services developed by partner organisations. These included Zeetta Automate slicing solution, 5G-VIOS, i2SM, MATI **Apps 1 and 2** storage/stream/backhaul NSs, UHA **App3**, Amarisoft 5G-call-box. These solutions and services were seamlessly integrated into the existing testbed, along with the newly created Nomadic Node.

In addition, the 5G-VIOS was integrated into the 5GUK test network, where Apps 1 and 2 NSs were deployed, orchestrated, monitored, and profiled through the 5G-VIOS. Moreover, the transport networks – VLANs, Dynamic Multipoint VPN (DMVPN), Open Shortest Path First (OSPF) – among edges (M Shed, HPN, WTC, Nomadic) and their connectivity for deployment of Apps 1 and 2 were automatically deployed by 5G-VIOS and were tested during the trial. During June and July 2023, UHA APP3 was also integrated into the 5G-VIOS and 5GUK test network.

Figure 5-2 shows the 5G-VICTORI Digital Mobility **UC #1.2** demonstration setup in Bristol facility, while details are provided in Table 5-1. Figure 5-3 also shows the end to end deployment of 5G-VICTORI architecture to demonstrate **Apps 1 to 3** in Bristol.

Figure 5-2 5G-VICTORI Bristol facility Digital Mobility UC (UC #1.2) demonstration at related edges

Figure 5-3 E2E deployments of 5G-VICTORI architecture to demonstrate the Digital Mobility UC (#1.2) Apps 1 to 3

Table 5-1 Bristol Facility – 5G Deployment Setup at edges for October’s field trial

	M Shed	WTC/MSQ	Nomadic Node	Smart Internet Lab
Open-Source	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
SA/NSA	SA	SA	SA	SA
Cloud options	OpenStack Bare-Metal	OpenStack Bare-Metal	OpenStack Bare-Metal	OpenStack Bare-Metal
MANO	OSM Zeetta Automate	OSM Zeetta Automate	OSM i2SM	OSM Zeetta Automate
Core	Open5gs	Open5gs	Open5gs	Open5gs
RAN	Nokia gNB	Nokia gNB	Amarisoft gNB	Accelleran CU/DU Benetel RU
UE	Redmi Note 9 Pro 5G Samsung S20+ 5G Huawei P40 Pro 5G 5G CPE (in-house built)	Redmi Note 9 Pro 5G Samsung S20+ 5G Huawei P40 Pro 5G 5G CPE (in-house built)	Samsung S20+ 5G Huawei P40 Pro 5G 5G CPE (in-house built)	Redmi Note 9 Pro 5G 5G CPE (in-house built)

The Network extension work to support Digital Mobility UC – Bristol field trial- Oct 2022 is summarised in the following. For more details, please see deliverable [D4.2](#) [2].

- Enhanced MEC resources at the edges to support **Apps 1, 2, and 3**:
 - More computational resources physically installed at the edges.
- Deployment of the Nomadic Node as an additional edge:
 - Improve 5G coverage and provide services to outage areas.
 - Installing new 5GNR supporting band n77 on the roof top of M Shed to provide network coverage towards SS Great Britain
 - Relaxed backhaul requirement – services run locally.

- In-house built 5G CPE - Wireless connection to the cloud over 5G/WiFi6.
- Integration of 5G-VIOS, Zeetta Automate and i2SM to the 5GUK Testbed and Nomadic Node, respectively:
 - End-to-End service provision.
 - Slicing and network infrastructure orchestration.

Previous Nomadic Node setup (in Oct 2022) was as depicted in Figure 5-4:

Figure 5-4 Nomadic Node – inside the box (High-level)

Figure 5-5 Nomadic Node - outside the box

Figure 5-5 provides an overview on the outside front, top, and back of the Nomadic Node box. This Node was built and integrated to the rest of the network by the 5GUK Testbed team where **i2CAT** integrated an Amarisoft 5G box (provided by **DCAT**) to the Nomadic Node, along with the i2CAT Slice Manager (i2SM) and a Wi-Fi6 AP. Furthermore, an in-house built CPE with multiple 5G modems was used to establish wireless connectivity with the 5GUK network, either via the testbed’s 5G network or a public operator’s LTE/5G network. A software solution was developed on the CPE to check the connectivity every 500 ms, switching between the 5GUK and public operator modems, demonstrating seamless layer-2 over layer 3 wireless connectivity between the nomadic and 5GUK networks, using both trusted and untrusted networks. Consequently, the demonstration was also possible at locations out-of-coverage of the 5GUK Testbed. For more details, please refer to deliverable **D4.2** [2].

Final demo in June 2023:

For the final demo in June 2023, the Bristol cluster contributed to demonstrate MATI **App2** between Bristol and Patras, as well as implementing the inter-cluster communication between Berlin and Bristol using a VPN-secured link between the sites over the internet. Furthermore, 5G-VIOS provided the inter-cluster service creation, with the remote class (**App2**) being available at both Patras and Bristol clusters. The Inter-cluster UC demonstration details are provided in Section 7. In addition, at this final project demo, **UNIVBRIS** upgraded Nomadic node with additional computational resources and a Nokia gNB.

The Nomadic node upgrades are as follows:

- Integrated Edge Routing using VyOS.
- The use of edge local domains/subnetting for higher:
 - Isolation
 - Flexibility
 - Scalability
- Full Integration with 5G-VIOS.
- Wired connection to external networks now possible.
 - Priority-based gateway selection.
 - Wired > Private Wireless > Public Wireless
- GPU processing capability.

5G deployment setup in June 2023’s final demo is provided in Table 5-2. The setup of the other edges were the same as Oct’s trial (see Table 5-1).

Table 5-2 Bristol Facility- 5G Deployment upgraded setup at Nomadic node edge (June 2023 demo)

	Nomadic Node
Open-Source SA/NSA	Yes SA
Cloud options	OpenStack Bare-Metal
MANO	OSM i2SM
Core	Open5gs
RAN	Nokia gNB (n77 @ 100MHz)
UE	Samsung S20+ 5G Huawei P40 Pro 5G 5G CPE (in-house built)

Performance improvements (DL and UL throughput between 5G UE and 5G Core) are shown in Figure 5-6 and Figure 5-7, respectively. The Latency (RTT) improvement is shown in Figure 5-8.

Figure 5-6 DL throughput between 5G UE and 5G Core

Figure 5-7 UL throughput between 5G UE and 5G Core

Figure 5-8 Latency (RTT) between 5G UE and 5G Core

Figure 5-9 i2SM slicing example using monolithic and disaggregated approaches.

For the final Bristol demo, **i2CAT** focused on evaluating two main features of the i2CAT Slice Manager (i2SM): (i) the disaggregated deployment of the 5G Core using Amarisoft and Open5Gs, and (ii) the deployment of two concurrent slices. In addition, the resources needed by the 5G Core instances were reduced compared to the previous demo in October 2022, consequently also reducing the slice deployment time due to the smaller footprint of the instances.

As shown in Figure 5-9, the implemented and evaluated approach supports two deployment modes: monolithic and disaggregated. In the monolithic approach, a single 5G Core instance is deployed per tenant or slice, containing all the 5G Core NFs. On the other hand, in the disaggregated approach, three different instances are considered: the shared control plane, the SMF and the UPF. While the first slice deployment of a tenant contains these three instances, the subsequent slices only require the SMF and the UPF. In both monolithic and disaggregated modes, multi-tenancy is supported using Multi-Operator Core Network (MOCN). Also, as shown in Figure 5-9, different VLANs are used to isolate control, user and data planes.

Table 5-3 outlines the minimum resources required by the considered deployment modes, based on the minimum requirement of Open5Gs and the number of deployed 5G Core instances. Despite the resources needed for the first disaggregated slice, which entails the deployment of the control plane plus the SMF and the UPF instances, the subsequent slices (i.e., only SMF and UPF instances) offer a more efficient solution than the monolithic case (i.e., one single instance with all NFs). This results in reductions of up to 25% in vCPU usage and 50% in RAM usage. This efficiency becomes increasingly significant as the number of slices increases, showcasing the scalability and cost-effectiveness of the disaggregated mode in managing resource allocation.

Table 5-3 i2SM deployment modes: minimum required resources

Deployment Mode	# vCPU	RAM (GB)
Monolithic (per tenant/slice)	4	4
Disaggregated (First slice per tenant)	4	6
Disaggregated (Subsequent slices)	3	2

Figure 5-10 Time spent during slice deployment operations by I2SM: one slice, 100 iterations

Figure 5-10 illustrates the average execution time for creating, activating and deploying (e.g., creation plus activation) one single slice using i2SM and considering the monolithic and disaggregated deployment modes. As aforementioned, due to the reduction of the resources needed by the 5G Core instances, the time for deploying a monolithic slice was reduced by 60% compared to the trial in October 2022. Note that all the evaluated cases achieved slice deployment times below 60 seconds, which are within reasonable limits for scenarios such as the temporary or pop-up network demonstrated in Bristol using the Nomadic Node.

Figure 5-11 illustrates the average execution time for deploying two concurrent slices using i2SM and considering the monolithic and disaggregated deployment modes. This evaluation is reported in the test case **RDNuComb04** of App1 (Table 5-9). In this case, we have considered a multi-tenant scenario; in which two slice deployment requests are handled simultaneously by i2SM. This means that we considered the concurrent deployment of: a) two monolithic slices; b) two first disaggregated slices (control plane, SMF and UPF); and c) two subsequent disaggregated slices (SMF and UPF). Being a more demanding scenario, we can observe an increase in the deployment times as expected. Nonetheless, achieved values are still favourable for the use case of pop-up networks.

Overall, these results indicate that, albeit i2SM’s disaggregated approach incurs slightly higher deployment times, it is an acceptable trade-off for its main benefits: traffic and resource isolation, finer resource allocation, and higher functions placement flexibility for multi-service capabilities. This allows tenants to efficiently manage shared resources according to service status and requirements instead of over-provisioning monolithic deployments.

Figure 5-11 Time spent during slice deployment operations by ISM: two slices, 100 iterations

5.2 App1: MATI immersive media and AR/VR services to travelers

MATI App1 focuses on exploiting the performance and added capabilities of the 5G Network to deliver to passengers’ location-based informative content by means of an immersive application in the city centre. It gives a 360° tour guide via 5G at specific geolocation video spots: M Shed, MSQ, Bristol Canal and MVB.

When or after travellers arrive at M Shed and as they move between specific geolocation spots, immersive content is delivered either as AR or directly on their 5G-enabled devices presenting relevant information for the route they are following including the M Shed and MSq edges and the boat ride on Bristol Canal (served by the Nomadic Node) and a walk to Smart Internet Lab (MVB).

Seamless service provisioning during mobility is demonstrated – also by deploying and testing the service on a movable base (a boat). For more details on the **App1** description, please refer to **D2.3** [5] and **D4.2** [2].

5.2.1 Field trial description

Services for **App1** are successfully provided at areas covering M Shed, MSQ, the Bristol Canal and MVB. The service coverage is implemented by three network edges, two conventional testbed edges at the M Shed museum and WTC, and one ‘mobile’ edge (Nomadic Node) on a boat. Each of the edges provide 5G SA and Wi-Fi connectivity to the end users, as well as MEC capability for low latency application processing. 5G-VIOS is deployed at MVB and is responsible for the end-to-end service provision and inter-edge service mobility. 5G-VIOS APIs were integrated to the transport network orchestrators (Zeetta automate, i2SM), cloud orchestrator (OSM), and **App1** itself to dynamically trigger and implement inter-edge service handover based on the end-user’s mobility.

5.2.2 Experiment and scenario descriptions

The next tables present **UC #1.2** experiment description for the different services.

Table 5-4 Experiment 1 (DCAT) (Ref: D4.2)

	Value	Comments
ExperimentType	Standard	
Automated	True	
TestCases	Test Case 1	

UEs	UE1, UE2	UE Models are provided in Table 5-1.
Network Slice	Mativision_App1_cacheserver, Mativision_App1_storageserver	The required network slices to run App1 NSs at corresponding edges
Network Services	NSD IDs: 5867207d-c4a7-4c88- bb8c-9fd2479d0c89, 3ac5d3de-81f3-45d2- b2f8-1b49cf9d3061	
Network Scenario	Scenario 1	
Exclusive Execution	True	
ReservationTime	N/A	
Experiment Name	Mativision_App1	
Performance targets & SLAs	<p>Network Service KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> cpu_utilisation: 0.98, memory_utilisation: 100 <p>Application KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mobility latency: 3 	The target KPIs include the Application KPIs, Network Service KPIs, etc. These KPIs will be used by 5G-VIOS profiler to find the optimum configuration of resources to assign to NSs and then through the Experiment Life Cycle Management, send alerts if the NSs are not meeting these KPIs in real time. Note: these KPIs (name and/or value) can be updated based on each experiment.
Experiment Parameters	<p>Minimum and Maximum configuration of Resources:</p> <p>cpu:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min_cores: 2, max_cores: 8 <p>memory:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min: 200, max: 1000 <p>link_capacity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min: 400000000, max: 1400000000 	The Minimum and Maximum configuration of resources. The 5G-VIOS Profiler will use them to profile the NSs and predict the optimum configuration of each resource (a value between min and max) utilising ML techniques to assign to each NS.
Edges		{VLANs: 143, 145,147,149 , Edge_IDs}
Remote	N/A	
Remote Descriptor	N/A	
Version	v1.0	
Extra	N/A	

Table 5-5 Scenario Description (Configuration of setup at Bristol facility edges) in October 2022's demo [2]

	HPN (Smart Internet Lab) Edge	M Shed Edge	WTC Edge	Nomadic Node Edge; 5G RAT	Nomadic Node Edge; Wi-Fi RAT
Radio access technology (RAT)	5GNR, Sub-6 GHz	5GNR, Sub-6 GHz	5GNR, Sub-6 GHz	5GNR, Sub-6 GHz	Wi-Fi 6

Standalone / Non-Standalone (if applicable)	SA	SA	SA	SA	N/A
Cell Power	27 dBm	41 dBm	42 dBm	≤ 10 dBm	≤ 20 dBm
Frequency band:	n77	n78	n77	n77	Channel 36 (primary)
Maximum bandwidth per component carrier	100 MHz	40 MHz	100 MHz	100 MHz	80 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz	30 kHz	30 kHz	30 kHz	
Number of component carriers	Maximum number of CC = 4 (5G)	Maximum number of CC = 4 (5G)	Maximum number of CC = 4 (5G)	1	1
Cyclic Prefix	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Massive MIMO	No	Yes, 64T64R	No	No	No
Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO)	4x2	4x2	4x2	4x2	2x2
Modulation schemes	DL: QPSK, 16 QAM, 64 QAM, 256 QAM UL: QPSK, 16 QAM, 64 QAM, 256 QAM	DL: QPSK, 16 QAM, 64 QAM, 256 QAM UL: QPSK, 16 QAM, 64 QAM, 256 QAM	DL: QPSK, 16 QAM, 64 QAM, 256 QAM UL: QPSK, 16 QAM, 64 QAM, 256 QAM	DL: QPSK, 16 QAM, 64 QAM, 256 QAM UL: QPSK, 16 QAM, 64 QAM, 256 QAM	Up to 1024-QAM
Duplex mode	TDD	TDD	TDD	TDD	
TDD DL:UL slots ratio	7:3	7:3	7:3	7:3	
Contention based random access procedure/contention free	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	CSMA/CA
User location and speed	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Background traffic	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Computational resources available	112 CPU cores, 256GB RAM, 4TB storage (shared)	56 CPU cores, 128GB RAM, 2TB storage (shared)	56 CPU cores, 128GB RAM, 2TB storage (shared)	56 CPU cores, 128GB RAM, 1TB storage	56 CPU cores, 128GB RAM, 1TB storage

Table 5-6 Scenario Description (Configuration of setup at Bristol facility upgraded Nomadic node edge) in June 2023's demo.

	Nomadic Node Edge; 5G RAT	Nomadic Node Edge; Wi-Fi RAT
Radio access technology (RAT)	5G NR, Sub-6 GHz	Wi-Fi 6
Standalone / Non-Standalone (if applicable)	SA	N/A
Cell Power	≤ 23 dBm	≤ 30 dBm
Frequency band:	n77	5 GHz (auto primary channel)
Maximum bandwidth per component carrier	100 MHz	160 MHz

Sub-carrier spacing	30 kHz	
Number of component carriers	Maximum number of CC = 4 (5G)	1
Cyclic Prefix	N/A	N/A
Massive MIMO	No	No
Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO)	4x4	4x4
Modulation schemes	DL: QPSK, 16 QAM, 64 QAM, 256 QAM UL: QPSK, 16 QAM, 64 QAM, 256 QAM	Up to 1024-QAM
Duplex mode	TDD	
TDD DL:UL slots ratio	7:3	
Contention based random access procedure/contention free	N/A	CSMA/CA
User location and speed	N/A	N/A
Background traffic	N/A	N/A
Computational resources available	80 CPU cores, 256GB RAM, 9TB storage	

5.2.3 Test Cases and KPIs tables

During the Bristol Field Trial (03-05 October 2022), for **App1**, **MATI** App1 was fully integrated into 5G-VIOS. Both the storage VM and the caching VM were instantiated through 5G-VIOS at corresponding edges close to the end user devices. The content was streamed from the storage VM and cached on the caching VM before reaching multiple UEs. The master application was run on one device while the client player was run on other two devices. The monitoring of metrics (KPIs measured by **App1**) was also tested and reported back to 5G-VIOS through appropriate APIs and shown in the metrics visualization 5G-VIOS portal. During the move of our group around Bristol, the services were migrated on multiple edges including M Shed, Nomadic Node, WTC and supported the playback of multiple high bitrate 360 videos on multiple devices at the same time. For more details, please refer to **D4.2** [2]. The following test cases (Table 5-7, Table 5-8, Table 5-9) show the test case reports that we run in October’s field trial. These test cases had been reported in D4.2 as well.

The Nomadic Node is upgraded with an additional server for higher computational (CPU and GPU) capability and storage capacity. The Amarisoft gNB and i2CAT WiFi solution were replaced with better performing (throughput, latency, and coverage) Nokia and Ruckus solutions, respectively. The Netgear (1GbE) L2 switch was also replaced by an Edgecore (1GbE/10GbE) L2 switch, and local routing capability was implemented using VyOS. The updated specifications are shown in Table 5-7. Some tests were also repeated with the newly added components, and the results are tabulated in Table 5-9.

As mentioned in Section 5.1, the evaluation done in June 2023 led to a reduction of the slice deployment time for the monolithic deployment mode. Also, we introduced and evaluated the disaggregated approach. In any case, the result originally reported in **D4.2** is still valid (pass, deployment time of less than 1 minute). Finally, as specified in **D3.2**, we evaluated Multi-Slice Deployment (Table 5-9). Due to the modifications done in the Bristol’s Nomadic Node, replacing the Amarisoft node with a Nokia gNB, the reported tests were realised in the **i2CAT** testbed using software and hardware resources which mimic the original Nomadic Node (i.e., Amarisoft gNB, Open5Gs, I2SM, OpenStack...).

Table 5-7 Test report: RDNu01

Field	5GUK Infrastructure test case between Core and Edges, and between the Edges.	
Test Case ID	RDNu01	
Facility, Site	Bristol cluster	
Description	Test the performance of dedicated 5G network resources such as latency, and throughput between the core and various edges. For testing the network KPIs detailed in related test cases, dummy VMs were instantiated at each edge (MShed, WTC). Throughput and latency tests were conducted between the dummy VMs (instantiated at each edge) and the 5G Core (MVB). iPerf3 was ran for 20 s to measure the TCP DL/UL throughput. Ping was run for 20 s to measure latency.	
Executed by	Partner: UNIVBRIS	Date: 03/10/2022 - 04/10/2022
Purpose	Pass/fail results; Pass if the Latency is <1 ms and Throughput is >1Gbps Note: Create two test records one for M Shed and another for WTC edge servers.	
Scenario	Refer to the right scenario template used for the test (see Table 5-5)	
Slice Configuration	N/A	
Components involved	Dummy Linux VMs on OpenStack machines located at HPN, M Shed and WTC.	
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	DL/UL Throughput, Latency (RTT).	
Tools involved	Iperf3, ping	
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	HPN (5G Core) – M Shed: DL/UL 9.3/9.3 Gbps , 0.46 ms HPN (5G Core) – WTC: DL/UL 9.3/9.3 Gbps , 0.46 ms WTC – M Shed: 9.3/9.3 DL/UL Gbps , 0.6 ms	
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	PASS	

Table 5-8 Test report: RDNu02 (Measurements involving only the Nomadic Node upgrades)

Field	Throughput and Latency tests between UE and Core/Edges.	
Test Case ID	RDNu02	
Facility, Site	Bristol cluster	
Description	Test the 5G network performance (latency, throughput) between the Nomadic Node and the 5GUK edges over wired backhaul. Latency and throughput measurements are taken between a UE connected to the Nomadic Node 5G network and dummy VMs on the Nomadic Node and the 5GUK edges. This test was taken inside the lab without an external wireless network, i.e., wireless backhauling was not possible.	
Executed by	Partner: UNIVBRIS	Date: 10/08/2023 - 11/08/2023
Purpose	(Assuming a worst-case wireless backhaul latency of 50ms. Wireless backhaul throughput varies depending on technology - 4G/5G/WiFi - and network congestion.) Pass/fail scenario 1:	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pass if the Latency between the UE and corresponding edges (MShed, MSQ, and Nomadic node) is <50 ms and Throughput is >100 Mbps Fail if the Latency between the UE and corresponding edges (MShed, MSQ, and Nomadic node) is >=50 ms or Throughput is <=100 Mbps
Scenario	Refer to the right scenario template used for the test (see Table 5-5)
Slice Configuration	N/A
Components involved	5G SA phone, server (bare metal) / VM (OpenStack) hosting the 5G core and an additional dummy VM (Nomadic Node).
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	DL/UL Throughput (wired), Latency (RTT).
Tools involved	Iperf3, ping
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	<p>Nomadic Node – UE DL/UL (peak) @ Nokia: 780/115 Mbps, 11 ms</p> <p>HPN (dummy VM) – UE DL/UL @ Nomadic Node: 780/115 Mbps, 14 ms</p> <p>MShed (dummy VM) - UE DL/UL @ Nomadic Node: 780/115 Mbps, 16 ms</p> <p>WTC (dummy VM) - UE DL/UL @ Nomadic Node: 780/115 Mbps, 16 ms</p>
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	PASS

Table 5-9 Test report: RDNuComb04

Field	5GUK Infrastructure combined test case for Multi-Slice Deployment	
Test Case ID	RDNuComb04	
Facility, Site	Bristol cluster	
Description	<p>Test the performance of on-demand multi-slice management, considering 5GNR SA RAN, in terms of network slice establishment and slice deployment time.</p> <p>Compare MOCN-based (monolithic) and SNSSAI-based (disaggregated) network slicing approaches.</p>	
Executed by	Partner: i2CAT	Date: June 2023
Purpose	Pass/fail results; Pass if the combined Slice Deployment time of both slices is < 90 mins.	
Scenario	Nomadic Node	
Slice Configuration	<p>The test case comprehended the deployment of two concurrent slices, with different PLMNId and S-NSSAI values.</p> <p>Monolithic deployment included two 5G Core instances (one per tenant or slice).</p> <p>Disaggregated deployment included several 5G Core instances (shared control plane, slice-specific SMF and UPF).</p>	
Components involved	Nomadic Node hardware (Amarisoft gNB, switches, 5G CPE, servers) and software (OpenStack, OSM, i2CAT's Slice Manager and RAN Controller).	
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Slice deployment time (creation plus activation)	
Tools involved	I2SM to report deployment time.	

Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	Slice deployment time was less than 90s for both monolithic and disaggregated approaches.
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	PASS

Report of KPIs being measured by **MATI App1**:

The following cases were tested from the set locations around Bristol (M Shed, SS Great Britain, MSq, MVB) that provided a 360 video to a group of people moving from one 360 video geolocation to another. When reaching each specified geolocation, the VR video was tested on multiple devices controlled by one master device. There was variance in the results depending on the location that the devices were in. The SS Great Britain was the spot with the lowest coverage with all devices achieving a synchronized state streaming the 6 Mbps stream. When one master and one client device was used, the 15 Mbps stream was able to be streamed. The rest of the tour had good coverage and the devices were able to stream the 15 Mbps target stream. The technology used for streaming the content provided multiple renditions of the same 360 video to allow for bitrate fluctuations and the tour run without re-buffering events and the devices kept synchronicity even with poor coverage.

Table 5-10 Test report: RDIu01

Field	Mativision Synchronization Latency
Test Case ID	RDIu01
Facility, Site	Tested on boat from M Shed edge
Description	Synchronization latency between master device and client devices
Executed by	Partner: MATI Date: 2022-10-04
Purpose	Test synchronization latency
Scenario	see Table 5-5
Slice Configuration	Configuration of the slices (if any) and details about them with respect to above
Components involved	Mativision Synchronization edge service
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Synchronization latency
Tools involved	Custom latency reporting
Results and KPIs Primary	10-22 ms
Complementary	
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	<100 ms

Table 5-11 Test report: RDIu02 [2]

Field	Mativision 360 VR Video Streaming
Test Case ID	RDIu02
Facility, Site	Tested on multiple locations
Description	Bandwidth achieved by devices
Executed by	Partner: MATI Date: 2022-10-04
Purpose	Get the most common bitrate achieved by devices
Scenario	see Table 5-5

Slice Configuration	Configuration of the slices (if any) and details about them with respect to above
Components involved	Mativision Backhaul storage server, Mativision edge caching service
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Bandwidth in kbps
Tools involved	Custom bitrate reporting
Results and KPIs Primary	15.000 kbps – M Shed, MSq, MVB
Complementary	15.000 kbps – SS Great Britain, One device
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	5000-6000 kbps – SS Great Britain, Two devices
	>10.000kbps

Table 5-12 Test report: RDIu03

Field	Mativision Mobility test
Test Case ID	RDIu03
Facility, Site	Tested on multiple locations
Description	Time it takes for a service to be instantiated on a new edge location
Executed by	Partner: MATI Partner: MATI
Purpose	Get the initialization time of an edge service and prepare it before it is needed.
Scenario	see Table 5-5
Slice Configuration	Configuration of the slices (if any) and details about them with respect to above
Components involved	Mativision edge caching service
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Time in seconds
Tools involved	Custom cronjob reporting initialization to backhaul server
Results and KPIs Primary	~50s
Complementary	
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	<60s

Table 5-13 Test report: RDIu04 (same as D4.2)

Field	Mativision Edge Caching Performance
Test Case ID	RDIu04
Facility, Site	Tested on boat from M Shed edge
Description	Network savings between backhaul server and UE devices
Executed by	Partner: MATI Date: 2022-10-04
Purpose	Test the network savings of the caching on the edge
Scenario	see Table 5-5
Slice Configuration	Configuration of the slices (if any) and details about them with respect to above
Components involved	Mativision Backhaul storage server, Mativision edge caching service
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Network savings in percentage

Tools involved	bmon ²
Results and KPIs	
Primary	49-60%
Complementary	
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	>30%

5.2.4 Conclusions – Lessons learned

The 5GUK testbed could deliver a satisfactory service provision along most of the demonstration route. However, depending on the users’ locations, the throughput and latency performance of the 5G link varied significantly. This performance variation also affected the wireless connectivity between the Nomadic Node and the rest of the 5GUK network/edges. Networks services for future mobility should always take into account these performance variations and be able to efficiently protect the end-to-end service provision.

The latency when synchronising the devices proved to be ultra low and provided fast synchronisation between devices. The devices had enough bandwidth to run 360 video on multiple devices at the same time. The only location that the devices did not receive the full allotted bitrate was when running on the boat near SS Great Britain and for this reason multi-bitrate streaming is implemented to provide a seamless experience on changing network conditions.

5.2.5 Vertical business KPI validation

During the course of 5G-VICTORI, the commercial exploitation plans have shifted focus. Initially **MATI** had identified tourism as a target market sector and aimed to use the results of this project to develop products and services for this sector. However, this sector was damaged considerably by the pandemic and other external factors and potential prospects have become weary of investments in any asset or technology or service which is not considered essential for their immediate survival, making it harder to bring the immersive application to the market. Therefore, while **MATI** still aims to target the Tourism Market, we expect that we will not see meaningful progress in the near future. However, the application also has considerable potential in other market comparable sectors, where the goal is also to deliver content to moving people. One of these is immersive enterprise solutions in HR tasks such as group training on location, H&S training in facilities and similar tasks. The technology developed is currently being incorporated into products in this market sector. One example is a VR based health and safety training application for a factory.

In terms of joint exploitation, there has been close cooperation with **UNIVBRIS** and **DCAT**. Beyond working on 5G-VICTORI related trials together, we have contributed to dissemination events, such as workshops that show the result to industry stakeholders and present potential uses of 5G based applications to companies. Working with DCAT is particularly beneficial, because as network specialists, they have a lot of knowledge on networks themselves and this can enrich our knowledge as application specialists, creating a productive overlap of topics. UNIVBRIS has also used insights from our joint work in publications.

Recently there have been discussions and knowledge exchange with **UHA** regarding capabilities for building streaming platforms and applications can be used, especially for immersive technologies. There have also been discussions with UoP regarding how a remote lecture infrastructure could be useful for them.

In terms of future exploitation, a focus is on further exploring the possibility of delivering localized content to people on move in industry settings. There appears to be a lack of solutions and a variety

² **bmon** is a monitoring and debugging tool to capture networking related statistics. **MATI** uses bmon to monitor the traffic coming in and going out of the caching server at any given time and also uses the tool to compare the volume of data received and transmitted during streaming.

of problems to which applications such as ours can present a solution. One example is visually supported remote warehouse management.

5.3 App2: MATI VR Multicamera Live streaming at UNIVBRIS campus

App2 not only demonstrates 360° VR Live streaming to multiple Users (one to many) but also demonstrates connectivity and bandwidth availability for multiple Users at the same time. It focuses on exploiting the performance and added capabilities of the 5G Network to implement Remote Virtual Classroom Applications which can deliver immersive training/education to remote groups of trainees. The Service can capture and deliver immersive content and applications and will offer the potential to connect remote educational/training facilities across Europe.

This App was also demonstrated between Patras and Bristol as one of the 5G-VICTORI inter-cluster usecases. More details about inter-cluster demonstration of this UC are provided in section 7.2.

Lecturers who are in any one of the connected locations, will be able to deliver lectures as immersive VR immersive experiences to full classrooms of trainees/students, who will be wearing appropriate 5G-enabled VR headsets or use their 5G-enabled phones. The students will have the impression that they are sitting in the lecture theatre from which the Lecturer is delivering the lecture.

5.3.1 Field trial description

Services for **App2** are successfully provided at areas covering M Shed, MSq, and MVB. The service coverage is implemented by three network edges at the M Shed museum, WTC and MVB. Each of the edges provide 5G SA and Wi-Fi connectivity to the end users, as well as MEC capability for low latency application processing. 5G-VIOS is deployed at MVB and is responsible for the end-to-end service provision, by instantiating cache servers at the edge for low latency video streaming with relaxed backhaul performance requirements. Due to the nature of this use-case, user mobility was not implemented as maximum availability and throughput is required.

5.3.2 Experiment and scenario descriptions

The next tables present **UC #1.2 (App2)** experiment description for the different services.

Table 5-14 Experiment 1 (DCAT) [2]

	Value	Comments
ExperimentType	Standard	
Automated	True	
TestCases	Test Case 2	
UEs	UE1, UE2	<i>UE Models are provided in Table 5-1.</i>
Network Slice	Mativision_App2_streamingserver Mativision_App2_cacheserver	<i>The required network slices to run App2 NSs at corresponding edges.</i>
Network Services	NSD IDs: 5867207d-c4a7-4c88-bb8c-9fd2479d0c89, 3ac5d3de-81f3-45d2-b2f8-1b49cf9d3061	
Network Scenario	Scenario 1	
Exclusive Execution	True	
ReservationTime	N/A	
Application	Mativision_App2	

<p>Performance targets & SLAs</p>	<p>Network Service KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> cpu_utilisation: 0.98, memory_utilisation: 100 <p>Application KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bandwidth: 300000 	<p>The target KPIs include the Application KPIs, Network Service KPIs, etc. These KPIs will be used by 5G-VIOS profiler to find the optimum configuration of resources to assign to NSs and then through the Experiment Life Cycle Management, send alerts if the NSs are not meeting these KPIs in real time. Note: these KPIs (name and/or value) can be updated based on each experiment.</p>
<p>Experiment Parameters</p>	<p>Minimum and Maximum configuration of Resources:</p> <p>cpu:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min_cores: 2, max_cores: 8 <p>memory:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min: 200, max: 1000 <p>link_capacity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min: 400000000, max: 1400000000 	<p>The Minimum and Maximum configuration of resources. The 5G-VIOS Profiler will use them to profile the NSs and predict the optimum configuration of each resource (a value between min and max) utilising ML techniques to assign to each NS.</p>
<p>Edges</p>		<p>{VLANs: 144, 146, 148, 150, Edge_IDs}</p>
<p>Remote</p>	<p>N/A</p>	
<p>Remote Descriptor</p>	<p>N/A</p>	
<p>Version</p>		
<p>Extra</p>		

The Scenario description is provided in Table 5-5. Please kindly note that for demonstrating **App2**, we only considered HPN (Smart Internet Lab), MShed and WTC edges.

5.3.3 Test Cases and KPIs tables

During the Bristol Field Trial (03-05 October 2022), for **App2**, **MATI** ran the caching VM of the application, instantiated through 5G-VIOS while keeping the streaming server VM close to the 360° video camera. The 360° video camera was placed in the Smart Internet Lab and we tested streaming high bitrate 360° video content for more than 15 hours throughout the two days of the 5G-VICTORI field trial. The stream was cached on the caching VM which was migrated to multiple edges. The 360° video content was played back on multiple devices while on the move around Bristol. The metrics were reported through the cache server back to 5G-VIOS and were displayed on the visualization page of 5G-VIOS. For more details, please refer to deliverable **D4.2** [2]. The following test cases (Table 5-16 Table 5-17) show the test case reports that we run in October's field trial. These test cases had been reported in D4.2 as well. However, the test case from Table 5-15 has been added newly to deliverable **D4.3**.

The following test cases have been revised to reflect the bitrate metrics of 1, 2 and 3 devices running concurrently from one edge in MVB which have been also tested in previous trials.

Table 5-15 Test report: RDLu01 (updated)

Field	Description
Test Case ID	RDLu01 Mativision Live 360 VR Video Streaming
Facility, Site	Tested in MVB
Description	Bandwidth achieved by devices
Executed by	Partner: MATI Date: 2022-10-04
Purpose	Get the most common bitrate achieved by devices
Scenario	see Table 5-5
Slice Configuration	Configuration of the slices (if any) and details about them with respect to above
Components involved	Mativision Backhaul storage server, Mativision edge caching service
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Bandwidth in kbps
Tools involved	Custom bitrate reporting
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	50.000 kbps on 1 device 20.000 kbps on 2 devices concurrently 10.000 kbps on 3 devices concurrently 5.000 kbps on 4 devices concurrently
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	>10.000 kbps on 2 devices concurrently

Table 5-16 Test report: RDLu02

Field	Description
Test Case ID	RDLu02 Mativision Edge Instancing test
Facility, Site	Tested on multiple locations
Description	Test to determine the latency between the request for an edge service and the edge service being up and running.
Executed by	Partner: MATI Date: 2022-10-04
Purpose	Get the initialization time of an edge service and prepare it before it is needed.
Scenario	see Table 5-5
Slice Configuration	Configuration of the slices (if any) and details about them with respect to above
Components involved	Mativision Backhaul storage server, Mativision edge caching service
KPIs collected	Time in seconds

(Metrics collected)	
Tools involved	Custom backhaul reporting
Results and KPIs	
Primary	~50 s
Complementary	
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	< 60 s

Table 5-17 Test report: RDLu03

Field	Description
Test Case ID	RDLu03
Facility, Site	Tested on boat from M Shed edge
Description	Network savings between backhaul server and UE devices
Executed by	Partner: MATI Date: 2022-10-04
Purpose	Test the network savings of the caching on the edge
Scenario	see Table 5-5
Slice Configuration	Configuration of the slices (if any) and details about them with respect to above
Components involved	Mativision Backhaul storage server, Mativision edge caching service
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Network savings in percentage
Tools involved	bmon ³
Results and KPIs	
Primary	45-61%
Complementary	
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	>30%

5.3.4 Conclusions – Lessons learned

The edge server provided more than 50% reduction in backhaul traffic enabling more devices to see the same content in multiple locations. The stream was also tested with streams of up to 50 Mbps, on multiple devices to stress the network and achieve a result on how many devices and which is the optimal bitrate to be used when streaming via the edge. The test showed that a scalable, multi bitrate streaming architecture is mandatory because as more devices request the stream, the highest achievable bandwidth that each UE can receive drops proportionately to the devices requesting the stream.

³ **bmon** is a monitoring and debugging tool to capture networking related statistics. Mativision uses bmon to monitor the traffic coming in and going out of the caching server at any given time and also uses the tool to compare the volume of data received and transmitted during streaming.

5.3.5 Vertical business KPI validation

The business idea behind the Multicamera Live streaming at **UNIVBRIS** campus focused on exploiting the performance and added capabilities of the 5G Network to implement Remote Virtual Classroom Applications which will deliver immersive training/education to remote groups of trainees. At the beginning of the project, **MATI** identified a gap in the market as regards immersive/interactive services that would be targeting Education establishments. While the Internet made availability of resources easy, the delivery of high-level education by eminent persons was restricted to the location these educators were. At the same time in less developed geographies, high-level education (e.g. in Medicine) was not available and this had serious and often catastrophic consequences in the societies.

The purpose of the whole endeavour was to make possible the implementation of remote Virtual Classrooms by exploiting the capabilities and performance of the 5G network combined with immersive technology. The proposed solution as it was tested during the 4G Victori project, can be easily adapted to any sector, and can be used on all levels of education and training where “learning by watching” is the mode of training.

During the COVID-19 Pandemic the lockdowns, restriction in movement and the closure of physical teaching facilities created an urgent need to provide remote training. As a result, similar functionality to the one under investigation in 5G Victori became available by several vendors. Those solutions, because they used inferior networking infrastructures, inevitably offered lower-quality, lower-performance service. Despite the serious shortcomings, such platforms, in view of the urgent need, have been adopted by many during the pandemic. Although at the present point in time, there seems to be limited interest in the education market for higher performance Remote Teaching Applications that will need 5G to work, we believe that despite the deployment of lower-performance platforms, there will still be a potential in the market, as soon as the limitations of the current solutions become too restrictive. Mativision will be monitoring the market to identify expected changes in the needs and will attempt to commercialise the developed solution when the market circumstances allow.

5.4 App3: UHA Future Mobility

UHA's Future Mobility UC is about passenger guidance outdoors and indoors based on OpenStreetMap GIS data and LiDAR scans. Unlike in Berlin, where the vertical usefulness was much in the center, the focus in Bristol is on demonstrating mobility. Namely that the service or cached versions of some of the visuals can move with the users within the network.

The visual experience is streamed from GPU cloud to front-end in a low latency high bandwidth 5G environment. Please refer to deliverables **D2.3** [5], **D3.1** [9] and **D3.2** [10] for more details on this UC.

Figure 5-12 left: Bristol harbour digital twin; middle: photo taken at the Bristol field trial while multiple front-ends are served and interact; right: real-time cost and accessibility map of the Bristol center area with goals and parameters queried into the Polaron engine

The digital twin representing Bristol central also ended up in a voxelised dataset at **UHA**'s back-end.

Figure 5-13 left: Bristol M Shed LiDAR scan; right: the Matthew LiDAR scan

The Polaron engine produced a series of 2D and 3D interactive simulations – based on terrain data and semantics - as well as detailed 3D data of the M-Shed Museum in Bristol. This was accomplished using a combination of an Oxford Robotics “Rooster” a SLAM based device from the Grand Prize Winning DARPA Sub-T challenge - which uses VILENS to correlate and correct IMU and LiDAR drift, as well as a range of smart devices, a stereo neural camera and OpenStreetMap data - to produce a hybrid model - in which we could facilitate a real-time WebRTC multi-user experience.

This allowed us to pass data, Obj models from scans, as well as .js events from legacy and 5G connected devices - to allow us to assess the number of concurrent users our simulations could support - and the relative latency and performance considerations of both 5G and existing networks.

The 5G access point was via the two 5G-enabled devices provided via Bristol University partner, as well as their Nomadic node, that was setup on “The Matthew” as it traversed down the river in Bristol. This meant that the simulation end point was moving between edges - and would be a facsimile of edge movement - therefore allowing us to consider the impact of simulation, with latency and re-connections and validate the concept of running multiple services into a real-time edge based service.

5.4.1 Field trial description

During June and July 2023, **UHA App3** was fully integrated into the 5G-VIOS and 5GUK test network. The **App3** NSs were deployed by 5G-VIOS at corresponding edges and the migration of NSs from one edge to the other edge was tested through the 5G-VIOS Mobility Manager component.

Figure 5-14 Signal penetration and scattering inside the scanned M Shed building; another use case beyond risk and travel

This permitted the 5G-VIOS system to be used to exploit **UHA**'s Polaron engine and WebRTC to issue data and connections over the network. Outside of interruptions between edge handovers, this

performed well, as Polaron **App3** sits at the edge in close network proximity or connected via fiber, the benefits of real-time feedback and net latency between the simulation and the network and the end user experience could be measured. **UHA** has since then provided an Open Source QCOW2 WebRTC Stun/Turn server to the wider team for use in their other applications, since it can pass data, interactions and video - acting as a network brokerage / NAT and data transfer layer for other types of data and not just Polaron (which requires a custom rendering WebRTC component to push into the generic open standards WebRTC service).

5.4.2 Experiment and scenario descriptions

The next tables present **UC #1.2** experiment description for the different services.

Table 5-18 Experiment 1 (DCAT)

	Value
ExperimentType	UoB_UHA_APP3
Automated	True
TestCases	Scenario 1
UEs	True
Network Slice	UoB UHA App3
Network Services	"0ae478eb-24e6-476e-8904-12c67481b059,6a2b7b7b-470a-4b8f-840d-b1c58c728982,mshed"
Network Scenario	Scenario 1
Exclusive Execution	True
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	UrbanHawk UoB App3
Performance targets & SLAs	Network Service KPIs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> cpu_utilisation: 0.98, memory_utilisation: 100 Application KPIs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mobility Latency: 300000 MIR : 200
Experiment Parameters	Minimum and Maximum configuration of Resources: cpu: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min_cores: 2, max_cores: 8 memory: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min: 2000, max: 10000 link_capacity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min: 400000000, max: 1400000000
Edges	VLAN147
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	
Extra	

The Scenario description related to the corresponding edges is provided in Table 5-5.

5.4.3 Test Cases and KPIs tables

Table 5-21 UHA Test report: RDFu01 (same as D4.2)

Future Mobility edge location spatial scanning and mapping	
Test Case ID	RDFu01
Facility, Site	Bristol cluster
Description	3D Spatial scanning of exterior and interior passenger relevant infrastructure. Stereo Neural Cameras, COTS LiDAR and Smart Phones were used to assemble and validate various scenes against a geospecific data (orthorectified)
Executed by	Partner: UHA Date: 2022-10-04
Purpose	To be used in indoor guidance with the Polaron Engine's route planner in the next phase of the project.
Scenario	Table 5-5
Slice Configuration	N/A
Components involved	Polaron Engine back-end (Windows, C++, OpenCL, WebRTC). Polaron Engine front-end (Android, vanilla Javascript, Web browser). Nvidia RTX 3090 GPU farm.
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Spatial resolution and error when registering separately scanned point-clouds.
Tools involved	Oxford Robotics Rooster SLAM sensor (from an earlier DARPA subterranean challenge).
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	The whole of M-Shed and the Matthew were scanned between 1 to 10 cm accuracy.
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	PASS

Table 5-22 UHA Test report: RDFu02 (same as D4.2)

Field	Description
Test Case ID	RDFu02
Facility, Site	Bristol cluster
Description	Future Mobility communication between Backend, Frontend and Edge nodes (lab & field).
Executed by	Partner: UHA Date: 2022-10-04
Purpose	To measure latency when a non-cached brute force simulation at back-end is streamed to front-end users.
Scenario	1 meter resolution map of Bristol central with an AI agent constantly doing route planning.
Slice Configuration	N/A
Components involved	Polaron Engine back-end (Windows, C++, OpenCL, WebRTC). Polaron Engine front-end (Android, vanilla Javascript, Web browser). Nvidia RTX 3090 GPU farm.

KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Latency between back and front-end.
Tools involved	WebRTC
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	Successful connection and streaming with dual way data comm. Average latency of 60 ms measured.
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	PASS

Table 5-23 UHA Test report: RDFu03 (new)

Field	Description
Test Case ID	RDFu03
Facility, Site	Bristol cluster
Description	Future Mobility high bitrate data distribution between Back-end and Edge nodes, and Front-end(s).
Executed by	Partner: UHA Date: 2023-08-22
Purpose	To test the shared data distribution with multiple concurrent interfaces via WebRTC into the Polaron rendering pipeline. WebRTC's performance is well understood - how this interacts with 5G and a custom rendering pipeline was to be assessed.
Scenario	Connect multiple concurrent devices to the Polaron Simulation service and promote simultaneous interactions. Each device has a custom set of interactions and must be streamed a rendered map of the area as well as activities of other users, with latency desirable at around 30-120ms for 2.5D spaces and 3D models running at 30fps (or faster).
Slice Configuration	N/A
Components involved	Polaron Engine back-end (Windows, C++, OpenCL, WebRTC). At Urban Hawk's Bristol office on fiber. Polaron Edge (Stun/Turn VM) at the Smart Internet Lab. Polaron Engine front-end (Android, vanilla Javascript, Web browser). Both at Urban Hawk's Bristol office and the Smart Internet Lab.
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Bitrate of video and data streaming. Latency between back and front-end via packets sent around.
Tools involved	WebRTC built-in metrics. Polaron built in packet send and receive then re-identification through unique IDs.
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	Between 500 and 800 kbps while the render stream left the back-end in 414 x 895 pixel resolution. This is per front-end. Latency wise, test packets did a full round in average 65.8 milliseconds, with peaks at 42 and 121 milliseconds.
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	For up to 10 users this is a PASS. Beyond 10 users neither can the GPU farm nor the bandwidth (peer to peer as every user gets a dedicated render stream) keep up. But that's beyond the current TRL. Future mitigation includes cloud GPU scaling like on AWS; addition of media servers so that identical render streams can be grouped to relevant users with the number of peer to peer streams reduced. User interactions via data streams are insignificant kbps wise compared to the render streams. 100MB+ spatial scan uploads from front-end sensor to back-end are not required in real-time.

Table 5-24 UHA Test report: RDFu04 (new)

Field	Description
Test Case ID	RDFu04
Facility, Site	Bristol cluster
Description	Future Mobility, hopping between Edges.
Executed by	Partner: UHA Date: 2023-08-22
Purpose	To test the mobility aspect of the service.
Scenario	Connect multiple concurrent devices to the Polaron Simulation service and promote simultaneous interactions while the Edge WM (Stun/Turn server) is orchestrating and coordinating the peer to peer connections.
Slice Configuration	N/A
Components involved	Polaron Engine back-end (Windows, C++, OpenCL, WebRTC). At Urban Hawk's Bristol office on fiber. Polaron Edge (Stun/Turn VM) at the Smart Internet Lab. Polaron Engine front-end (Android, vanilla Javascript, Web browser). Both at Urban Hawk's Bristol office and the Smart Internet Lab.
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Demonstrate reconnection between front-end and back-end while the Edge VM changes. Old VM gets destroyed and a new WM created on a different IP. This is useful when a user moves away from one datacenter and gets closer to another.
Tools involved	5G-VIOS. Front-end and back-end metrics to validate successful reconnection.
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	The front-end managed to disconnect then reconnect while the Stun/Turn server's VM was replaced.
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	The test was triggered manually. PASS. It worked. In future this shall be automated but requires additional components to be developed.

5.4.4 Conclusions – Lessons learned

The simulation had some bugs, when connecting multiple end users to the backend - which **UHA** have since debugged. This was to do with the message brokering and ordering and some brittle code that had been inherited.

Despite some challenges, **UHA** with the help of **UNIVBRIS** and Digital Catapult (**DCAT**), managed to realise the mobility side of the plan: WebRTC presents an interesting capability and facsimile for other transport methods, and it's ability to move and sit between different services across a 5G enabled network, along with the movement of the QCOW2 and **UHA** operated service over the Bristol Smart Lab network suggests that leveraging an intelligent management tool such as 5G-VIOS to move, data, services and network components close to the point of demand - allows for faster connections, lower latency and contextualized serving of relevant simulations and experiences to end users.

By running some of the work through public connections and some via 5G we were able to assess the comparable speed and performance of a 5G Nomadic node and localised edges, versus the much slower input and experience able to be delivered over non-5G networks.

The M Shed museum scans, were a particular highlight, as was the Mathew scans - allowing a user to see inside and experience a museum, pushed over a local network and acting as a facsimile of the value add digital twins and interactive experiences offer. The live multi-user trials, with concurrent

interactions into the semantic data (one person able to close roads, or factor in different data - akin to a preference or mobility profile) allowed us to validate the concept of live multi-user or agent driven planning. Since this experience has to compete from a real-time basis with pre-cached performance, we were happy with the results - and validated that we could continue to pursue the Parametric Insurance and Multi-Modal transport applications.

We have since implemented a number of additional systems on the back of this trial, such as live terrain profiling against change, a more refined GUI and reworked some significant memory management components to provide even greater performance, scale, and a better end user experience.

5.4.5 Vertical business KPI validation

This was designed to validate work ahead of the inter-cluster demonstrations - hence the focus on 3D and indoor spaces, semantic data (e.g. Mobility profiles - such as cobbled streets being less attractive to certain users) and the interfaces between 3D and 2.5D experiences.

We aimed to validate circa 10 concurrent users and reached 8 before some quirks of WebRTC (rather than Polaron) caused some issues. This has shown us that we need to consider how we manage and engage with all parts of the experience, since a fully real-time simulation running at the backend means very little if the front end experience is disjointed or jittery.

It also determines the experience of the user, since we already know what our backend data ingestion rate is, the ability to then pass not only this mapped experience, but calculations within it, disruption and then push data back to a user or other system to query and suggest an alternative is critical.

The multi-user test also showed that public safety and planning (supply side of multi-modal transport and insurance) can be played out effectively by people, but those interactions and queries can be codified and automated. This means that users can quickly highlight preferences in an interactive manner and have this be added to their particular requirements.

These mobility profiles and criteria are critical, since it allows for the multitude of different user profiles to be considered and factored into both a Parametric model as well as into the journey planning aspect of our proposal.

We also learned that for every sensor, people will often want to add in their own data - often via a finger, to indicate a traffic jam, road-works or other data that might not have been added to the system. This ease to react as well as the Validation of the data presents some interesting opportunities for us albeit with a need to follow up these reports with V&V and inference. However within a trusted group (e.g. Family / Commuters / Colleagues) such an ability to augment known data from larger sources with bespoke custom data and have the two interact was seen as highly desirable.

5G performance is a critical part of our success in this regard - since the real-time collaborative mapping, queries and qualifiable insurance triggers (non-insured products) is a key part of providing an attractive service, gaining user generated data and insights and delivering an ultra fast and responsive product that can compete with global suppliers who charge nothing for their products and services. Consequently the latency, scale and concurrent number of users 5G affords unlocks a lot of scope for growth especially around complex or unfamiliar environments or where privacy and security laws, economic constraints, and other factors discourage the use of pervasive surveillance.

Additionally we have been suggested to consider risks - especially in regards to larger events, such as protests and disruption; be it weather or increasing complexity of transport interactions. In order to generate insight from less well defined data - potentially operating via a Nomadic 5G node in austere conditions or during recovery operations, affording the ability to provide information on resilience and support the direction of limited resources.

5.5 Conclusions – Bristol

UNIVBRIS designed, integrated and deployed a fully operational network, meeting all of the requirements of the 5G-VICTORI services. From Cloud, to MEC and 5G, the 5GUK testbed successfully delivered service provisioning at all network edges supporting the demonstration route for the field trial. Despite numerous unforeseen events, such as the fire at the WTC museum, **UNIVBRIS** delivered a complete 5G-VICTORI platform incorporating all the required hardware components, networking functionality and software capability. A non-stationary network edge, namely the Nomadic Node, was also deployed to provide the functionality required for **Apps 1** and **3**. In addition, the set of different solutions and services developed by the partners involved in the Bristol demonstration (e.g. **Zeetta** Automate slicing solution, **i2CAT** Slice Management (i2SM), and **DCAT**'s Amarisoft 5G-call-box and Wi-Fi Access Point) were fully integrated to the already existing testbed as well as the newly created Nomadic Node.

For **App1**, **MATI** tested both the synchronization and caching services on multiple devices running in parallel. For **App2**, **MATI** tested live streaming of 360 video on multiple devices with edge caching enabled. Both tests were run successfully, meeting the required KPIs and providing the expected quality of experience. For **App3**, **UHA** ran some basic tests of their solution where their application was implemented based on WebRTC and data streaming from the Cloud (MVB – HPN lab) to the edges over 5G connection. With additional integration of a GPU at the edge node and further testing **App3** application services at the edge node could have created a better user experience for **App3**. Due to the limitations during the field trial the GPU resources were not available at any of the edges.

5G-VIOS was fully integrated to the 5GUK testbed and all the edges, including the Nomadic Node. 5G-VIOS was mainly hosted in the 5GUK Cloud (MVB - HPN), while some of its components, such as the edge proxy and edge monitoring were deployed at the edges. **App1** and **App2** were fully integrated to the 5G-VIOS ecosystem, supporting a dynamic end-to-end service creation and deletion at any network location (HPN, M Shed, WTC, Nomadic Node) while also storing the measured KPIs at each edge and then sharing them with the central profiling service. The deployment of **App3** has been verified and the migration of **App3** from the M Shed edge to the HPN edge has been successfully tested allowing service continuation after migration. In addition, all Apps 1 and 2 were profiled through the VIOS Profiler, and their profiling dataset were stored in Elasticsearch data repository. Finally, The VIOS Profiler could predict the optimum configuration of resources per each Network service through utilising Machine Learning techniques. In this way, 5G-VIOS could assign optimum resource values to each application.

For the final project demo in June 2023, the Bristol and Patras clusters demonstrated the inter-cluster service provision involving **App2**. In addition, the Bristol and Berlin demonstration also took place including the inter-cluster **App3**. The inter-cluster communication between **Patras-Bristol** was implemented using a VPN-secured link between the sites over the internet. The Berlin-Bristol inter-cluster communication took place through Amazon AWS. 5G-VIOS also provided the inter-cluster service creation, with the remote class being available at both clusters (in case of **App2**). The Nomadic Node was also upgraded with additional computational resources and 5G RAN.

UHA provided a QCOW2 image to Bristol University, who were able to install and operate this on their 5G-VIOS platform. Tests were conducted to demonstrate that an image could be moved between instances and containers, then resumed in a new location. Since the QCOW2 image and WebRTC component could then reconnect using the infra from other systems in the network as well as the NAT negotiation offered by the STUN / TURN services of WebRTC.

Tests were conducted to demonstrate how the component would be moved between each location, and a fiber connection to each, and internet connection provided the means to validate the performance of the WebRTC > Polaron connections as well as the end user device input and overall latencies.

6 Field trials in the FR/RO Cluster

Field trials in FR/RO cluster took place during the 5G-VICTORI Interim Review in June 2022 and has been continued in September 2022 and May 2023, concluding the UCs functionality in the 5G environment (**UC #1.2** and **UC #4.2**):

- **UC #1.2** Digital Mobility – Electric Bus connected to 5G SA network, running in the area of the 5G Site.
 - **App1:** Infotainment/ video services in dense, static and mobile environment.
 - **App2:** AI recognition and identification of emergency situation.
 - **App3:** Prioritized communication to command and control center.
- **UC #4.2** Energy – Low-Voltage (LV) metering devices located in different municipality locations in the city, in the area of the site coverage.
 - **App1:** Real-time LV energy metering services for designated points of interests.
 - **App2:** Energy Analytics for predictive and proactive maintenance for designated points of interest.

The location in Figure 6-1 corresponds to the Orange Romania (**ORO**) network edge deployment of the 5G SA infrastructure for the UCs running in real life deployment in Alba Iulia Municipality (**AIM**).

Figure 6-1 FR/RO cluster UCs demonstration area

6.1 Detailed Network topology for the trials

To execute and validate the trials, the 5G SA infrastructure has been implemented, as described in deliverable **D2.2** [4], network baseline from 5G-EVE was extended to the FR/RO cluster infrastructure to support 5G SA services and multi-slice capabilities. The E2E architecture can be seen in Figure 6-2. The key network components are the 5G SA RAN and Core, as they will be further described in detail, the virtualized infrastructure based on Kubernetes and Openstack tools, service orchestration framework and the end-to-end connectivity between elements. These are used to deliver 5G services in the specified area as described in Table 6-1.

Table 6-1 5G-VICTORI core technology involved

Technology	5G-VICTORI for UC #1.2 and UC #4.2
Open- Source	OpenAirInterface (mosaic5g)
SA/NSA	SA option 2
Cloud options	IaaS/CaaS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OpenStack • Kubernetes
MANO	OSMv12
Core	Mosaic5G Rel.16
RAN	Mosaic5G Rel.16
Devices	Quectel /Huawei Multiple devices 2 network slices(eMBB/URLLC) 5G SA camera

Figure 6-2 FR/RO 5G SA network architecture design

5G components have been integrated and tested through 5G services and 5G network functionality. These services have been demonstrated in AIM focusing on a real life live scenario, on which a 5G SA network (RAN and Core) and a virtualized environment supporting a set of network functions were deployed. The 5G deployment in the FR/RO cluster is based on the OAI 5G Stack implemented at the **ORO** facility. It integrates the RAN, CN software and hardware components of 5G SA systems. These are described in detail in deliverable **D2.3** [5], together with the software functions and interfaces integration, as shown in Figure 6-3.

Figure 6-3 FR/RO Cluster 5G SA deployment

The key characteristics of the FR/RO integrated 5G system are:

- 5G SA option 2 cloud native deployment
- AMF, SMF, UPF (SPGWU), NRF, UDM, UDR, AUSF, MYSQL
 - FLEXRIC O-RAN-compliant flexible RAN intelligent controller allowing to perform slicing in the RAN domain
- Hardware details running the 5G services
 - Compute infrastructure (HPE)
 - IP/Network (Cisco)
 - Security/Access (Fortinet)
 - RHU (2x2 MIMO)
 - 5G Antennas (2x2 MIMO)
- Software
 - Kubernetes
 - 5G OAI for 5G SA RAN/Core running in virtualized infra(K8s)
- Radio spectrum: N78 [50 MHz]

Figure 6-4 FR/RO Cluster AIM network deployment details

Figure 6-5 FR/RO UCs running on top of the infrastructure

The deployment (5G SA software blocks implementation) permits **UC #1.2** and **UC #4.2** to run in parallel, over a single 5G SA network, with each of the service flows running over a 5G configured slice respecting and preserving the traffic characteristics: **traffic prioritization and low latency, broadband traffic or IoT traffic**, within eMBB Slice, Low-Latency Slice, as seen in Figure 6-5.

The detailed design is providing in RAN and Core the network slice services, 5G SA setup & data traffic Packet Data Networks (PDNs) (UL/DL/latency), multiple-APNs, as the requested bandwidth is released and the required radio resources are allocated to the slice ensuring the required QoS. The 5G network computing platform, based on the **EUR** solution, is based on a number of dense servers and white-box switches (Cumulus) and includes eNB (outdoor 2x2 10 MHz, B28 or B13), eNB (indoor SISO RRUs, B38), gNB FR 1 (4x50 MHz or 2x100 MHz, n78), gNB FR 2 (100 MHz, n261), 4G/5G core (with NSA/SA), as seen in Figure 6-6.

Figure 6-6 FR/RO 5G SA Radio deployment

Figure 6-7 FR/RO cluster mapping of 5G SA services

Figure 6-7 illustrates the mapping of deployed services over the 5G infrastructure, implementing the specific related interfaces for the required 5G SA functionality and services definition, interconnecting the 5G DNN interfaces to the datacenter application hosting in the cloud, as in Figure 6-7.

Relevant characteristics of 5G services are mapped to the 5G FR/RO infrastructure and tested based on the testing scenarios described by Figure 6-8:

- 5G UE and Video camera: the cameras located in the bus, connected to the analytics server (Edge Computing Component for video service), the communication component is provided over the Low Latency PDN slice.
- 5G SA Network: installed in Orange 5G site, as RRH/BBU, 5GCN core network components, network interfaces and local processing servers.
- Digital Mobility C&C: connected through N6 interface to the Emergency service video services.
- 5G UE Wi-Fi: located in the bus, providing Internet access through Wi-Fi, passengers connected to the AIM service portal and internet, the communication component provided over the broadband PDN slice.
- Analytics application: performing real time video services analytics for the emergency UC.
- IoT end device: the IoT metering device, connected to the IoT Telemetry analytics server, acting as aggregating component, the communication component is provided over the Low Latency PDN slice.
- 5G NSA/SA Network: installed in Orange 5G site, as RRH/BBU, vEPC/5GCN core network components, network interfaces and local processing servers.
- Telemetry platform: installed in cloud, acting as Telemetry Data Aggregator, Telemetry Database, Telemetry Application and engines and telemetry data storage, connected through N6/SGi interface to the IoT devices.

	UC Media - eMBB	UC Media - prioritized URLLC	UC LV Energy - mMTC	UC LV Energy - mMTC combined
Services tested	✓ user's data traffic as authentication, internet browsing, video streaming;	✓ single UE/Video cameras streams	✓ ~30 IoT devices running in parallel (sending data to Telemetry application)	✓ ~30 IoT devices running in parallel ✓ 3000 devices traffic simulated in the network in parallel
Measurements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> throughput tests Ookla & iperfv3 performance, network traffic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> data traffic network latency packet loss 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> network load measurements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> network load measurements
FR/RO cluster combined test-case 1	X		X	
FR/RO cluster combined test-case 2		X	X	
FR/RO cluster combined test-case 3	X	X	X	
FR/RO cluster combined test-case 4	X	X	X	X

Figure 6-8 FR/RO cluster 5G test scenarios

6.2 UC #1.2 Digital mobility and public safety

UC #1.2 focuses on real time media service delivery and prioritized communication to the Command and Control Centre (C&CC) in case of emergency situations triggered when detected by Artificial Intelligence (AI) enabled recognition and identification mechanisms. The required information is transmitted over 5G dedicated slices assuring real time management, E2E orchestration and QoS control.

Description of provided UC services:

- Infotainment/video services in dense, static and mobile environment.
- Prioritized communication to Command &Control Centre (DNN).
- AI recognition and identification of emergency situation.
- Creation of two network slices:
 - Internet connectivity
 - Slice1: slice offers up to 100 Mbps, downlink traffic, low traffic prioritisation.
 - Cameras' connectivity
 - Slice2: the URLLC slice offers 10 Mbps, uplink traffic; prioritised traffic (5QI).

Figure 6-9 FR/RO cluster UC #1.2 mapping

Figure 6-10 FR/RO Cluster UC #1.2 deployment

6.2.1 Field trial description

In the network two network slices have been configured, (1) the eMBB slice, as the DNN is connected to the internet for bus user access to different media types and (2) the URLLC slice, as the DNN is connected to the EDGE computing for analytics and traffic prioritization. The two network slices are configured and properly prioritized in the network based on 5QI and QoS parameters. Video Cameras and mobile routers have been installed in the bus, running in the demo experimentation area.

The UC implementation is based on a set of novelties and key innovation, as 5G SA Services deployment for 5G RAN and Core (5G SA), common Core. Also, the 5G service is provisioned to users, services slice is created and UEs association to proper slice (eMBB and URLLC), based on the RAN agent (RIC) application that auto-associates UEs to slices based on NSSAI, and the 5G traffic is prioritized through 5QI. From Network perspective, main Network KPIs are related to the 5G

SA network deployment and instantiation, service slices creation and UEs association to slices, service slice performance (Bandwidth/Latency) and traffic prioritisation, as the technology is validated by:

- E2E Network slices (eMBB & URLLC), as in Figure 6-11.

```
Mobile-gateway pdn bearer-context supi 226107900000077 detail |
Gi Network Inst : orangeurllc
N3 DL packets  : 29292287          N3 DL bytes      : 38720581272
SGI UL packets  : 25331370          SGI UL bytes     : 33707863336
Gi Network Inst : orange5glab
N3 DL packets  : 80168818          N3 DL bytes      : 107311183624
SGI UL packets  : 73294600          SGI UL bytes     : 97910600099
```

Figure 6-11 5G SA E2E slicing capabilities

- Traffic prioritisation (5QI/DSCP), seen in Figure 6-12.

Figure 6-12 5G SA URLLC traffic prioritisation

- Dynamic slicing control characteristics of the UEs and dynamic configuration of the 5G profiles.
- Parallel slices running (DNNs configured).

Figure 6-13 5G SA URLLC latency measurements KPI

Figure 6-14 5G SA eMBB throughput measurements KPIs

6.2.2 Experiment and scenario descriptions

The next tables present **UC #1.2** experiment description for the different services.

Table 6-2 Experiment 1 (ORO)

Description	
ExperimentType	Lab Network measurements KPIs (DL/UL/RTT)
Automated	NO
TestCases	MDIe01; MDIe02; MDCe01
UEs	Quectel 5G SA device
Network Slice	eMBB
Network Services	Infotainment data throughput and RTT, no mobility and no HO
Network Scenario	5G SA network eMBB slice
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	Iperf3 using UDP and TCP
Performance targets & SLAs	DL 20 Mbps; UL 10 Mbps RTT external < 100 ms RTT internal 60 ms DNS ping 8.8.8.8 < 60 DNS ping ORO < 40
Experiment Parameters	Static LAB environment
Edges	Edge Servers deployed with the 5G SA packet core
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 6-3 Experiment 2 (ORO)

Description	
ExperimentType	Field Network measurements KPIs (DL/UL/RTT)
Automated	NO
TestCases	MDIe01; MDIe02; MDCe01
UEs	Quectel 5G SA device
Network Slice	eMBB
Network Services	Infotainment data throughput and RTT, no mobility and no HO
Network Scenario	5G SA network eMBB slice
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	Iperf3 using UDP and TCP
Performance targets & SLAs	DL 100 Mbps; UL 30 Mbps RTT external < 40 ms RTT internal 10 ms DNS ping 8.8.8.8 < 40 DNS ping ORO < 20
Experiment Parameters	Static field environment
Edges	Edge Servers deployed with the 5G SA packet core
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 6-4 Experiment 3

Description	
ExperimentType	Field Network measurements KPIs (DL/UL/RTT)
Automated	NO
TestCases	MDIe01; MDIe02; MDCe01
UEs	Quectel 5G SA device
Network Slice	eMBB
Network Services	Infotainment data throughput and RTT, mobility and no HO
Network Scenario	5G SA network eMBB slice
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	Iperf3 using UDP and TCP
Performance targets & SLAs	DL 50 Mbps; UL 10 Mbps RTT external < 40 ms RTT internal 10 ms DNS ping 8.8.8.8 < 40

	DNS ping ORO < 20
Experiment Parameters	dynamic field environment
Edges	Edge Servers deployed with the 5G SA packet core
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 6-5 Experiment 4

Description	
ExperimentType	Field Network measurements Network slice capabilities
Automated	NO
TestCases	MDCe01, MDCe02, MDCe03, MDCe04
UEs	Quectel 5G SA device; Huawei P40
Network Slice	eMBB/URLLC
Network Services	Infotainment data network slice
Network Scenario	5G SA network eMBB/URLLC parallel slice
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	Iperf3 using UDP and TCP; ping tools; StableNet; TWAMP
Performance targets & SLAs	<p>Network slice capabilities/management</p> <p>E2E latency for interactive service (in ms) <30 ms;</p> <p>E2E latency for public safety service (in ms) < 5 ms;</p> <p>High bandwidth required for data intensive public safety applications and HD video</p> <p>streaming > 20 Mbps;</p> <p>Jitter for URLLC < 1ms</p> <p>E2E latency for interactive service (in ms) < 30 ms;</p> <p>E2E latency for public safety service (in ms) < 5 ms;</p> <p>High bandwidth required for data intensive public safety applications and HD video</p> <p>streaming > 20 Mbps;</p> <p>Jitter for URLLC < 1 ms</p> <p>iperf the average, min and max values for throughput and latency, for both slices</p>
Experiment Parameters	Static field environment
Edges	Edge Servers deployed with the 5G SA packet core
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 6-6 Experiment 5

Description	
ExperimentType	Field Network measurements Network slice capabilities
Automated	NO
TestCases	MDCe01, MDCe02, MDCe03, MDCe04
UEs	Quectel 5G SA device; Huawei P40
Network Slice	eMBB/URLLC
Network Services	Infotainment data network slice
Network Scenario	5G SA network eMBB/URLLC paralel slice
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	Iperf3 using UDP and TCP; ping tools; StableNet; TWAMP
Performance targets & SLAs	<p>Network slice capabilities/management</p> <p>E2E latency for interactive service (in ms) <30 ms;</p> <p>E2E latency for public safety service (in ms) < 5 ms;</p> <p>High bandwidth required for data intensive public safety applications and HD video streaming > 20 Mbps;</p> <p>Jitter for URLLC < 1ms</p> <p>E2E latency for interactive service (in ms) < 30 ms;</p> <p>E2E latency for public safety service (in ms) < 5 ms;</p> <p>High bandwidth required for data intensive public safety applications and HD video streaming > 20 Mbps;</p> <p>Jitter for URLLC < 1 ms</p> <p>iperf the average, min and max values for throughput and latency, for both slices</p>
Experiment Parameters	dynamic field environment
Edges	Edge Servers deployed with the 5G SA pachet core
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 6-7 Experiment descriptor related to UC #1.2

	Value	Comments
Experiment Type	Standard	
Automated	Manual	
TestCases	Test Case 1	
UEs	UE1, UE2	4 x Quectel 5G SA module 2x PI2 router
Network Slice	eMBB QCI 9 slice	3GPP Rel. 16

	URLLC QCI 5 slice	
Network Services	NSD IDs: eMBB & URLLC	N/A
Network Scenario	Scenario #1.2	
Exclusive Execution	True	
ReservationTime	N/A	
Experiment Name	UC#1.2_App1_2	
Performance targets & SLAs	Network Service KPIs: RTT (ms): eMBB 30ms; URLLC 10 ms DL/UL(Mbps): eMBB 30; URLLC 15; Application KPIs: Mobility latency": 3	<i>Network KPIs throughput/latency MDe01-04</i> Apps KPIs: Analytics Object detection Apps KPIs: MD Ae01-04
Experiment Parameters	Resources: Application vCPU Core:min 8 max 16, RAM: min:16GB, max: 32GB link_capacity(Mbps): min: 40 max: 1000	
Edges	HPE Gen10 K8s 5G SA EDGE Apps	VLANs: 101 DNN eMBB 102 DNN URLLC
Remote	N/A	
Remote Descriptor	N/A	
Version	v1.0	
Extra	N/A	

Table 6-8 Scenario Description (ORO ab)

Scenario Description Template – Lab	
Radio access technology (RAT)	5G-NR
Standalone / Non-Standalone (if applicable)	SA
Cell Power	10 W
Frequency band:	N78
Maximum bandwidth per component carrier	20 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 KHz
Cyclic Prefix	Normal
Massive MIMO	2x2 MIMO
Duplex mode	TDD
TDD uplink/downlink pattern	8:1
User location and speed	100 Mbps / 0 km/h
Background traffic	N/A
Computational resources available	112 CPU cores, 1TB RAM, 4TB storage

Table 6-9 Scenario Description field (AIM)

Scenario Description Template – field	
Radio access technology (RAT)	5G-NR
Standalone / Non-Standalone (if applicable)	SA
Cell Power	40 W
Frequency band:	N78
Maximum bandwidth per component carrier	50 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 KHz
Cyclic Prefix	Normal
Massive MIMO	2x2 MIMO
Duplex mode	TDD
TDD uplink/downlink pattern	8:1
User location and speed	100 Mbps / 30 km/h
Background traffic	N/A
Computational resources available	112 CPU cores, 1TB RAM, 4TB storage

6.2.3 Test Cases and KPIs tables

The following tables summarise the key results of the UC requirements and KPIs that have been evaluated in the FR/RO cluster during the field demonstration. The extracted results confirm that the 5G technical implementation addresses the needs of the UCs under evaluation. FR/RO cluster tests results, based on AIM field experiments, are shown further.

Table 6-10 UC #1.2 MDI test cases results

Test case group MDI (Infotainment)			
Test case name	Place	Key UC requirements and KPIs	Network performance requirements and KPIs
MDIe01	FR/RO AIM	DL 20 Mbps; UL 10 Mbps RTT external < 100 ms RTT internal 60 ms	DL: 100 Mbps UL: 30 Mbps RTT external 40 ms RTT internal 20 ms
MDIe02	FR/RO AIM	Browsing time <3s Service availability > 99%	www.gsp.ro browsing time latency <1.8s service availability 99,999 % during tests

Table 6-11 UC #1.2 MDC test cases results

Test case group MDC (Prioritized Communication)			
Test case name	Place	Key Use-case requirements and KPIs	Network performance requirements and KPIs
MDCe01	FR/RO AIM	DNS ping 8.8.8.8 < 60 DNS ping ORO < 40	40 ms 20 ms EDGE & C&C < 20 ms

MDCe02	FR/RO AIM	Network slice capabilities/management (Yes/No); E2E latency for interactive service (in ms) < 30ms; E2E latency for public safety service (in ms) < 5ms; High bandwidth required for data intensive public safety applications and HD video streaming > 20Mbps; Jitter for URLLC < 1ms	YES RTT < 30 ms RTT < 4 ms 30 Mbps DL 12 Mbps UL 0.05 ms 100% (ping/service tests)
MDCe03	FR/RO AIM	E2E latency for interactive service (in ms) < 30 ms; E2E latency for public safety service (in ms) < 5 ms; High bandwidth required for data intensive public safety applications and HD video streaming > 20 Mbps; Jitter for URLLC < 1 ms	28 ms 3-4 ms 40 Mbps 0.05 ms
MDCe04	FR/RO AIM	iperf the average, min and max values for throughput and latency, for both slices	100%

Table 6-12 Test Case Experiment MDIe01

Field	Authentication
Test Case ID	MDIe01
Facility, Site	FR/RO cluster
Description	The UE attaches to SSID Wi-Fi from the bus, is redirected to the portal that is offering administration information such as surveys, local news and tourism ads.
Executed by	Partner: ORO Date: Sep 2023
Purpose	Pass/fail scenario: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pass if within KPIs Fail if outside KPIs
Scenario	D3.4 Table 5 1 MDIe01: User authentication using captive portal
Slice Configuration	eMBB
Components involved	One laptop/tablet Wi-Fi AP eMBB slice configured over 5G network
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Portal access and authentication: < 5s DL/UL: 30/30 Mbps RTT: 30 ms(internal)
Tools involved	iperf3, tcpdump

Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	Authentication and network KPIs DL/UL: 30/30 Mbps RTT: 22 ms (internal)
	Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail) passed

Table 6-13 Test Case Experiment MDIe02

Field	Data availability
Test Case ID	MDIe02
Facility, Site	FR/RO cluster
Description	The scope of the test is to check the successful integration of the portal with different content sources.
Executed by	Partner: ORO Date: Sept 2023
Purpose	Pass/fail scenario: Pass if within KPIs Fail if outside KPIs
Scenario	D3.4 Table 5-2 - MDIe02: Captive portal data availability
Slice Configuration	eMBB slice is enabled in the network.
Components involved	One laptop/tablet Wi-Fi AP Wi-Fi portal eMBB slice configured over 5G network One synthetic monitoring tool.
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	loading times for each of the data sources
Tools involved	Tcpdump, synthetic monitoring tool(portal)
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	loading times threshold < 2-3s min/average/max loading times for each of the data sources 1.5/2.1s/4s Total number of unsuccessful tests for each data source: <0.01% Total number of successful tests for each data source: 99.99%
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	pass

Table 6-14 Test Case Experiment MDCE01

Field	End-to-end connectivity over a specific slice
Test Case ID	MDCE01
Facility, Site	FR/RO cluster

Description	Verify the establishment of E2E connectivity over an interactive eMBB slice for a tablet which is already authenticated on the portal towards the Control and Command Centre server, using ping and traceroute.
Executed by	Partner: ORO Date: Sept 2023
Purpose	Pass/fail scenario: Pass if within KPIs Fail if outside KPIs
Scenario	D3.4 Table 5 3 MDCe01 : Establishment of basic E2E connectivity over a specific slice
Slice Configuration	eMBB preconfigured slice
Components involved	One laptop Wi-Fi AP eMBB slice configured over 5G network.
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	RTT: 30 ms DL/UL: 30/20 Mbps
Tools involved	Icmp/iperftool
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	ping towards the IP of the Command & Control server works. ping towards the URL of the Command & Control server works (meaning that also the URL is resolved by the DNS service) RTT: 28 ms DL/UL: 50/30 Mbps
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	pass

Table 6-15 Test Case Experiment MDCe02

Field	End-to-end connectivity over two slices with different QoSs
Test Case ID	MDCe02
Facility, Site	FR/RO cluster
Description	checks the deployment of two different network slices having two different quality of service metrics: one eMBB slice for interactive service/camera's video and one slice with uRLLC capability.
Executed by	Partner: ORO Date: July 2023
Purpose	Pass/fail scenario: Pass if within KPIs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fail if outside KPIs
Scenario	MDCe02: Establishment of advanced E2E connectivity over two different slices with different QoS metrics configured
Slice Configuration	Two slices configured in the network
Components involved	Two laptops/tablets, Wi-Fi AP Two slices configured over 5G network: URLCC, eMBB.

	<p>Two laptops/tablets are connected to the two different slices: eMBB & URLCC; the connection is performed directly over 5G using SIM, two slices are configured in the 5G network with the needed QoS.</p> <p>On each of the two laptops/tablets iperf is activated for measuring network performance (bandwidth, latency and jitter).</p>
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	<p>eMBB DL/UL: 20/20 Mbps eMBB RTT: 25 ms URLLC DL/UL: 10/10 Mbps URLLC RTT: 6 ms Jitter: 0.1 ms</p>
Tools involved	<p>Iperf3, icmp, tcpdump, oss tool</p>
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	<p>eMBB DL/UL: 30/20 Mbps eMBB RTT: 20 ms URLLC DL/UL: 15/15 Mbps URLLC RTT: 5 ms Jitter: 0.1 ms</p>
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	<p>passed</p>

Table 6-16 Test Case Experiment MDCE02

Field	QoS prioritization on slices with congestion on radio part	
Test Case ID	MDCE03	
Facility, Site	FR/RO cluster	
Description	Once the threat alarm is triggered, the CCC operator needs to access camera images from the bus to decide what further emergency measures need to be taken. In this respect, the QoS of the slices with guaranteed bandwidth and low latency must be fulfilled.	
Executed by	Partner: ORO	Date: July 2023
Purpose	Pass/fail scenario 1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pass if within KPIs 	
Scenario	MDCE03: Load test for observing the QoS prioritization among slices with congestion on radio part	
Slice Configuration	eMBB slice URLLC slice	
Components involved	Two laptops/tablets, Two slices configured over 5G network: URLCC, eMBB	
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	<p>Two tests are performed on the 2 slices (eMBB and URLCC) simultaneously (one test/slice).</p> <p>For eMBB the traffic flow is configured with a bandwidth of 20Mbps.</p> <p>The tests are repeated three times, resulting in a total number of 6 tests.</p> <p>eMBB DL/UL: 20/20Mbps eMBB RTT: 25ms URLLC DL/UL: 10/10Mbps URLLC RTT: 5ms Jitter: 0.04 ms</p>	

Tools involved	Iperf3, oss
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	Slices configuration and performance during the tests UL/DL performance and QoS assurance between slices
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	passed

Table 6-17 Test Case Experiment MDCE04

Field	Stability test over consecutive days
Test Case ID	MDCE04
Facility, Site	FR/RO cluster
Description	Being a UC in the public safety and security area, the availability and the stability of the services are very important. The following test-case measures the performance of the E2E connectivity over one slice for a period of seven days. The interactive slice was chosen to be tested in order to check also the connectivity via Wi-Fi AP. The expected result is to have network availability over 99.9% and latency lower than 30 ms.
Executed by	Partner: ORO Date: June 2022
Purpose	Pass/fail scenario: Pass if within KPIs Fail if outside KPIs
Scenario	MDCE04 : Stability test - injecting traffic over one
Slice Configuration	slice configured (e.g. eMBB)
Components involved	Laptop Iperf3 server, server connected to eMBB slice
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	UL/DL performance: min 20/20 Mbps max 25/22 Mbps Connectivity time:4h of testing
Tools involved	Iperf3, oss
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	UL/DL min 22/21Mbps max 25/23Mbps Connectivity time
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	pass

Table 6-18 Test Case Experiment MDCE04

Field	AI emergency identification and alerting
Test Case ID	MDAe01 – MDAe04
Facility, Site	FR/RO cluster

Description	track passengers as they enter and leave the bus. We also track carried baggage that we link to the passenger's body pose when entering. If the baggage stays on board while the passenger (to whom it has been linked) leaves we trigger an alert.
Executed by	Partner: ORO Date: Sept 2023
Purpose	Pass/fail scenario: Pass if within KPIs Fail if outside KPIs
Scenario	MD Ae01: Passenger fall detection in an emergency break MD Ae04: Lost item – detection and alerting
Slice Configuration	URLLC slice Min 10 Mbits/s connection for the camera video streaming with maximum 20 ms latency
Components involved	RGB camera. GPU compute capability in the Edge node. People pose detection code for the parallel AI network execution AI app's Edge
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Monitoring frequency is 10-15 times per second
Tools involved	EDGE Analytics
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	the automatic detections against the ground truth data
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	passed

```

[ 4] 78.00-79.01 sec 2.96 MBytes 24.7 Mbits/sec 2372
[ 6] 78.00-79.01 sec 2.96 MBytes 24.7 Mbits/sec 2372
[ 8] 78.00-79.01 sec 2.96 MBytes 24.7 Mbits/sec 2372
[10] 78.00-79.01 sec 2.96 MBytes 24.7 Mbits/sec 2372
[SUM] 78.00-79.01 sec 11.9 MBytes 98.9 Mbits/sec 9488
    
```

Figure 6-15 FR/RO cluster eMBB test results

```

 4] 13512.00-13513.01 sec 243 KBytes 1.98 Mbits/sec 190
 6] 13512.00-13513.01 sec 243 KBytes 1.98 Mbits/sec 190
 8] 13512.00-13513.01 sec 243 KBytes 1.98 Mbits/sec 190
10] 13512.00-13513.01 sec 243 KBytes 1.98 Mbits/sec 190
12] 13512.00-13513.01 sec 243 KBytes 1.98 Mbits/sec 190
SUM] 13512.00-13513.01 sec 1.19 MBytes 9.91 Mbits/sec 950
    
```

Figure 6-16 FR/RO cluster URLLC test results

6.2.4 Conclusions – Lessons learned

In FR/RO cluster the **UC #1.2** requirements have been achieved based on the solution described and implemented, as highlighted in Table 6-19.

Table 6-19 FR/RO cluster UC #1.2 results evaluation

Test Case	Result
MDIe01 User authentication using captive portal	<p>Single user network slice, 5G SA, Radio BW 50MHz in N78</p> <p><u>Results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DL: 112 Mbps UL: 30 Mbps RTT external server (8.8.8.8) 40 ms RTT internal server (edge computing) 20 ms
MDIe01 Passed/Failed	Passed
MDIe02 Captive portal data availability	<p>eMBB slice is enabled in the network</p> <p><u>Results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> www.gsp.ro Browsing time (latency) – time to display the requested information <3s; Service availability>99% tcpdump ~ 1.8s
MDIe02 Passed/Failed	passed
MDCe01 Establishment of basic E2E connectivity over a specific slice	<p><u>Results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ping towards DNS 8.8.8.8 ~40 ms Ping towards internal DNS(ORO) ~ 28ms Ping towards EDGE C&C (through ORO) ~ 29ms
MDCe01 Captive portal data availability	passed
MDCe02 Establishment of advanced E2E connectivity over two different slices with	<p><u>Results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Network slice capabilities/management (Yes/No);

<p><i>different QoS metrics configured</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The two network slices are manually configured (eMBB/Low Latency) ● E2E latency for interactive service (in ms) < 30ms; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ~28ms ● E2E latency for public safety service (in ms) < 5ms; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ~5 ms ● High bandwidth required for data intensive public safety applications and HD video streaming > 20Mbps; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Test performed in the N78 50MHz context ○ 100Mbps DL throughput ● Jitter for URLLC < 1ms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ < 0.070
<p>MDCe02 Passed/Failed</p>	<p><u>passed</u></p>
<p><i>MDCe03 Load test for observing the QoS prioritization among slices with congestion on radio part</i></p>	<p><u>Results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Slices configured ● E2E latency for interactive service (in ms) < 30 ms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ~28 ms ● E2E latency for public safety service (in ms) < 5 ms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ~ 12 ms ● High bandwidth required for data intensive public safety applications and HD video streaming > 10 Mbps <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 20 Mbps ● Jitter for URLLC < 1 ms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ~0.05 – 0.5 ms <p><u>Comment:</u> proper optimization resource allocation will be performed in LAB condition</p>
<p>MDCe03 passed/failed</p>	<p><u>passed</u></p>
<p><i>MDCe04 Stability test - injecting traffic over one slice for 3 consecutive days</i></p>	<p><u>Results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Network availability reached highly traffic load ● E2E latency for interactive service (in ms) < 27ms;
<p>MDCe03 passed/failed</p>	<p><u>Passed (3 field testing days)</u></p>
<p><i>MDAe01-MDAe04 (for all AI recognition and identification of emergency situation test-cases)</i></p>	<p><u>Results</u> (measurements performed from the device level):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 40Mbps DL/20Mbps UL, ● RTT ~5ms
<p>MDAe01-MDAe04</p>	<p><u>Passed</u></p>

The tests for **UC #1.2** were successfully conducted and results were collected through the demonstration activities. The operation of the mobility management service was validated successfully, as it was able to preserve the connections across the same/cross-technology networks. The mobility scenarios supported by the infrastructure design allows municipalities to run infotainment and safety services without any conflict between them, by the suitable slice implementation; by exploiting the emergency situation in the bus, view of the network and appropriate monitoring, through the 5G network the required vertical services has been delivered as required, to the C&C Center, situated in **AIM**. It is worth mentioning that the 5G-VICTORI deployment in Alba-Iulia is one of the first 5G SA OpenRAN/Open Core implementations in operational environments, demonstrating the maturity of the technology at this moment and business potential that can rise on top of this open implementations.

6.2.5 Vertical business KPI validation (AIM / ORO)

We have demonstrated an E2E 5G SA network and implementation of a set of services in AIM, a successful Open RAN/Open Core 5G SA in a live environment running on top of the infrastructure, the real Municipality UC #1.2, providing one of the first real life deployments of open-source 5G network (O-RAN and Core). 5G slicing has been implemented, multi-slices are available and have been validated supporting different applications and UCs with different requirements (eMBB or ultra-low-latency).

The results of the trials validate the potential of 5G and the potential of the implementation new business cases for commercial scope. From the Vertical's business perspective, the analysis and the validation is performed for the various UC #1.2 Applications:

- **App1: Infotainment/ video services in dense, static and mobile environment.** This Application was implemented successfully and achieved the targeted network KPIs, as presented, supporting the business case validation for basic infotainment and video services in dense environments. Through 5G slice creation, the municipality easily extends the application KPIs at the City area, offering services to bus passengers. Following the implementation, a simple UC is implemented at the community level.
- **App2: AI recognition and identification of emergency situation.** The Application is network demanding in terms of resources, and computational resources as well as usage of 5G network for traffic prioritization and resource reservation and was achieved through the implementation of network slice. The vertical KPIs and validation of this App is evaluated from the safety and passenger's security perspective in the buses. The business owner is in this case the Municipality, providing in real-time the status related to emergency situations in public transportation services and improves the transportation experience and service quality to travellers, supported by AI recognition of emergency situation.
- **App3:** Prioritised communication to command and control center. The Application supports the App2 functionality, dynamic network slice implementation and traffic prioritization.

6.3 UC #4.2 Low Voltage Energy Metering

UC #4.2 focuses on real time Low Voltage (LV) Energy metering and comprises the following applications: Real-time LV energy metering services for designated points of interests and Energy Analytics for predictive and proactive maintenance. The required information is transmitted over 5G dedicated slices assuring real time management, E2E orchestration and QoS control, as seen in Figure 6-17.

Figure 6-17 FR/RO cluster UC #4.2 service mapping

UC components, as described in Figure 6-18:

- IoT end device: the IoT metering device, connected to the IoT Telemetry analytics server, acting as aggregating component, the communication component is provided over the Low Latency PDN slice.
- 5G NSA/SA Network: installed in Orange 5G site, as RRH/BBU, vEPC/5GCN core network components, network interfaces and local processing servers.
- Telemetry platform: installed in cloud, acting as Telemetry Data Aggregator, Telemetry Database, Telemetry Application and engines and telemetry data storage, connected through N6/SGi interface to the IoT devices.

Figure 6-18 UC #4.2 components

6.3.1 Field trial description

One network slice has been configured in the 5G SA network. The DNN is connected to the EDGE computing for analytics. The network slice is configured in the network based on 5QI and QoS parameters.

Figure 6-19 FR/RO UC #4.2 deployment in AIM

Figure 6-20 FR/RO cluster IoT platform integration

The field implementation of LV metering and Energy analytics (see Figure 6-19) provides several KPIs, as LV energy metering services for the AIM infrastructure, energy analytics for predictive and proactive maintenance for the AIM LV infrastructure and metering data collection from endpoints. In this context, the Novelties and key innovations include the 5G Service deployment for 5G RAN and Core (5G SA), the common Core, the 5G service provisioning to the users, service slice creation and UEs association to proper slice, the RAN agent application that auto-associates Ues to slices based on NSSAI. The 5G network deployment and instantiation, service slices creation and UEs association to slices and service slice performance assurance (Bandwidth/Latency) are performed. An example of IoT devices mapping is highlighted in Figure 6-20, the IoT platform integration and LV metering devices retrieved in the platform.

6.3.2 Experiment and scenario descriptions

The next tables present UC #4.2 experiment description for the different services, supported in this IoT specific environment by the already defined Energy Metering Test Cases, as in Table 6-20 and for Energy Analytics as in Table 6-21.

Table 6-20 FR/RO Cluster UC#4.2 test cases (1)

Test case group ESM (Energy Metering)			
Test case name	Place	Key Use-case requirements and KPIs	Network performance requirements and KPIs
ESMe01	FR/RO AIM	E2E connectivity over smart energy slice	E2E Latency < 100ms mMTC packet size < 20kB

			Service Availability > 99.9%
ESMe02	FR/RO AIM	advanced E2E connectivity over smart energy slice with different QoS metrics configured	E2E Latency < 100ms mMTC packet size < 20kB Service Availability > 99.9%
ESMe03	FR/RO AIM	traffic generated simultaneously by 3000 LV metering devices	E2E Latency < 100ms mMTC packet size < 20kB Service Availability > 99.9%
ESMe04	FR/RO AIM	dynamic resource allocation 5G capability against service stability	E2E Latency < 100ms mMTC packet size < 20kB Service Availability > 99.9%

Table 6-21 UC#4.2 test cases (2)

Test case group ESA (Energy Analytics)			
Test case name	Place	Key Use-case requirements and KPIs	Network performance requirements and KPIs
ESAE01	FR/RO AIM	energy consumption monitoring accuracy	E2E slice connectivity
ESAE02	FR/RO AIM	Preventive maintenance	E2E slice connectivity

Table 6-22 Scenario Description

Scenario Description Template – field	
Radio access technology (RAT)	5G-NR
Standalone / Non-Standalone (if applicable)	SA
Cell Power	40 W
Frequency band:	N78
Maximum bandwidth per component carrier	50 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	30 KHz
Cyclic Prefix	Normal
Massive MIMO	2x2 MIMO
Duplex mode	TDD
TDD uplink/downlink pattern	8:1
User location and speed	100 Mbps / 30 km/h
Background traffic	N/A
Computational resources available	112 CPU cores, 1TB RAM, 4TB storage

6.3.3 Test Cases and KPIs tables

In FR/RO cluster the **UC #4.2** requirements have been achieved based on the solution described and implemented, as highlighted in the following tables

Table 6-23 Experiment 1

Description	
ExperimentType	E2E connectivity over mMTC slice
Automated	Manual
TestCases	ESMe01
UEs	mMTC sensor
Network Slice	NSD IDs mMTC (SST=1 for particular IoT scenario)
Network Services	Low bandwidthIoT
Network Scenario	validate the e2e slice connectivity between different components/facilities involved: low voltage metering device - 5G IoT device - 5G radio access - 5G core networks
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	UC #4.2 LC IOT Slice
Performance targets & SLAs	E2E connectivity over the mMTC (100kbps/device)
Experiment Parameters	Raw data packets are sent toward Telemetry platform
Edges	Telemetry platform
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 6-24 Experiment 2

Description	
ExperimentType	Advanced E2E connectivity over mMTC slice with different QoS metrics
Automated	Manual
TestCases	ESMe02
UEs	mMTC sensor
Network Slice	NSD IDs mMTC (SST=1 for particular IoT scenario)
Network Services	Low bandwidthIoT
Network Scenario	QoS performance of the smart energy network slice
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	UC #4.2 LC IOT Slice
Performance targets & SLAs	E2E connectivity over the mMTC (100kbps/device)
Experiment Parameters	Raw data packets are sent toward Telemetry platform Service Availability > 99.9% E2E latency for smart metering service < 100 ms Packet loss rate < 0.01%
Edges	Telemetry platform LV sensor simulator

Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 6-25 Experiment 3

	Description
ExperimentType	establishment of simultaneous 5G raw data transfer to process the traffic generated simultaneously by 3000 LV metering devices over Alba-Iulia
Automated	Manual
TestCases	ESMe03
UEs	mMTC sensor
Network Slice	NSD IDs mMTC (SST=1 for particular IoT scenario)
Network Services	Low bandwidth IoT(3000 devices)
Network Scenario	QoS performance of the smart energy network slice
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	UC #4.2 LC IOT Slice
Performance targets & SLAs	E2E connectivity over the mMTC (100kbps/device) Raw data received successfully by the Telemetry platform from all 3000 simulated devices
Experiment Parameters	data rates capacity for simultaneously transfers of large raw data volumes of LV metering devices
Edges	Telemetry platform LV sensor simulator
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 6-26 Experiment 4

	Description
ExperimentType	one slice for mMTC
Automated	Manual
TestCases	ESMe04
UEs	mMTC sensor 3000 5G/ LTE-M IoT
Network Slice	NSD IDs mMTC (SST=1 for particular IoT scenario)
Network Services	Low bandwidth IoT (3000 devices)
Network Scenario	transfer capacity volume of aggregated information for all 3 slices RTT; UL/DL per slice
Exclusive Execution	N/A

ReservationTime	N/A
Application	UC #4.2 LC IOT Slice
Performance targets & SLAs	slice performance measurement is performed from network (bandwidth, jitter, latency) and Telemetry (SR%) perspective
Experiment Parameters	data rates capacity for simultaneously transfers of large raw data volumes of LV metering devices
Edges	Telemetry platform LV sensor simulator
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

Table 6-27 Experiments results 5

	Description
ExperimentType	one slice for mMTC
Automated	Manual
TestCases	ESAe01 & ESAe02
UEs	LV metering devices 5G / LTE-M IoT device Telemetry platform
Network Slice	NSD IDs mMTC (SST=1 for particular IoT scenario)
Network Services	Low bandwidth IoT (3000 devices)
Network Scenario	detection accuracy & Consumption accuracy %
Exclusive Execution	N/A
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	UC #4.2 LC IOT Slice
Performance targets & SLAs	slice performance measurement is performed from network (bandwidth, jitter, latency) and Telemetry (SR%) perspective
Experiment Parameters	data rates capacity for simultaneously transfers of large raw data volumes of LV metering devices
Edges	Telemetry platform LV sensor simulator
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	N/A
Extra	N/A

The E2E functionality and validation of the **UC #4.2** is demonstrated by the IoT sensors functionality, as they are seen in the Edge Platform, seen in Figure 6-21 and Figure 6-22.

Figure 6-21 FR/RO UC #4.2 Cluster IoT platform for LV

Figure 6-22 FR/RO UC #4.2 Cluster LV analytics

Parameters Used from Sensor Lovato - DMG110

Remove all paramet

Channel	Unit	Name	Type	Multiplier	Hex	Last Value	Last Msg. UTC	Conn.
2	V	Voltage L1N	Voltage L1N	0.01	-	240.29	09/05/2021 21:56:05	
4	V	Voltage L2N	Voltage L2N	0.01	-	237.91	09/05/2021 21:56:05	
6	V	Voltage L3N	Voltage L3N	0.01	-	239.73	09/05/2021 21:56:05	
8	A	Current L1	Current L1	0.0001	-	3.245	09/05/2021 21:56:05	
10	A	Current L2	Current L2	0.0001	-	2.78	09/05/2021 21:56:11	

Figure 6-23 FR/RO UC #4.2 Cluster LV consumption accuracy (%)

6.3.4 Conclusions – Lessons learned

The tests for UC #4.2 were successfully conducted and results were collected through the demonstrations. The services were validated successfully, as it was possible to preserve connections across the same/cross-technology networks. The scenarios supported by the infrastructure design allowed municipalities to run LV real-time measurements services, through suitable slice implementation. The required vertical services has been appropriately delivered by exploiting LV measurements in the municipality having a view of the network and supporting LV monitoring through the 5G network. It is worth mentioning that the 5G-VICTORI deployment in Alba-Iulia is one of the first 5G SA OpenRAN/Open Core implementations in operational environments, demonstrating the maturity of the technology at this moment and business potential that can rise on top of this open implementations.

Table 6-28 FR/RO cluster UC #4.2 results and KPIs

	Value	Comments
Experiment Type	Standard	
Automated	Manual	
Test Cases	Test Case LV	
UEs	mMTC-LV1; mMTC-LV2	mMTC/LTE-M devices
Network Slice	mMTC QCI 9 slice	3GPP Rel.16
Network Services	NSD IDs: mMTC	N/A
Network Scenario	Scenario #4.2	
Exclusive Execution	True	
ReservationTime	N/A	
Experiment Name	UC#4.2_App1	
Performance targets & SLAs	E2E latency 100 ms mMTC packet size 20kB Service availability	Network KPIs ESMe01-04 Apps KPIs: Energy monitoring & performance identification Apps KPIs: ESAe01-02
Experiment Parameters	Resources: Application vCPU Core:min 2max 4, RAM: min:4GB, max: 8GB link_capacity(Mbps):	

	min: 40 max: 40	
Edges	HPE Gen10 K8s 5G SA EDGE Apps Thingboard Platform	VLANs: 103 DNN eMTC slice
Remote	N/A	
Remote Descriptor	N/A	
Version	v1.0	
Extra	N/A	

The KPIs described have been achieved in the setup described within the 5G/LTE-M network capability, using a limited number of physical devices and extending the functionality with an IoT simulator developed by Orange.

6.3.5 Vertical business KPI validation

The 5G technical context is as described in section 6.2.5, 5G SA services facilitated by the network implementation in AIM. The energy is a hot topic for cities municipalities, as the UC #4.2 is providing in this case a set of reach capabilities with a strong impact for the Cities in terms of LV services functionalities and in detail analysis of the services:

- **App1:** Real-time LV energy metering services for designated points of interests.
- **App2:** Energy Analytics for predictive and proactive maintenance for designated points of interest.

The Municipalities are able to monitor LV data as well as perform collection from endpoints and they have the real time status of energy consumption in different points. This allows them to evaluate the consumption and predict further characteristics. In this context AI energy analytics can help predict the behaviour and enable pro-active implementation of LV network maintenance, fully satisfying relevant business needs.

6.4 Conclusions – FR/RO

The tests and experiments performed in FR/RO facility have been implemented in both laboratory and Field environment:

- **UC #1.2:** Digital Mobility Services Alba Iulia
- **UC #4.2:** LV Energy metering

The final 5G SA network deployment and UCs configuration have been validated in AIM, with the support of the local partners, for both UCs, achieving several key milestones:

- 5G SA option 2 implementations (RAN/Core) using an open source platform (OAI).
- 5G SA Network: installed in Orange 5G site, as RRH/BBU, 5GCN core network components, network interfaces and local processing servers
- Slice and service configuration, different network slices and DNN configuration to the EDGE.
- 5G network deployment and instantiation
- Service slices creation and UEs association to slices
- Service slice performance (Bandwidth/Latency)
- Traffic prioritization
- UCs running in an operational environment, for Media and Energy, demonstrated in real scenarios.

Test Case	Result
MDIe01 User authentication using captive portal	<p>Single user network slice, 5G SA, Radio BW 50MHz in N78</p> <p><u>Results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DL: 110 Mbps UL: 30 Mbps RTT external server (8.8.8.8) 40 ms RTT internal server (edge computing) 20 ms
MDIe01 Passed/Failed	<i>Passed</i>
MDIe02 Captive portal data availability	<p>eMBB slice is enabled in the network</p> <p><u>Results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> www.gsp.ro Browsing time (latency) – time to display the requested information <3s; Service availability>99% tcpdump ~ 1.8s
MDIe02 Passed/Failed	<i>passed</i>
MDCe01 Establishment of basic E2E connectivity over a specific slice	<p><u>Results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ping towards DNS 8.8.8.8 ~40 ms Ping towards internal DNS(ORO) ~ 28ms Ping towards EDGE C&C (through ORO) ~ 29ms
MDCe01 Captive portal data availability	<u>passed</u>
MDCe02 Establishment of advanced E2E connectivity over two different slices with different QoS metrics configured	<p><u>Results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Network slice capabilities/management (Yes/No); <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The two network slices are manually configured (eMBB/Low Latency) E2E latency for interactive service (in ms) < 30 ms; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~28 ms E2E latency for public safety service (in ms) < 5 ms; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~5 ms High bandwidth required for data intensive public safety applications and HD video streaming > 20 Mbps; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Test performed in the N78 50MHz context 100 Mbps DL throughput Jitter for URLLC < 1 ms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> < 0.070
MDCe02 Passed/Failed	<u>passed</u>
MDCe03 Load test for observing the QoS prioritization among slices with congestion on radio part	<p><u>Results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slices configured E2E latency for interactive service (in ms) < 30 ms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~28 ms E2E latency for public safety service (in ms) < 5 ms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~ 12 ms High bandwidth required for data intensive public safety applications and HD video streaming > 10 Mbps <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 20 Mbps

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Jitter for URLLC < 1 ms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~0.05 – 0.5 ms <p><u>Comment:</u> proper optimization resource allocation will be performed in LAB condition</p>
MDCe03 passed/failed	<u>passed</u>
MDCe04 <i>Stability test - injecting traffic over one slice for 3 consecutive days</i>	<p><u>Results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Network availability reached highly traffic load E2E latency for interactive service (in ms) < 27 ms;
MDCe03 passed/failed	<u>Passed (3 field testing days)</u>
MDAe01-MDAe04 (for all AI recognition and identification of emergency situation test-cases)	<p><u>Results</u> (measurements performed from the device level):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 40 Mbps DL / 20 Mbps UL, RTT ~5 ms
MDAe01-MDAe04	<u>Passed</u>

The **FR/RO** cluster and its deployment in **AIM** has validated the performance and the functionality of the implemented UC scenarios, highlighting the LV results for energy metering, pro-active management and automatic alarming system in case of issues.

7 Inter-cluster Field Trials

Two inter-cluster UCs are described in this section, referred to as **MATI App2 Patras-Bristol UC** and **UHA Future Mobility App3 Berlin-Bristol UC**. A sketch of the connectivity for the inter-cluster UCs is shown in Figure 7-1. The deployment and inter-domain connection of the network services to be consumed by the users of each UC relied on 5G-VIOS, as it is discussed in the next subsection.

Figure 7-1 5G-VICTORI inter-cluster UCs

7.1 Role of 5G-VIOS

As for every deployment of 5G-VIOS, the first step is to register the facilities as Edges in the 5G-VIOS Platform. Then, in each of the facility domains, the MANO platform (in this case OSM) needs to be updated with the latest NS and VNF descriptors as part of the NS registry of each domain. Apart from access to the MANO platform, the Edge Proxy of 5G-VIOS also needs to be able to access the cloud management platform but only for the purpose of creating the appropriate VLAN the network service will be attached based on the already created VLANs by the Inter-domain Connectivity Manager (ICM) – when applicable.

To facilitate inter-domain connectivity for deploying the transport network used by the network services, the VyOS virtual router plays a key role allowing the use of DMVPN for flexible and secure inter-connection of each edge over the Internet as well as the discovery and connectivity of hosts within the different VLANs using OSPF. DMVPN relies on the hub and spoke paradigm and, therefore, for each UC the Edge hosting the 5G-VIOS Platform also hosted the VyOS Hub while the Edge facilities hosted the VyOS Spokes. All VyOS routers are configured automatically by 5G-VIOS during deployment of the experiment.

The user of 5G-VIOS can then provide the required experiment descriptor that includes core information such as the desired deployment of network services in each facility in order for 5G-VIOS to deploy the desired inter-domain network service (see example in Figure 7-2).

Figure 7-2 5G-VIOS experiment life cycle

7.2 App2 Bristol – Patras (MATI App2 360° VR Live stream UC)

During June’s final demo, a 360° VR Live stream was delivered, focusing on large scale user connectivity, greater number of users and high bitrate videos. MATI’s inter-cluster proposed application involved a 360° VR Live stream from University of Bristol (UNIVBRIS), using capabilities of MATI, and 5G-UK test network. The users could see the stream from anywhere in Bristol, with access to the 5G-UK test network, and within areas of Patras University, with access to the UoP network; and access the stream via VR in real-time with low latency. Selected locations were:

- UNIVBRIS (Smart Internet Lab) in Bristol.
- M Shed / Nomadic node in Bristol.
- UoP.

The novelties related to this inter-cluster UC are as follows:

- Accessing the 360° VR Live stream from more than one cluster.
- Content caching at the edge (existing at the corresponding cluster) close to the end user.
- Network traffic reduction to backhaul server as devices fetch cached content from the edge.

7.2.1 Field trial description

Patras’ cluster was deployed as an additional ‘inter-cluster’ edge (through 5G-VIOS) for App2. Figure 7-3 shows the inter-cluster connectivity between Patras and Bristol clusters through a secured tunnel. The inter-cluster connectivity was implemented using secure gateways at each cluster, which are integrated to the Edge Proxies in Patras edge as well as the 5G-VIOS in Bristol. By doing so, the 5G-VIOS is capable of enabling App2 in Patras edge by instantiating the corresponding edge caching servers and bringing the App2 services to life within the edge.

Figure 7-3 Bristol-Patras inter-cluster communication through Open VPN

7.2.2 Experiment and scenario descriptions

The next tables present the inter-cluster experiment description for the different services.

Table 7-1 Experiment 1 (DCAT)

	Value
ExperimentType	Standard
Automated	True
TestCases	Test Case 2
UEs	UE1, UE2
Network Slice	Mativision_App2_streamingserver Mativision_App2_cacheserver
Network Services	NSD IDs: 5867207d-c4a7-4c88-bb8c-9fd2479d0c89, 3ac5d3de-81f3-45d2-b2f8-1b49cf9d3061
Network Scenario	Scenario 1
Exclusive Execution	True
ReservationTime	N/A
Application	Mativision_App2
Performance targets & SLAs	Network Service KPIs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> cpu_utilisation: 0.98, memory_utilisation: 100 Application KPIs: Bandwidth: 300000
Experiment Parameters	Minimum and Maximum configuration of Resources: cpu: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min_cores: 2, max_cores: 8

	memory: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min: 200, max: 1000 link_capacity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min: 400000000, max: 1400000000
Edges	
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	
Extra	

Table 7-2 Experiment 2 (DCAT)

	Description
ExperimentType	Standard
Automated	True
TestCases	TestCase 2
UEs	UE1, UE2
Network Slice	UoB_Patras_Mativision_App2
Network Services	NSD ID: "b9ec2dfe-a159-4402-b705-18eff2bcc426,e0c1bc3b-5bae-49f7-8b05-c8a6025d532c,patras"
Network Scenario	Scenario 2
Exclusive Execution	True
Reservation Time	N/A
Application	Mativision_App2_UoB_Patras
Performance targets & SLAs	Network Service KPIs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> cpu_utilisation: 0.98, memory_utilisation: 100 Application KPIs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mobility Latency: 300000 MIR : 200
Experiment Parameters	Minimum and Maximum configuration of Resources: <p>cpu:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min_cores: 2, max_cores: 8 <p>memory:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min: 2000, max: 10000 <p>link_capacity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> min: 400000000, max: 1400000000
Edges	VLAN200 (Patras), VLAN147 (Univbris)
Remote	N/A
Remote Descriptor	N/A
Version	
Extra	

Please refer to Table 5-5 for detailed scenario description of corresponding edges in Bristol.

7.2.3 Test Cases and KPIs tables

The KPIs related to this inter-cluster UC are as following:

- BW >10 Mbps per user
- Latency <60 s
- Network savings >30%

Table 7-3 Ping Tests between the VMs deployed in the Bristol-Patras clusters

Ping Direction	Measurements
From Patras Cache Server to UNIVBRIS Streaming server	1000 packets transmitted, 1000 received, 0% packet loss, time 1000437 ms rtt min/avg/max/mdev = 58.156/60.513/71.386/1.321 ms
From UNIVBRIS Streaming server to Patras Cache Server	1000 packets transmitted, 1000 received, 0% packet loss, time 1000415 ms rtt min/avg/max/mdev = 58.007/60.523/72.160/1.369 ms

Table 7-4 iPerf tests between the VMs deployed in the Bristol-Patras clusters

Server/Client	Measurements
Statistics from Patras iperf server (192.168.200.14)	0.00-1000.06 sec 2.07 GBytes 17.8 Mbits/sec receiver
Statistics from UNIVBRIS iperf client (192.168.147.23)	0.00-1000.00 sec 2.07 GBytes 17.8 Mbits/sec 4068 sender
	0.00-1000.06 sec 2.07 GBytes 17.8 Mbits/sec receiver

Table 7-5 5G-VIOS experiment deployment across multiple facilities test case

Field	5G-VIOS experiment deployment across multiple facilities	
Test Case ID	RDNu06	
Facility, Site	Bristol cluster, 5G-VINNI Patras	
Description	This test deploys an experiment to the testbed of Bristol and Patras. During this filed trial, an experiment with two network services will be deployed to the multiple inter-facilities edges.	
Executed by	Partner: DCAT	Date:
Purpose	All the resources belonging to the experiment are deployed and configured within 90 mins.	
Scenario	Refer to the right scenario template used for the test (see Table 5-5)	
Slice Configuration		
Components involved	Components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OpenStack - OSM 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - K8s cluster - 5G-VIOS platform. <p>Configurations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Edge proxy is deployed at each edge. - Edge is registered with 5G-VIOS - API Gateway, OSM, NetOS, profiler, and monitoring platform are configured with edge proxy. - OpenStack is registered with OSM.
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	
Tools involved	
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	<p>All the resources belonging to the experiment are deployed to the expected infrastructure.</p> <p>Pass/Fail results:</p> <p>Pass: If the experiment deployed correctly within the 90 mins threshold.</p> <p>Fail: If the experiment is not deployed correctly within 90 mins.</p>

Figure 7-4 and Figure 7-5 show the end-to-end test results (latency and throughput, respectively) between VMs in Bristol and Patras using OpenVPN over Internet. The latency was measured by ping over 10 minutes and the throughput was measured using Iperf3 for 5 minutes each round.

Figure 7-4 End-to-End Latency (ms) Bristol to Patras

Figure 7-5 DL/UL Throughput benchmark – Bristol to Patras

7.2.4 Conclusions – Lessons learned

During designing the inter-cluster communication as well as the demonstration we faced challenges such as:

- Setting up the network connection between two clusters’ testbeds (VPN protocols, internal policies, IP/VLAN availability/loops, security concerns, etc.).
- Coordination among partners to implement the inter-cluster UC demos.

Also, the 5G-VIOS faced some risks and challenges on orchestrating inter-cluster NSs, including:

- NS image version control available across clusters.
- Stability of the inter-cluster connectivity when deploying NS.

7.2.5 Vertical business KPI validation

The inter-cluster task is a logical extension of the business idea behind the Multicamera Live streaming at **UNIVBRIS** campus, adding to the **UNIVBRIS** campus (in Bristol, UK) the loop a remote facility, at a remote geographical location, the **UoP** (in Patras, Greece).

The business validation as presented in section 5.3.5 is reflected in the present case as well, with even more relevance, because the COVID-19 Pandemic and its consequent restrictions put even more emphasis in the capability to provide remote training to far geographical locations. As it was mentioned in section 5.3.5, at the present point in time, the deployment and adoption of lower performance platforms has limited the interest in the education market for higher performance Remote Teaching Applications which need 5G to work. Despite this current trend, we believe that there will still be a potential in the market, as soon as the limitations of the current solutions become too restrictive. In parallel to the business and market-focused activities mentioned in 5.3.5, **MATI** will be monitoring the market to identify expected changes in the needs for delivery of high-performance remote training to far geographies, and will attempt to commercialise the developed solution when the market circumstances allow.

7.3 Berlin – Bristol

7.3.1 Field trial description

Due to both, Berlin and Bristol clusters having dynamic (non-static) public IP addresses, the inter-edge connectivity was implemented via an OpenVPN server located in AWS (Frankfurt - location

closest to the middle between the two cities). The OpenVPN server was assigned with a static public IP address, which enables the deployment of a VPN link between the sites.

Figure 7-6 5G-VICTORI Berlin-Bristol Network Connectivity using AWS

Based on earlier work conducted by both the Berlin and Bristol clusters a test would be conducted to establish the ability to move the 5G-VIOS component of the simulation around different edges across the continent, focused on the ability to use different 5G networks, including nomadic, to connect to the 5G-VIOS management system and not only connect to different end user devices, but pause, and move the entire containerised QCOW 2 WebRTC network component and some data, in order to evaluate the viability of moving containerised services across the network (having already shown that switching end points to duplicates of the WebRTC service > Simulation in earlier trials within the Bristol Cluster.

For **UHA** we also needed to demonstrate a series of disruptive events, focused on the simulated passage of an end user undertaking a journey from Berlin > Berlin Central Station > Berlin Airport > Bristol Airport and into the Bristol Public Transport > Hotel change and how a real-time simulation can be used to query at the edge, as well as deliver geo and contextual relevant updates to an end user - including parametric events to trigger mitigation or alternative transport plans.

- Business traveler en-route from Berlin central via Berlin Central Station to Berlin airport then flight to Bristol airport, then journey to hotel.
- Later our traveler plans to attend conference at Bristol University. Through the Insurer's App traveler adds the journey legs and approximate timings.
- This will then allow us to simulate the impact of different events on this journey.
- Being a live unfolding event, no service (Google and others) has detailed data on accessibility around the station, therefore the traveler will manually input his/her observations through the **UHA** front-end interactive map. The simulation (re-routing) will real-time adapt. Serves both as data input interface, and guidance from the traveler's perspective.
- Different train and flight will be taken as the outcome. The journey will be delayed, the guidance and interactive personalised routing will continue over at the Bristol side to make

the disrupted journey as smooth as possible. Optionally Insurer's App can auto e-mail both hotel and conference about late arrival and/or different order of appearance, provided such contact details were input by the traveller.

Figure 7-7 Bristol transport infrastructure. @1m2

Disruption & insurance based events

Riots around Berlin Central Station disrupt most train journeys. Multiple users message our back-end via a simple press of a button inside the front-end App where users' location is sent via the WebRTC data channel.

Events & realtime lookups:

In parallel, train journeys are looked up. Seeing the delays and cancellations the parametric insurance event is triggered. The traveller is guided to the HauptBahnhof business lounge until further notice. Covered by the Insurer. Different routes, walk around the station area will be trialled in accordance with the marked disruption = blocked areas, cordons, police, rioters.

Through the Insurer's App traveller adds the journey legs and approximate timings.

Riots / Protests around Berlin Central Station disrupt most train journeys.

Multiple users message our back-end via a simple press of a button inside the front-end App where users' location is sent via the WebRTC data channel.

In parallel, train journeys are looked up. Seeing the delays and cancellations the parametric insurance event is triggered. The traveller is guided to Berlin Central Station business lounge until further notice. Covered by the Insurer. Different routes, walk around the station area will be trialled in accordance with the marked disruption = blocked areas, cordons, police, rioters

Our service is expected to run inside the Insurer's app as an embedded solution, as well as to feed the Insurer's dataset from our back-end. Messaging, and alerts will be displayed in the Insurer's app, not ours.

Based on feedback from Insurers, providing non-insured products and value add to a customers journey without it being a traditional insured product (financial payout / claim) especially if driven on empirical data or multiple confidences is embedding insurance into innumerable services and likely the future of consumer embedded services. Therefore offering a WebRTC service that can be

located in network location in proximity to a passenger and an edge based simulation in likely areas of incidents - provides a rapid means to deliver an effective service, with minimal latency and mitigate a lot of customer experience challenges faced by transportation companies.

We have worked with our 5G-VICTORI partners to deliver a realtime streaming experience to end user devices on both 5G and legacy networks.

By moving the network component between edges – based on triggered events – we’re able to simulate the data and performance of an end user’s experience and validate the use of 5G edge based systems to drive real-time – sensor and data driven simulations.

The demo would once again be passed from the **UHA** backend (fiber connected) into the Smart Internet Lab or Berlin Cluster Fiber connected networks, where the QCOW2 image containing the WebRTC Stun/Turn server could then be moved around the different edges - and different scenarios and multiple users connect into the simulation via edge based devices / 5G enabled devices.

The relay servers (VM IPs) inside 5G-VIOS have all been added to the list of ICE servers so WebRTC shall be able to hop between when reestablishing peer-to-peer between front-end and back-end.

Figure 7-8 Smartphone view streamed from back-end, debugged in the browser with console logs turned on; riot in blue, planned route in yellow colour

Next to transmitting, we are capturing the metrics as well (in Mysql) every 5 seconds. All of it in the json format that was suggested to us (see screenshot). Since many of the metrics are accumulative the 5 seconds interval is sufficient. Failing connecting between our front-end metrics and the Bristol

central metrics due to CORS policy challenges we still will be able to provide the SQL dump / JSON time series for post processing / importing to the central metric

This would be run in both the terrain engine and the 3D model - as well as a hybrid, allowing for a delay in one to be passed to another in reduced fidelity (ie how an issue in the HBH affects the wider city model).

Berlin Central Station

Orange is the projected pointcloud LiDAR scan onto the OpenStreetmap GIS 1 meter resolution situational awareness map of Berlin.

Blue is the manually marked disruption by the traveller.

Disrupted areas are considered non traversable / un-safe.

Similar semantic or characteristics for other traits such as reduced mobility or temporary changes can be added

Figure 7-9 Back-end simulation rendered in 2D conventional map and 3D views

Calculating solutions

In this case the non-insured product has been triggered, due to acceptance of the delays caused by the protest, based on the inaccessibility of the station from that avenue of approach. The trigger uses the phones location, the planned service and the delay and allows passage on the next service but also allows access to the Berlin Central Station business lounge to wait for the next service.

Solutions to reach the business lounge are calculated real-time as new data comes in.

This permits multiple different queries and simultaneous analyses to be run.

This can be exponentially complex – and factor in different types of user, scenario and even apriori planning by both transport operators and insurance companies.

This offers support for both un-insured and insured products – ie a cash payout vs a remediation / quality of life measure.

In this case the Cellular Automata also references the model to calculate the nearest clear route, and provides a navigation path - that can be accessed or pushed to the end user device.

Figure 7-10 Alternative route using a different station entrance that leads to the business lounge

Realtime WebRTC rendering

As can be seen, this slide demonstrates the ability to stream the live simulation to an end user device and takes them from 3D navigation to 2.5D.

Figure 7-11 Since the complete 3D scan of the station itself exists in the simulation (unlike the surroundings that are just reconstructed based on OpenStreetMap data) from station entrance till the business lounge the route planning happens in 3D. Left: voxelised station entrance with escalators; Right: same entrance with walkable surfaces / floors autoclassified in real-time.

This brings their access to data into real-time responsiveness – providing the ability to query and modify data layers via an end mobile device.

By design as the service must be embedded into insurance applications and other tools – this has to be lightweight and exploits 5G and WebRTC to deliver cutting edge situational awareness and planning without burdening end user devices.

Simplifying the end user deliverable

For reasons ranging from user experience, to reducing latency and good UX, a new path is calculated based on real-time data and feedback, algorithms and even safety / security or human input into the simulation.

The key point is to deliver the optimum solution rather than just the fastest solution and where local regulations, privacy and optin has been granted - can tailor the pathfinding and planning to the end user's preferences. This also becomes advantageous when considering serving groups, multiple end users and for caching and serving solutions that aren't all real time - but to the end user they are - as well as providing a means to scale the value add from an edge based solution into both local, cloud or other edge based services, business logic and tools.

In the insurance application for instance, there would need to be some handover and exchange of corroborating data (e.g take a photo, enable GPS / WI-Fi, etc.) in order to counter fraud and pass the necessary parametric confidences to trigger an insured event and the policies it affords.

Using 5G access points in localized environments - where GPS or other voluntary fingerprinting of location is provided - could also provide additional proofs to drive the insured action and mitigation.

Figure 7-12 New path calculation

At this point the passenger has moved to through the crowd and the Berlin Central Station disruption and has been able to board their train, and arrives at Berlin Airport.

Our passenger has eventually made it to Berlin Airport – and taken a flight to Bristol.

At this point the passenger is handed over from the Berlin edge to the Bristol Edge – allowing access to local processing and and sensor data.

The network component that routes this – can also be hopped around Edges (e.g. 5G-VIOS) to optimise the performance and delivery of real-time simulation.

Figure 7-13 Bristol airport and surroundings in Polaron; terminal building in the center (no 3D scan available for this facility but as a concept a similar 3D route planning shall happen from terminal to bus stop once a full scan of the terminal building may be taken)

This can also contain data (assuming it meets privacy and data laws, allowing the profile and network component to be added over between extra national edges - essentially dedicated to fulfilling the functions of a given group of passengers (e.g. Every passenger on the flight from Berlin Airport > Bristol Airport). This provides a means to also handover an entire edge or keep it with the passengers (e.g. between a station and onboard moving train edge).

This allows for portions of simulation or services to “hug” the end user - reducing latency and optimizing a service to their needs or be available at the next nearest Edge (e.g. Berlin > Bristol).

Our passenger has eventually made it to Berlin Airport – and taken a flight to Bristol.

Figure 7-14 Bristol central in Polaron

Having boarded a bus – our passenger can now query and navigate this unfamiliar city and carry their preferences and profile – into the localised simulation.

Since these can be generic (typically 23 passenger profile types) – and anonymised – there is a low GDPR risk and high privacy component - whilst still providing a useful service - and this has been seen as offering an attractive means to augment passenger information and journey planning - without compromising safety and security - as the simulation doesn't “know” the individual - merely the profile of the user's preferences in journeys or accessibility.

Whilst we undertook a lot of work to prepare for this intercluster demo, ultimately technical challenges prevented it from being run. We did however take on a lot of data and are confident that the 5G-Vios / WebRTC component would have delivered similar performance to other tests.

Figure 7-15 Logs of all WebRTC metrics from all users from the field trial @5 second intervals

7.3.2 Test Cases and KPIs tables

The next tables present the inter-cluster Berlin-Bristol etest cases and results.

RDNu02	5GUK Infrastructure test case Between Core (HPN) and the Nomadic Node (field test)
Testbed	5G-UK Bristol
Description	Test the performance of dedicated 5G network and compute resources to the 5G-VICTORI project such as latency, and throughput between the core and Nomadic node.
Key Use-case requirements and KPIs	Latency, Uplink and Downlink capacity between dummy compute nodes in core and edges as well as between the edges.
Network performance requirements and KPIs	<100 ms latency >100 Mbps uplink and downlink throughput
Network Functional requirements and KPIs	It is required to instantiate dummy VMs on corresponding compute resources before starting the test.
Components and configuration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Components: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dummy VMs on both core and edge compute resources 2. Core and MEC servers 3. Nomadic Node - Configuration: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Network slice deployment

Test procedure	<p>- Preconditions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Confirm that the corresponding edges are configured and all Edge components such as the Edge Orchestrator, VIMs and WIMs are up and running. 2. Confirm that the corresponding edges are registered to the 5G-VIOS. <p>- Test Case Steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run a network service comprising 2 VNFs. One in the core, and one in Nomadic Node edge servers with the same required resources as the use case application requirements. 2. Create a network Slice between these 2 nodes 3. Start Monitoring and KPI measurement using the 5GUK monitoring and measurement tool 4. Extract the result and make the report to validate the KPIs
Measurements	<p>- Methodology</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Generate the traffic 2. Monitor the corresponding metrics 3. Measure the KPIs 4. Create and record the network performance profiles 5. Generate the Pass/Fail test results 6. Expose the results to the authenticated users. <p>- Complementary measurements</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. N/A <p>- Calculation process</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Compute the throughput by dividing the amount of received data by the time taken to transmit data from sender to receiver and convert to (Mbps) 2. Measure Round Trip Time (RTT) using corresponding monitoring tools such as Ping

Table 7-6 5G-VIOS experiment deployment across multiple facilities test case

Field	5G-VIOS experiment deployment across multiple facilities
Test Case ID	RDNu06
Facility, Site	Bristol cluster, Berlin cluster
Description	This test deploys an experiment to the testbed of Bristol and Patras. During this field trial, an experiment with two network services will be deployed to the multiple inter-facilities edges.
Executed by	Partner: DCAT Date:
Purpose	All the resources belonging to the experiment are deployed and configured within 90 mins.
Scenario	Refer to the right scenario template used for the test (see Table 5-5)
Slice Configuration	
Components involved	<p>Components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OpenStack - OSM - K8s cluster - 5G-VIOS platform. <p>Configurations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Edge proxy is deployed at each edge.

<p>KPIs collected (Metrics collected)</p> <p>Tools involved</p> <p>Results and KPIs Primary Complementary</p> <p>Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Edge is registered with 5G-VIOS - API Gateway, OSM, NetOS, profiler, and monitoring platform are configured with edge proxy. <p>OpenStack is registered with OSM.</p>
	<p>All the resources belonging to the experiment are deployed to the expected infrastructure.</p> <p>Pass/Fail results:</p> <p>Pass: If the experiment deployed correctly within the 90 mins threshold.</p> <p>Fail: If the experiment is not deployed correctly within 90 mins.</p>

Figures 7-6 and 7-7 show the end-to-end test results (latency and Throughput, respectively) between VMs in Bristol and Berlin using OpenVPN over AWS. The latency was measured by ping over 10 minutes and the throughput was measured using Iperf3 for 5 minutes each round.

Figure 7-6 End to End Latency (ms) Bristol to Berlin.

Figure 7-7 DL/UL Throughput benchmark – Bristol to Berlin.

Field	Description
Test Case ID	UHABriBer1
Facility, Site	Bristol and Berlin cluster
Description	Future Mobility – Intercluster edge hopping
Executed by	Partner: UHA Date:
Purpose	To test if the WebRTC Turn/Stun service VM can be moved from Germany to England with Polaron reconnecting.
Scenario	During the disrupted multi-modal travel journey that leads to the parametric insurance trigger event, the passenger moves from Berlin to Bristol that involves different network infrastructure at both ends.
Slice Configuration	N/A
Components involved	5G-VIOS Polaron Engine back-end (Windows, C++, OpenCL, WebRTC). At Urban Hawk’s Bristol office on fiber. Polaron Edge (Stun/Turn VM). Polaron Engine front-end (Android, vanilla Javascript, Web browser).
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	Edge Destruction > Creation > Re-Connection MySQL queries on metrics every 5 seconds P2P & Front-End to Backend metrics
Tools involved	Chrome browser on Laptops in developer mode. Polaron engine back-end in streaming mode with console window logging on.
Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	Failing connection / CORS policy challenge – means a SQL dummy / JSON time series will be amalgamated.

Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)

Managed to reconnect the front and back-ends with 1 test user through the Stun/Turn service first on the Berlin VM then on the Bristol VM.

PASS. Lab.

Field	Description
Test Case ID	UHABriBer2
Facility, Site	Bristol and Berlin cluster
Description	Future Mobility – Pramateric insurance trigger
Executed by	Partner: UHA Date:
Purpose	To simulate the validity of a parametric insurance trigger event based on the data available in the hybrid spatial model on the locations involved.
Scenario	A disruption in the multi-modal travel journey leads to the parametric insurance trigger event.
Slice Configuration	N/A
Components involved	<p>Polaron Engine back-end (Windows, C++, OpenCL, WebRTC). At Urban Hawk's Bristol office on fiber.</p> <p>Polaron Edge (Stun/Turn VM).</p> <p>Polaron Engine front-end (Android, vanilla Javascript, Web browser).</p>
KPIs collected (Metrics collected)	<p>User's location (from the smartphone's GPS via the webbrowser in https)</p> <p>Timestamp</p> <p>Submitted (drawn into the map) obstruction</p>
Tools involved	Chrome browser on Laptops in developer mode. Polaron engine back-end in streaming mode with console window logging on.

Results and KPIs Primary Complementary	User location, timestamp, and the data received at back-end. That paired with a social media scraping/monitoring service that also identifies a potential riot in the area can trigger the parametric insurance event.
Target metric/KPI and verification (pass/fail)	PASS. Lab.

7.3.3 Conclusions – Lessons learned

During designing the inter-cluster communication as well as the demonstration we faced challenges such as:

- Setting up the network connection between two clusters’ testbeds (VPN protocols, internal policies, ip/vlan availability/loops, security concerns, etc.) had lots of discussions and challenges. Which was resulted in implementing the Berlin-Bristol connectivity using AWS. This needed lots of Coordination among partners to implement the inter-cluster UC demos.
- Due to technical challenges in the coordination of the 5G-VIOS platform across the Berlin & Bristol clusters, the final intercluster demo was not able to be show on time.

However, based on the demo work performed by **UHA** in preparation for this, from scanning the Berlin Central station, to simulating the interfaces between 2D and 3D planning, as well as end user device tests using COTS (non-5G but Wi-Fi enabled devices) we were able to “mock up” the Berlin components of the demo.

As Bristol is our base – **UHA** had previously conducted many tests on our own and with the Bristol cluster, including validating the 5G-VIOS platforms ability to move and resume the QCOW2 image containing the WebRTC services.

7.3.4 Vertical business KPI validation

Working with the **IZT** team, **UHA** was able to eliminate two different UCs as likely not being commercially viable. From this we moved to the model of offering both a data driven edge based service, as well as tying into other systems and functionality (for instance SQL, NoSQL and Graph based services).

This allows us to offer a service that augments the passenger experience, can be embedded into existing systems and run at the edge, providing both resilience and the means to tie into local or external data feeds in order to query the real world and passenger events, in order to calculate routes and parametric insurance triggers.

The mock trials and previous tests, suggest that the latency and localisation of services offer a lot of benefits to the end user performance and even the possibility to offload some processes directly to the edge.

Having both the network processes and cached services run in this container might offer enhanced benefits of both performance and scale - in effect being able to adopt a hybrid approach and ensure real-time transport planning and output to both insurers, customers and operators alike.

8 Conclusions

This deliverable report describes the execution of the final trials of the 5G-VICTORI project that have taken place during the last year of the project. 5G-VICTORI UCs have been executed at the vertical facility sites, where the 5G deployments have been integrated the vertical facilities sites that corresponding UC are delivered by and in all cases have been enhanced with features that are required to meet the expected KPIs both at network and service levels.

As indicated in the previous deliverable (D4.2), the maturity of testing at each facility varies according to the level of integration that had to be performed among the vertical applications and the 5G-VICTORI elements deployed in each facility. In some cases extension of the 5G facility through newly deployed transport extensions is performed to allow executing the field trials in the vertical operational environment. Despite difficulties in accessing the sites and scheduling the trials in some of the vertical premises (train station in Berlin and railway track in the Patras cluster, HV environments in Patras cluster, etc.), the field trials were executed successfully. Moreover, all testing results in the field trials have exhibited very good performance in support of the vertical services and 5G KPIs.

Specifically, the conclusion for each facility is described on a per UC basis:

For the **Berlin** cluster, 5G is a suitable technology for streaming remote rendered 3D applications (**UC #1.2**) since it has proved in an operational environment that reliability and other QoS parameters (particularly latency) can be guaranteed. For the digital twin part of the UC, 5G provided sufficient bandwidth and latency for the render streaming and user interaction parts, which will be enhance in future networks beyond 5G. Multiple concurrent users could connect without breaking the service, and that is promising. **UC #1.3** services were fully tested in an operational environment with success. QoS has been implemented to differentiate between connections that need to be are prioritized over secondary ones. The results are promising and useful for the vertical industries involved, despite the limitations in discriminating MC services (5QIs) due to RAN constraints. **UC #3** was delivered using mmWave as the wireless transport technology providing track-to-train connectivity. A datarate of up to 1.6 Gbps has been obtained in two field trials in operational environments. The goal of caching large amounts of video data to the train server in the order of 7GB within relatively short 30s intervals has been shown viable when utilising high-bandwidth mmWave wireless links. In addition, 5G has been assessed in paralell to the initial trial in a lab environment using the nomadic 5G node. The results stemming from the use of 5G reveal that still mmWaves underperform 5G in both data rate and latency, given the high modulation bandwidth of the former, and we need to wait until 6G to balance this comparison.

In the Patras facility 5 fully operational 5G network deployments have been implemented, and a full end-to-end transport deployment has been prepared for executing the Patras 5G-VICTORI UCs. Four UCs, i.e. **UC #1.1**, **UC #2**, **UC #3** and **UC #4**, have been deployed at the vertical facilities in large scale heterogeneous environments and have deployed several services (counting 10 services over 4 vertical and cross vertical industries). All UCs have been demonstrated as large scale field trials in 2023, all integrated in operational vertical facilities with very interesting results. **UC #1.1** provided 5G connectivity on board while the operational train was moving along an operational railtrack. The mobility management framework that was developed for 5G-VICTORI supported connectivity over a 4 node transport network of various technologies that was deployed for the purposes of **UC #1.1** large scale trials, which proved to be very tedious with respect to the design and deployment of the network technologies. The **KCC** Mission Critical Solution based on MCx / FRMCS deployed both at the **TRA** trials and Berlin trials provided important insights for the specific service deployment. **UC #2** services were fully tested in an **ADMIE** operational environment, despite the limitations in hardware deployment in those HV facilities. End to end network slicing was achieved and private network solutions with two 5G indoor configurations was exhibited. **UC #3.1** was deployed at the **TRA** facility with performed in the field, the lab results of the previous two phases

were validated, for both the vCDN and the Surveillance services. Finally, **UC #4** was deployed at **TRA** facility where innovative service deployment unveiled benefits of 5G for the specific vertical industry.

The **FR/RO** cluster and its deployment in **AIM** has validated the performance and the functionality of the implemented field trials. This particular 5G-VICTORI deployment is one of the first 5G SA OpenRAN/Open Core implementations in operational environments, demonstrating the maturity of the technology at this moment and business potential that can rise on top of this open implementations. All **UC#1.2** objectives have been achieved based on the OAI RAN/Core solution implemented. The results in terms of 5G SA service communication and UCs experimentation in the field have been successful, both in terms of the 5G SA network integration and deployment, to the network configuration and UC onboarding on top of the 5G SA system. For **UC #4.2** the services were validated successfully, as it was possible to preserve connections across the same/cross-technology networks. The scenarios supported by the infrastructure design allowed municipalities to run LV real-time measurements services, through suitable slice implementation. The required vertical services has been appropriately delivered by exploiting LV measurements in the municipality having a view of the network and supporting LV monitoring through the 5G network..

UNIVBRIS designed, integrated and deployed a fully operational network, meeting all of the requirements and successfully delivering service provisioning for the field trial. A non-stationary network edge, namely the Nomadic Node, was also deployed to provide the functionality required for **Apps 1** and **3**. In addition, the set of different solutions and services developed by the partners involved in the Bristol demonstration were fully integrated to the already existing testbed as well as the newly created Nomadic Node. For **App1**, **MATI** tested both the synchronization and caching services on multiple devices running in parallel. For **App2**, **MATI** tested live streaming of 360 video on multiple devices with edge caching enabled. Both tests were run successfully, meeting the required KPIs and providing the expected quality of experience. For **App3**, **UHA** ran some basic tests of their solution where their application was implemented based on WebRTC and data streaming from the Cloud (MVB – HPN lab) to the edges over 5G connection. With additional integration of a GPU at the edge node and further testing **App3** application services at the edge node could have created a better user experience for **App3**. Due to the limitations during the field trial the GPU resources were not available at any of the edges.

5G-VIOS was fully integrated to the 5GUK testbed and all the edges, including the Nomadic Node. **App1** and **App2** were fully integrated to the 5G-VIOS ecosystem, supporting a dynamic end-to-end service creation and deletion at any network location (HPN, M Shed, WTC, Nomadic Node) while also storing the measured KPIs at each edge and then sharing them with the central profiling service. The deployment of **App3** has been verified and the migration of **App3** from the M Shed edge to the HPN edge has been successfully tested allowing service continuation after migration.

UHA provided a QCOW2 image to Bristol University, who were able to install and operate this on their 5G-VIOS platform. Tests were conducted to demonstrate that an image could be moved between instances and containers, then resumed in a new location. Since the QCOW2 image and WebRTC component could then reconnect using the infra from other systems in the network as well as the NAT negotiation offered by the STUN / TURN services of WebRTC. Tests were conducted to demonstrate how the component would be moved between each location, and a fiber connection to each, and internet connection provided the means to validate the performance of the WebRTC > Polaron connections as well as the end user device input and overall latencies.

Finally, two inter-cluster trials have been executed involving 5G-VIOS and the verticals that provide the service(s) across the 5G facilities: Bristol – Patras and Bristol – Berlin. Regarding the former, **MATI**'s inter-cluster proposed application involves a training course hosted at **UNIVBRIS**, being offered to **UoP**, using capabilities of **MATI**, 5G-VIOS and 5G-UK test network. The results obtained guarantee more than 10 Mbps per user and latencies < 60s. Regarding the latter, and despite the

connectivity challenges between the clusters, **UHA** succeeded to move and resume the WebRTC service across sites for a mock-up business trip of a traveller between the cities. The measured KPIs ensure a proper execution of the service.

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